

On Grothendieck constants, type B Catalan numbers, and Fourier series.

Roberto Alfano^{1,2}

¹The Institution of Engineering and Technology, Futures Place, Kings Way, Stevenage SG1 2UA, Hertfordshire, England, United Kingdom.

²Computationally Intelligent Systems & Signals Laboratory, University of Manitoba, Winnipeg R3T 5V6, Manitoba, Canada.

E-mail: roberto.alfano@physics.org

Abstract In functional analysis, the upper bound of Grothendieck inequality in ∞ -dimensional Hilbert space defines fundamental relationships across several strands of mathematics. Is its action felt in analytic number theory and in analytic combinatorics? For the former, we considered the explicit bounds established by the theorems of Krivine, König and Tomczak-Jaegermann, and Braverman et al. For the latter, we considered Flajolet and Sedgewick analyses of the Eulerian distribution of triangular functions convergent to the bell-shaped curve of Gaussian density, as any of those for which a local limit law holds. We searched for closed-form expressions connecting special cases of Apéry-type series of reciprocals of type B Catalan numbers or central binomial coefficients; Dirichlet L -series; generalised Stieltjes constant $\gamma_1(m/8)$; Euler-Kronecker constant γ_8 of the global field $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{8})$, etc. We identify recurring closed-form expressions involving the pair $(\pi, \sqrt{8})$ across combinatorial, analytic, and operator-theoretic quantities. We show that Braverman et al. theorem is based on the same algebraic integer λ that Apéry used to prove the Riemann zeta-function $\zeta(3)$ irrationality. Appendix D is Davie's proof of the theorem establishing the lower bounds of Grothendieck inequality.

Keywords Central binomial coefficient, type B Catalan numbers, Grothendieck's constant, Dirichlet L -series, Eulerian distribution, global-to-local reduction, local limit law

MSC 2020 11B65 11E39 11G40 11M06 11R52 11Z05 42A16 42B05 42C10

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1. Introduction.

Seventy-three years ago, Grothendieck [1] discovered a connection between Banach spaces, like \mathcal{L}_∞ , \mathcal{L}_1 , and \mathcal{L}_2 , which implies the existence of universal constants, denoted K_G . Over \mathbb{R}^∞ , it holds:

Theorem 1.0. (Alon, Makarychev, Makarychev, and Naor [16, p. 500 (1)]). *For every $n \times m$ matrix (a_{ij}) and every choice of unit vectors $x_1, \dots, x_n, y_1, \dots, y_m \in S^{n+m-1}$ there exists a choice of signs $\varepsilon_1, \dots, \varepsilon_n, \delta_1, \dots, \delta_m \in \{-1, +1\}$ for which*

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m a_{ij} \langle x_i, y_j \rangle \leq K_G \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m a_{ij} \varepsilon_i \delta_j \quad (1.0)$$

1.1 König and Tomczak-Jaegermann theorem for Lebesgue measurable functions.

Let us denote as (Ω, μ) a space Ω of measure μ , and as $f, g \in L_\infty(\Omega, \mu; \ell_2)$ a pair of bounded measurable functions over the Hilbert space \mathcal{H} . Let us denote as $K \in L_1(\Omega \times \Omega, \mu \times \mu)$ the odd oscillatory Gaussian kernel $K : \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^n |_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ which is the imaginary part of the Gaussian Fourier transform [2, p. 185], [4, p. 5 (1.4)], [64, pp. 467–530]–[66]:

$$K(\vec{x}, \vec{y}) := \frac{\sin(\langle \vec{x}, \vec{y} \rangle)}{\sqrt{e^{\|\vec{x}\|_2^2 + \|\vec{y}\|_2^2}}} \Big|_{\vec{x}, \vec{y} \in \mathbb{R}^n} \quad (1.1)$$

1.1.1 Bilinear form $B_K(f, g)$.

In 2000, König and Tomczak-Jaegermann, argued that:

Conjecture 1.1. (König and Tomczak-Jaegermann [2, p. 185 (1.1)], [3], [4, p. 5 Conjecture 1.3]). *If $B_K(f, g)$ denotes a bilinear form $B_K : \mathcal{L}_\infty(\mathbb{R}^n) \times \mathcal{L}_\infty(\mathbb{R}^n) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ given by [4, p. 5 (1.5)]*

$$B_K(f, g) := \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} f(\vec{x}) g(\vec{y}) \frac{\sin(\langle \vec{x}, \vec{y} \rangle)}{\sqrt{e^{\|\vec{x}\|_2^2 + \|\vec{y}\|_2^2}}} d\vec{x} d\vec{y}$$

defining $f_0 : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow [-1, 1]_{\mathbb{R}}$ by $f_0(\vec{x}_1, \vec{x}_2, \dots, \vec{x}_n) = \text{sign}(\vec{x})$ then $B_K(f, g) \leq B_K(f_0, f_0), \forall n \in \mathbb{N}, \forall f, g : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow [-1, 1]_{\mathbb{R}}$.

Those authors attempted to express the upper bound of Grothendieck's inequality in the Hilbert space $\mathcal{H} \in \mathbb{R}^\infty$ in terms of two-dimensional spherical integral operators [2, p. 187 (2.1)] as

$$K_G^{\mathbb{R}} \geq \frac{\int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty f(\vec{x})g(\vec{y}) \frac{\sin(\langle \vec{x}, \vec{y} \rangle)}{\sqrt{e^{\|\vec{x}\|_2^2 + \|\vec{y}\|_2^2}}} d\vec{x}d\vec{y}}{\int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty \text{sign}(\vec{x})\text{sign}(\vec{y}) \frac{\sin(\langle \vec{x}, \vec{y} \rangle)}{\sqrt{e^{\|\vec{x}\|_2^2 + \|\vec{y}\|_2^2}}} d\vec{x}d\vec{y}} = \frac{\pi}{2 \log(1 + \sqrt{2})} \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{n+1}{2}\right)^2 {}_2F_1\left(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}; \frac{n}{2} + 1; -1\right)}{\Gamma\left(\frac{n}{2}\right)\Gamma\left(\frac{n+1}{2}\right)} \tag{1.2}$$

According to **Conjecture 1.1**, in the limit $n \rightarrow \infty$ (1.2) reduces to the first factor of the RHS. Namely, Krivine’s bound. The rightmost factor in (1.2) represents the solution to the special case ${}_2F_1(2^{-1}, 2^{-1}; 2^{-1}n + 1; -1)$ of the hypergeometric differential equation $y = {}_qF_{q-1}(a, b; c; z)$ [63, pp. 1014–27]. König and Tomczak-Jaegermann obtained it by applying [63, p. 824 (7.525/1)] to [63, p. 824 (7.525/1)]. These functions and operators lead to the integration of expectation values of powers of inner products of random, uniformly distributed vectors on the sphere.

1.1.2 $n = 1$ dimensional Krivine rounding schemes.

On 31 March 2011, Braverman, Makarychev, Makarychev, and Naor [4, p. 11] reanalysed the Krivine’s upper bound of Grothendieck’s inequality in the Hilbert space $\mathcal{H} \in \mathbb{R}^\infty$. They demonstrated that Krivine rounding schemes hold in the $n = 1$ dimensional case [4, p. 8 Definition 2.1]. Thus, confirming the $n = 1$ dimensional case of (1.2) [2, p. 187 (2.1)], [3]:

Theorem 1.2. (König and Tomczak-Jaegermann [3]–[4, pp. 6 34–40 Theorem 1.4 (1.6)]). *For every Lebesgue measurable function $f, g : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \{-1, 1\}$, we have*

$$\int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty f(\vec{x})g(\vec{y}) \frac{\sin(\langle \vec{x}, \vec{y} \rangle)}{\sqrt{e^{\|\vec{x}\|_2^2 + \|\vec{y}\|_2^2}}} d\vec{x}d\vec{y} \tag{1.3}$$

$$\leq \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty \text{sign}(\vec{x})\text{sign}(\vec{y}) \frac{\sin(\langle \vec{x}, \vec{y} \rangle)}{\sqrt{e^{\|\vec{x}\|_2^2 + \|\vec{y}\|_2^2}}} d\vec{x}d\vec{y} \rightarrow I_1 = \sqrt{8} \log(1 + \sqrt{2}) \approx 2.49290 \tag{1.4}$$

Moreover, (1.3) equals (1.4) only when $f(\vec{x}) = g(\vec{x}) = \text{sign}(\vec{x})$ almost everywhere or when $f(\vec{x}) = g(\vec{x}) = -\text{sign}(\vec{x})$ almost everywhere.

We refer to templates such as [8, A#####] as codes from The Online Encyclopedia of Integer Sequences [8]. Let us denote as $B_K(f, g)$, the bilinear form (1.3), and as M its supremum. Braverman et al. demonstrated that [4, p. 5 (1.5)], [4, pp. 34–6], [8, A196525]

$$M := \sup B_K(f, g) = \sup_{\substack{f, g \in L_\infty(0, \infty) \\ f, g \in [-1, 1] \\ \text{almost} \\ \text{everywhere}}} \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty f(\vec{x})g(\vec{y}) \frac{\sin(\langle \vec{x}, \vec{y} \rangle)}{\sqrt{e^{\|\vec{x}\|_2^2 + \|\vec{y}\|_2^2}}} d\vec{x}d\vec{y} = M_0 = \frac{\log(1 + \sqrt{2})}{\sqrt{2}} \tag{1.5}$$

whose minimal, irreducible monic polynomial is $x^2 - 2x + 2^{-1}$. Furthermore, they proved:

Corollary 1.3. (Braverman et al. [4, p. 10 Corollary 2.3]). *Assume that $f, g : \mathbb{R}^k \rightarrow [-1, 1]_{\mathbb{R}}$ is a Krivine rounding scheme. Then [8, A088367]*

$$K_G^{\mathbb{R}} \leq \frac{1}{c(f, g)} \tag{1.6}$$

Lemma 1.4. (Braverman et al. [4, p. 11 Lemma 2.4]). *Let $f, g : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a Krivine rounding scheme. Then*

$$c(f, g) \leq \frac{2 \log(1 + \sqrt{2})}{\pi} \tag{1.7}$$

(see sections 2.14–5 and [8, A355186]) which indicates that there exists a one-dimensional Krivine rounding scheme $c(f, g) \leq c(\text{sign}(\vec{x}), \text{sign}(\vec{y}))$ among all schemes $f, g : \mathbb{R}^1 \rightarrow [-1, 1]_{\mathbb{R}}$. Thus, making unnecessary \mathbb{R}^1 partitions more complicated than the half-line partition. In 2012, Naor and Regev [13] demonstrated that, working with Krivine’s rounding schemes over $\mathbb{R}^k \Big|_{k \rightarrow \infty}$, the Krivine bound $K_G^{\mathbb{R}}$ follows.

1.1.3 $|K_G - K_G^{\mathbb{R}}| \leq 8.23 \times 10^{-457}$.

Theorem 1.5. (Braverman et al. [4, p. 4 Theorem 1.1]). *There exists $\varepsilon_0 > 0$ such that*

$$K_G < \frac{\pi}{2 \log(1 + \sqrt{2})} - \varepsilon_0 \tag{1.8}$$

and quoting [4, p. 4]: “We chose not to state an explicit new upper bound on the Grothendieck constant since we know that our result is suboptimal”. Very recently, Heilman’s [30] inspected **Theorem 1.5**’s proof. At several different steps, the proof (part 5) [4, pp. 26–33] of the main result of [4, p. 4 Theorem 1.1] includes non-explicit constants. For example, using a Taylor expansion without an explicit error term. Heilman made explicit all constants. In a sequel to this paper, we are going to present the proof that the difference of the Grothendieck and Krivine bounds is [30, p. 7]:

$$|K_G - K_G^{\mathbb{R}}| \leq \frac{\pi \delta_0}{2 \log(1 + \sqrt{2})(\log(1 + \sqrt{2}) + \delta_0)} \Big|_{\delta_0 \geq 4.07123102832 \times 10^{-457}} \leq 8.23 \times 10^{-457} \quad (1.9)$$

Remark 1.6. (Braverman et al. [4, p. 33 Remark 5.6]). Assume that $f, g : \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow [-1, 1]_{\mathbb{R}}$ are measurable functions and consider the function $H : \mathbb{S} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ given by

$$H(z) = \frac{1}{2\pi(1-z^2)} \int_{\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2} \frac{f(\vec{x})g(\vec{y})}{\sqrt{e^{\| \vec{x} \|_2^2 + \| \vec{y} \|_2^2 - 2z \langle \vec{x}, \vec{y} \rangle}}} d\vec{x}d\vec{y} \quad (1.10)$$

Assume that:

$$B_K(f, g) > 4\pi \log(1 + \sqrt{2}) \in \mathbb{C} \setminus \mathbb{A} \subset \mathcal{P} \subset \mathbb{C} \approx 11.07566 \quad (1.11)$$

where B_K is König's bilinear form:

$$B_K(f, g) := \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} f(\vec{x})g(\vec{y}) \frac{\sin(\langle \vec{x}, \vec{y} \rangle)}{\sqrt{e^{\| \vec{x} \|_2^2 + \| \vec{y} \|_2^2}}} d\vec{x}d\vec{y} \quad (1.12)$$

Then, one can repeat the proof of **Theorem 1.5** with H_η replaced by H , to arrive at the same conclusion.

1.2 Grothendieck constants $K_G > 1$ meet combinatorial classes in \mathbb{R}^4 .

1.2.1 An update on correlations between spacelike separated surfaces in \mathbb{R}^4 .

Section 1.2.1 provides an update on the physics underlying evaluations of Grothendieck constants that violate Bell's inequalities. In 1970, Penrose [88] delivered a series of lectures at the University of Pittsburgh, where techniques of differential topology were applied to special relativity, including the spacelike separations at the focus of Tsirel'son's [11] foundational paper. In 1984, Penrose and Rindler [89, pp. 8–32], [90, pp. 110] detailed the relationship between the Riemann sphere [69, pp. 117–52], and Minkowski vector spaces of special relativity, which correspond to events' tangent spaces of general relativity. To honor Penrose, we illustrate the pseudo-Euclidean geometric support of Grothendieck constants that violate Bell's inequalities reproducing a foundational sketch he drew, as **Figure 1**. Let us denote as $\mathbb{M} \subset \mathbb{R}^4$ the connected oriented linear affine homogeneous isotropic, time-oriented, pseudo-Euclidean, Lorentzian vector space, endowed with a bilinear inner product of signature $(+ - - -)$, called Minkowski space. Let $(T, X, Y, Z) \in \mathbb{R}^4$ denote the coordinates of a null vector in the Minkowski vector space \mathbb{V} , which satisfy the equation $T^2 - X^2 - Y^2 - Z^2 = 0$. Let S^-, S^+ denote a pair of abstract spheres whose elements are, respectively, past and future null directions. Let us denote as S^-, S and S^+ Riemann spheres of Argand planes, which,

Figure 1. The limit case $K_G^{\mathbb{R}}$ of Grothendieck constant, corresponds to points $P(T, X, Y, Z)$ in the *elsewhere* subspace of $\mathbb{M} \subset \mathbb{R}^4$ external to the bicone, such that $T^2 - X^2 - Y^2 - Z^2 < 0$ or external to the Riemann spheres of Argand planes, S^- , S and S^+ .

in the subspace $(X, Y, Z) \in \mathbb{E}^3$, are spheres with an equation $x^2 + y^2 + z^2 = 1$ [69, pp. 117–52]. Since 1967, Penrose has identified the one-complex projective hypersurface denoted $\mathbb{C}\mathbb{P}^1 \cong \mathbb{R}^4$ by the twistor whose representation in **Figure 1** is the Riemann sphere of the Argand plane S^- [87, pp. 478–88]–[90], [92]–[95]. At the right side of **Figure 1**, the abstract sphere S^- is a representation of the *celestial sphere* at an arbitrarily-chosen origin point $O(T, X, Y, Z) = O(0, 0, 0, 0)$. The latter, is true provided no *obstruction* [72, pp. 253–69] exists between corresponding points in S^- and S^- . The point $O(0, 0, 0, 0)$ is assumed stationary relative to a restricted tetrad of linearly independent vectors $\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{z} : \mathbf{U} = T\mathbf{t} + X\mathbf{x} + Y\mathbf{y} + Z\mathbf{z}$. **Figure 1** does not show the corresponding abstract sphere S^+ called the *anti-celestial sphere*. Symbols S^-, S, S^+ denote intersections of, respectively, the *past, present* and *future null cones*, with the hyperplanes $T(-1, 0, 1)$. Each future-pointing null vector is invariantly and uniquely associated with a past-pointing null vector. For given boundary conditions, a null cone’s surface is characterized by minimal surface area. The two-wedge region of $\mathbb{M} \subset \mathbb{R}^4$, external to the bicone, is called *elsewhere*. In 1961, Borchers [110] demonstrated that the algebra of observables in an open set corresponds to the algebra of observables in a larger open set, called the *timelike envelope*, and proved the so-called *timelike tube* theorem for non-gravitational quantum fields in $\mathbb{M} \subset \mathbb{R}^4$. In 1985, Tsirel’son [11, p. 567] connected the Krivine bound $K_G^{\mathbb{R}}$ to correlations between quantum systems into domains with spacelike separation. Penrose clarified that the space **Figure 1** depicts is over \mathbb{R}^4 iff we ignore four further dimensions which the geometry of Lie finite reflection groups dictates [123], arising by reflections in the chambers. Hence, Grothendieck constant evaluations such as $K_G^{\mathbb{R}}$ have relationship to the space $\mathbb{M} \subset \mathbb{R}^8 \cong \mathbb{C}^4 \cong \mathbb{O}$. Positive evaluations characterize points $P(T, X, Y, Z)$, in the elsewhere

subspace of $\mathbb{M} \subset \mathbb{R}^4$ external to the light-cone, such that the spacetime interval is an imaginary number $T^2 - X^2 - Y^2 - Z^2 < 0$. As early as 1988, Summers and Werner [108] proved that the Reeh-Schlieder [109] property is responsible for those maximal violations of Bell's inequalities in quantum field theory. In 2022, Vourdas [27] demonstrated that the Grothendieck inequality formalism applies to single quantum systems. In 2024, Strohmeier and Witten [111] extended Borchers' theorem to quantum fields on real-analytic curved spacetimes and, on that ground, very recently Guo, He, and Zhang [112] showed that *timelike* entanglement entropy is closely related to spacelike entanglement entropy. We recall a theorem of differential topology [73], [74] relevant to Riemann surfaces [69, pp. 247–393] which, in 2004, Mikhalkin proved:

Theorem 1.7. (Mikhalkin [73, p. 1035]). *Every smooth complex projective hypersurface of arbitrary dimension $\mathbb{C}\mathbb{P}^{n+1}$, $n \in [0, \infty)_{\mathbb{Z}}$ admits a decomposition into primitive topological objects called pairs-of-pants, each diffeomorphic to a Riemann sphere minus 3 points.*

1.2.2 Combinatorial classes are surfaces in \mathbb{R}^4 .

Definition 1.8. (Flajolet and Sedgewick [49, p. 16 Definition I.1.]). *A combinatorial class or simply a class is a finite or denumerable set where we define a size function, which satisfies the conditions:*

- (i) *The size of an element is $\alpha \in \mathbb{N}_0$.*
- (ii) *Any given size has a finite number of elements.*

The graph of the generating function of a combinatorial class, considered as a function $C : \mathbb{C} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$, is a Riemann surface [69, pp. 247–393]. Therefore, based on its enumerative properties, Flajolet and Sedgewick [49, p. 12] envision a combinatorial class as a surface in \mathbb{R}^4 .

1.3 Structure of the paper.

Section 1 reviews known theorems of operator space theory that we will use in Section 2. Section 2 focuses on the invariants in the König's and Tomczak-Jaegermann's theorem [2]–[4, pp. 6 34–40 Theorem 1.4] for Lebesgue measurable functions. It indicates relationships with certain special functions of mathematical physics [61]–[66], [75]–[82], [116], [125]. Section 2 examines constants in **Conjecture 1.1**, **Theorem 1.2**, **Corollary 1.3**, **Lemma 1.4**, **Theorem 1.5**, and **Remark 1.6** in their unexplored number-theoretic ground. The appendices review several salient details that section 2 applies to section 1 constants. **Appendix A** outlines the notation, evaluation, and representations of selected quadratic Dirichlet L -series, zeta-regularised infinite product of natural numbers, super-regularised product over all prime numbers, Plouffe constant P_A [37], [122], semifactorial and central binomial coefficients or type B Catalan numbers. **Appendix B** defines Pisot-Vijayaraghavan numbers. Moreover, it shows representations of the logarithm of the Pisot-Vijayaraghavan number $1 + \sqrt{2}$. **Appendix C** gives the Euler-Kronecker constant γ_8 of the global field $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{8})$. **Appendix D** is Davie's proof of the famous theorem which, in 1984, established the lower bounds $K_{\mathbb{C}}^{\mathbb{F}}$ of the Grothendieck's inequality in $\mathcal{H} \in \mathbb{R}^{\infty}$ and $\mathcal{H} \in \mathbb{C}^{\infty}$. Davie's theorem is referenced by these [12], one monograph [28, p. 5], and papers [8, p. 200], [10, pp. 328–9], [15, p. 10 (20–1)], [30], [31]. In 1991, unaware of Davie's proof, Reeds [19, p. 10 Theorem 3] reached a similar unpublished result.

2. An analytic number-theoretical perspective of König theorem.

Special values of Dirichlet L -series [33, pp. 97–112], [41, [91, pp. 95–144], [99] and of their special case, called Riemann zeta-functions, encode significant arithmetic information and often admit closed-form expressions involving fundamental constants. One of the reasons lies in their proven *universality*. The latter is an extension of the Voronin’s 1975 theorem for Riemann zeta-functions, for which we refer the reader to Matsumoto’s [91, pp. 95–144] survey and the very recent Petrović’s [124] monograph. On this ground, section 2 demonstrates that section 1’s enunciations and certain fundamental constants of mathematical physics admit closed-form expressions.

2.1 König bilinear form $B_K(f, g)$ supremum and Dirichlet L -series $L_8(1)$.

Lemma 2.0. *The quadratic Dirichlet L -series $L_8(1)$ of determinant $D = 2$ and fundamental unit of norm 1 and the supremum of König’s bilinear form $B_K(f, g)$, on $\vec{x} \in [0, \infty)_{\mathbb{R}}$ have the same exact evaluation:*

$$\sup_{\substack{f, g \in L_{\infty}(0, \infty) \\ f, g \in [-1, 1] \\ \text{almost} \\ \text{everywhere}}} \int_0^{\infty} \int_0^{\infty} f(\vec{x})g(\vec{y}) \frac{\sin(\langle \vec{x}, \vec{y} \rangle)}{\sqrt{e^{\|\vec{x}\|_2^2 + \|\vec{y}\|_2^2}}} d\vec{x}d\vec{y} = M_0 = L_8(1) = \frac{\log(1 + \sqrt{2})}{\sqrt{2}} \quad (2.1)$$

Proof. The exact evaluations (1.5) and (A.1) are identical. Hence:

$$M_0 = L_8(1) = \frac{\log(1 + \sqrt{2})}{\sqrt{2}} \approx 0.623225 \in \mathbb{C} \setminus \mathbb{A} \subset \mathcal{P} \subset \mathbb{C} \quad (2.2)$$

The claim follows. ■

2.2 A Dirichlet series analog of the König and Tomczak-Jaegermann theorem.

Theorem 2.1. (König and Tomczak-Jaegermann [2]–[4, pp. 6 38–40 Theorem 1.4]). *For every Lebesgue measurable function $f, g : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \{-1, 1\}$ that identity between evaluations holds*

$$L_8(1) = M_0 \leq I_1 = 4 L_8(1) \quad (2.3)$$

Moreover, equality is attained only when $f(\vec{x}) = g(\vec{x}) = \text{sign}(\vec{x})$ almost everywhere, or when $f(\vec{x}) = g(\vec{x}) = -\text{sign}(\vec{x})$ almost everywhere.

Proof. The ratio of (1.4) to (2.1) is equal to:

$$I_1 M_0^{-1} = 4 \log(1 + \sqrt{2}) (\log(1 + \sqrt{2}))^{-1} = 4 \tag{2.4}$$

Then, in **Theorem 1.2** (1.4) is quadruple of $M := \sup B_K(f, g) = M_0$. Hence, the evaluation of the Dirichlet L -series of determinant $D = 2$ and fundamental unit E of norm 1 is equal to that which defines the bounds of the König's theorem: $L_8(1) = M_0 \leq I_1 = 4 L_8(1)$. The claim follows. ■

2.3 Krivine bound as quotient of Dirichlet L -series $L_{\mp 8}(1)$ of symmetric determinants.

Theorem 2.2. *The quotient of Dirichlet L -series $L_{\mp 8}(1)$ of symmetric determinants $D = \mp 2$ and the Grothendieck's inequality Krivine bound $K_G^{\mathbb{R}} \leq c(f, g)^{-1}$ over $\mathcal{H}^{\mathbb{R}}$ have the same evaluation:*

$$K_G^{\mathbb{R}} \leq \frac{1}{c(f, g)} \leq \frac{L_{-8}(1)}{L_8(1)} \tag{2.5}$$

Proof. The ratio of the Dirichlet L -series $L_{-8}(1)$ (A.3) [8, A093954] to $L_8(1)$ (A.1) or (2.1) is

$$\frac{L_{-8}(1)}{L_8(1)} = \frac{\pi}{\sqrt{8}} \frac{\sqrt{2}}{\log(1 + \sqrt{2})} = \frac{\pi}{2 \log(1 + \sqrt{2})} \geq \frac{1}{c(f, g)} \geq K_G^{\mathbb{R}} \tag{2.6}$$

The quotient is the evaluation of Krivine's bound. The claim follows. ■

2.4 Sums and differences of Dirichlet L -series and the Krivine's bound $K_G^{\mathbb{R}}$.

Corollary 2.3. *The Krivine bound $K_G^{\mathbb{R}} \leq c(f, g)^{-1}$ over $\mathcal{H}^{\mathbb{R}}$ and the Dirichlet L -series $L_{\mp 8}(1)$ of symmetric determinants $D = \mp 2$ and fundamental unit of norm 1, have closed-form expression*

$$\frac{1 - K_G^{\mathbb{R}}}{1 + K_G^{\mathbb{R}}} \leq \frac{L_8(1) - L_{-8}(1)}{L_{-8}(1) + L_8(1)} \tag{2.7}$$

Proof. Based on **Theorem 2.2**, we can express the Krivine bound $K_G^{\mathbb{R}}$ [8, A088367] as a function of the difference and sum of the Dirichlet L -series $L_{\mp 8}(1)$ by rewriting equation (2.5) as

$$\frac{K_G^{\mathbb{R}} - 1}{1 + K_G^{\mathbb{R}}} \leq \frac{L_{-8}(1) - L_8(1)}{L_{-8}(1) + L_8(1)} \tag{2.8}$$

Multiplying both sides of equation (2.8) by -1 yields:

$$\frac{1 - K_G^{\mathbb{R}}}{1 + K_G^{\mathbb{R}}} \leq - \frac{L_{-8}(1) - L_8(1)}{L_{-8}(1) + L_8(1)} \tag{2.9}$$

After **Corollary 1.3**, $c(f, g) K_G^{\mathbb{R}} = 1$. Hence, under those conditions:

$$K_G^{\mathbb{R}}, L_{-8}(1), L_8(1) > 0, K_G^{\mathbb{R}} > 1, L_{-8}(1) > L_8(1) \tag{2.10}$$

$$\frac{1 - K_G^{\mathbb{R}}}{1 + K_G^{\mathbb{R}}} \leq \frac{L_8(1) - L_{-8}(1)}{L_{-8}(1) + L_8(1)} \tag{2.11}$$

The claim follows. ■

2.5 Ratio of König integrals to regularized infinite products.

Let us denote as M_0 the supremum of the bilinear form $B_K(f, g)$, as I_1 the two-dimensional integral (1.4), and as $K_G^{\mathbb{R}}$ the Krivine upper bound of the Grothendieck’s inequality. We denote as $c(f, g)$ the reciprocal of the latter. Let us denote as $\zeta(2)$ the Riemann zeta-function at $s = 2$, as P_A the Plouffe constant A [37], [122] (see section A.3) and as $\alpha_2 \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} 1 + \sqrt{2}$ the algebraic number [8, A014176], [48] which satisfies the minimal polynomial $\alpha^2 - 2\alpha - 1$ (see section B.1, [45]).

Corollary 2.4.

$$\begin{aligned} \sup_{\substack{f, g \in L_\infty(0, \infty) \\ f, g \in [-1, 1] \\ \text{almost} \\ \text{everywhere}}} \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty f(\vec{x})g(\vec{y}) \frac{\sin(\langle \vec{x}, \vec{y} \rangle)}{\sqrt{e^{\|\vec{x}\|_2^2 + \|\vec{y}\|_2^2}}} d\vec{x}d\vec{y} / \prod_p p &= \frac{\log\left((1 + \sqrt{2})^{\sqrt{2}}\right)}{8\pi^2} = M_0 P_A^2 \\ &= \frac{M_0}{24\zeta(2)} \end{aligned} \tag{2.12}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \sup_{\substack{f, g \in L_\infty(0, \infty) \\ f, g \in [-1, 1] \\ \text{almost} \\ \text{everywhere}}} \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty f(\vec{x})g(\vec{y}) \frac{\sin(\langle \vec{x}, \vec{y} \rangle)}{\sqrt{e^{\|\vec{x}\|_2^2 + \|\vec{y}\|_2^2}}} d\vec{x}d\vec{y} / \prod_{k=1}^\infty k &= \frac{\log(1 + \sqrt{2})}{2\sqrt{\pi}} = \sqrt{P_A} M_0 \\ &= \log\left(\alpha_2^{\sqrt{\frac{P_A}{2}}}\right) = \log\left(\sqrt{\pi} \sqrt{\alpha_2^5}\right) \end{aligned} \tag{2.13}$$

$$\int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty \text{sign}(\vec{x})\text{sign}(\vec{y}) \frac{\sin(\langle \vec{x}, \vec{y} \rangle)}{\sqrt{e^{\|\vec{x}\|_2^2 + \|\vec{y}\|_2^2}}} d\vec{x}d\vec{y} / \prod_p p = \frac{\log(1 + \sqrt{2})}{\sqrt{2}\pi^2} = 4P_A^2 M_0 = \frac{M_0}{\pi^2} = \frac{M_0}{6\zeta(2)} \tag{2.14}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty \text{sign}(\vec{x})\text{sign}(\vec{y}) \frac{\sin(\langle \vec{x}, \vec{y} \rangle)}{\sqrt{e^{\|\vec{x}\|_2^2 + \|\vec{y}\|_2^2}}} d\vec{x}d\vec{y} / \prod_{k=1}^\infty k &= \frac{2 \log(1 + \sqrt{2})}{\sqrt{\pi}} = P_A I_1 \\ &= \log\left(\sqrt[{\sqrt{\pi}}]{(1 + \sqrt{2})^2}\right) = \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{K_G} \end{aligned} \tag{2.15}$$

Proof. (i) The ratio of the supremum of the bilinear form (1.5) to the super-regularised product over all prime numbers (A.7), [8, A212002], [44, p. 73 Definition 1] is equal to:

$$M_0 / \prod_p p = \frac{\log(1 + \sqrt{2})}{4\sqrt{2}\pi^2} = \frac{\sqrt{2} \log(1 + \sqrt{2})}{8\pi^2} = \frac{\log\left((1 + \sqrt{2})^{\sqrt{2}}\right)}{8\pi^2} \approx 0.015786 \tag{2.16}$$

The volume of the region of the three-space generated by the 360° revolution of the sine or cosine curve around the x -axis, is given by the identity $\pi^2 = 6 \zeta(2)$ [8, A002388]. Based on the relationships involving the Plouffe constant $P_A = 1/2\pi$ (A.8–9) [37], [122], we have

$$M_0 / \prod_p p = \frac{M_0}{24 \zeta(2)} = \mathcal{P}_A^2 M_0 \tag{2.17}$$

(2.16) and (2.17) are equal to (2.12). (ii) The explicit evaluation of the ratio of the supremum of the bilinear form (1.5), to the zeta-regularised infinite product of natural numbers (A.6) is equal to

$$\begin{aligned} M_0 / \prod_{k=1}^\infty k &= \frac{\log(1 + \sqrt{2})}{\sqrt{2}\sqrt{2\pi}} = \log\left((1 + \sqrt{2})^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{4\pi}}}\right) = \log\left({}^{2\sqrt{\pi}}\sqrt{1 + \sqrt{2}}\right) = \log\left(\alpha_2 \sqrt{\frac{P_A}{2}}\right) \\ &= \sqrt{P_A} M_0 \approx 0.24863 \end{aligned} \tag{2.18}$$

The degree of the radical $2\sqrt{\pi} = \sqrt{\pi}/5 = \sqrt{2/P_A}$ (see [8, A019707]). Hence:

$$M_0 / \prod_{k=1}^{\infty} k = \log \left((1 + \sqrt{2})^{\frac{5}{\sqrt{\pi}}} \right) = \log \left(\sqrt{\pi} \sqrt{\alpha_2^5} \right) \tag{2.19}$$

(2.18) and (2.19) include identities from (2.13). (iii) The evaluation of the ratio between the two-dimensional integral I_1 (1.4) and the super-regularised product over all primes (A.7) is given by:

$$I_1 / \prod_p p = \frac{\log(1 + \sqrt{2})}{\sqrt{2}\pi^2} \approx 0.0631459 \tag{2.20}$$

Based on the relationships of the Plouffe constant P_A (A.9) [37] and of those between the volume of the region of the three-space obtained by the revolution 360° of the sine or cosine curve around the abscissa axis, and the Riemann zeta-function $\zeta(2)$. Hence:

$$I_1 / \prod_p p = 4P_A^2 I_1 = \frac{I_1}{\pi^2} = \frac{I_1}{6 \zeta(2)} \tag{2.21}$$

(2.20) and (2.21) are equal to (2.14). (iv) the ratio the two-dimensional integral I_1 (1.4), to the zeta-regularised infinite product of natural numbers (A.6) is given by:

$$I_1 / \prod_{k=1}^{\infty} k = \frac{2 \log(1 + \sqrt{2})}{\sqrt{\pi}} = \log \left(\sqrt{\pi} \sqrt{(1 + \sqrt{2})^2} \right) = \log \left(\alpha_2^{\frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}}} \right) \approx 0.99452 \tag{2.22}$$

(2.22) includes both leftmost elements of (2.15). Based on the Plouffe constant P_A (A.8–9) [37], [122] and the Krivine bound (1.6) [8, A088367], the following identities hold:

$$I_1 / \prod_{k=1}^{\infty} k = \frac{1}{K_G^{\mathbb{R}} \sqrt{2P_A}} = \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{K_G^{\mathbb{R}}} = P_A I_1 \tag{2.23}$$

(2.23) includes the pair of rightmost terms from equation (2.15). The claim follows. ■

2.6 Generalised Stieltjes constant γ_1 at arbitrary rational arguments.

2.6.1 Introduction.

In the number field $K = \mathbb{Q}$, the Stieltjes constant denoted $\gamma_K = \gamma_{\mathbb{Q}} = \gamma_0 \in \mathbb{C} \setminus \mathbb{A}$ is the Euler-Mascheroni constant γ [8, A001620], [32, pp. 28–39], [34, pp. 4–6], [35]. In 2015, Blagouchine [76] proved a theorem that enables to evaluate generalised Stieltjes constants γ_1 [8, A082633] and γ_2 [8, A086279] at arbitrary rational arguments, like $\{\gamma_1(m/8)\}_{m=1,3,5,8}$.

Example 2.5. The generalised Stieltjes constant $\gamma_1(1/8)$ expression [8, A255188], [77, p. 579]

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma_1\left(\frac{1}{8}\right) &= \gamma_1 + \sqrt{2} \left[\zeta''\left(0, \frac{1}{8}\right) + \zeta''\left(0, \frac{7}{8}\right) \right] + \sqrt{8}\pi \log \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{8}\right) - \sqrt{2}\pi(1 - \sqrt{2}) \log \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{4}\right) - \gamma \\ &\times \left[\frac{\pi}{2}(1 + \sqrt{2}) + 4 \log 2 + \sqrt{2} \log(1 + \sqrt{2}) \right] - \frac{\pi + 8 \log 2 + 2 \log \pi}{\sqrt{2}} \log(1 + \sqrt{2}) - \frac{7(4 - \sqrt{2})}{4} \\ &\times \log^2 2 + \frac{\log 2 \log \pi}{\sqrt{2}} - \frac{\pi(10 + 11\sqrt{2})}{4} \log 2 - \frac{\pi}{2}(3 + \sqrt{8}) \log \pi \approx -16.64171976 \end{aligned} \quad (2.24)$$

In 2017, Coffey [84] investigated the relationships between Stieltjes constants and other fundamental constants in analytic number theory [84, p. 17] stating that

Proposition 2.6. (Coffey [84, p. 9 Proposition 7 (d)]).

$$\frac{\pi^2}{\sqrt{2}} = \frac{1}{8} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^k}{k!} \left(\gamma_k\left(\frac{1}{8}\right) - \gamma_k\left(\frac{3}{8}\right) - \gamma_k\left(\frac{5}{8}\right) + \gamma_k\left(\frac{7}{8}\right) \right) \quad (2.25)$$

(2.25) links π to the generalised Stieltjes constants at rational arguments $\gamma_1(8^{-1}m)|_{m=\{1; 3; 5; 7\}}$.

2.6.2 Supremum of König bilinear form $B_K(f, g)$ and the generalised Stieltjes constant γ_1 .

Proposition 2.7. The supremum $M_0 = \sup B_K(f, g)$ of the bilinear form $B_K(f, g)$, the generalized Stieltjes constant $\{\gamma_1(m/8)\}_{m=1,3,5,8}$ and the super-regularized product over all primes admit the closed-form expression:

$$M_0 = \log(1 + \sqrt{2}) \prod_p p / \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^k}{k!} \left(\gamma_k\left(\frac{1}{8}\right) - \gamma_k\left(\frac{3}{8}\right) - \gamma_k\left(\frac{5}{8}\right) + \gamma_k\left(\frac{7}{8}\right) \right) \quad (2.26)$$

Proof. Multiply both sides of equation (2.25) by 8, obtaining:

$$\sqrt{32}\pi^2 = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^k}{k!} \left(\gamma_k\left(\frac{1}{8}\right) - \gamma_k\left(\frac{3}{8}\right) - \gamma_k\left(\frac{5}{8}\right) + \gamma_k\left(\frac{7}{8}\right) \right) \quad (2.27)$$

The denominator of (2.16) **Corollary 2.5** is identical to the LHS of (2.25).

$$M_0 \left(\prod_p p \right)^{-1} = \frac{\log(1 + \sqrt{2})}{\sqrt{32}\pi^2} \quad (2.28)$$

Replacing the RHS of (2.27) in the denominator of equation (2.28), yields:

$$M_0 = \log(1 + \sqrt{2}) \prod_p p / \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^k}{k!} \left(\gamma_k \left(\frac{1}{8} \right) - \gamma_k \left(\frac{3}{8} \right) - \gamma_k \left(\frac{5}{8} \right) + \gamma_k \left(\frac{7}{8} \right) \right) \quad (2.29)$$

(2.29) is equivalent to (2.26). The claim follows. ■

2.7 The Euler-Kronecker constant γ_8 of the global field $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{8})$.

2.7.1 Krivine bound and the Euler-Kronecker constant γ_8 of the global field $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{8})$.

Section 2.7.1, connects the Krivine bound $K_G^{\mathbb{R}} \leq c(f, g)^{-1}$ of the Grothendieck's inequality over the Hilbert space $\mathcal{H}^{\mathbb{R}}$ [4, p. 11 Lemma 2.4], the Euler-Kronecker constant γ_8 (**Appendix C**), [20, pp. 407–58], [27], [28], [33, p. 103], [36, pp. 407–58] of the global field $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{8})$ [40] and special values of R-functions whose argument the number 8^{-1} factors out [27, p. 6 (15–6)], [33, p. 104].

Corollary 2.8. *The Krivine bound $K_G^{\mathbb{R}} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} c(f, g)^{-1}$ of the Grothendieck's inequality over $\mathcal{H}^{\mathbb{R}}$, and the Euler-Kronecker constant γ_8 of the global field $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{8})$, have a closed-form expression*

$$K_G^{\mathbb{R}} \leq \frac{1}{c(f, g)} \leq \pi \frac{\gamma_8 - \log(2\pi e^{2\gamma})}{R\left(\frac{1}{8}\right) - R\left(\frac{3}{8}\right) - R\left(\frac{5}{8}\right) + R\left(\frac{7}{8}\right)} \quad (2.30)$$

Proof. If we wish, we may write (C.1) **Appendix C** as:

$$\gamma_8 - \log(2\pi e^{2\gamma}) = \left(R\left(\frac{1}{8}\right) - R\left(\frac{3}{8}\right) - R\left(\frac{5}{8}\right) + R\left(\frac{7}{8}\right) \right) (2 \log(1 + \sqrt{2}))^{-1} \quad (2.31)$$

Multiplying the LHS and the RHS of (2.31) by π , gives:

$$\pi(\gamma_8 - \log(2\pi e^{2\gamma})) = \pi \left(R\left(\frac{1}{8}\right) - R\left(\frac{3}{8}\right) - R\left(\frac{5}{8}\right) + R\left(\frac{7}{8}\right) \right) (2 \log(1 + \sqrt{2}))^{-1} \quad (2.32)$$

In the RHS of equation (2.32), the rational factor $\pi/(2 \log(1 + \sqrt{2}))$ is the Krivine bound $K_G^{\mathbb{R}} \leq c(f, g)^{-1}$ of Grothendieck's inequality over $\mathcal{H}^{\mathbb{R}}$ (**Lemma 1.4**) [8, A088367]. Hence:

$$\pi(\gamma_8 - \log(2\pi e^{2\gamma})) = K_G^{\mathbb{R}} \left(R\left(\frac{1}{8}\right) - R\left(\frac{3}{8}\right) - R\left(\frac{5}{8}\right) + R\left(\frac{7}{8}\right) \right) \quad (2.33)$$

whose solution for $K_G^{\mathbb{R}}$ is:

$$K_G^{\mathbb{R}} \leq \frac{1}{c(f, g)} \leq \pi(\gamma_8 - \log(2\pi e^{2\gamma})) / \left(R\left(\frac{1}{8}\right) - R\left(\frac{3}{8}\right) - R\left(\frac{5}{8}\right) + R\left(\frac{7}{8}\right) \right) \quad (2.34)$$

The claim follows. ■

2.7.2 König theorem and the Euler-Kronecker constant γ_8 of the global field $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{8})$.

Section 2.7.2 links the Euler-Kronecker constant γ_8 of the global field $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{8})$ [26, pp. 407–458], [27], [34, p. 103], [40], and **Appendix C** to **Theorem 1.2** integrals (1.3)–(1.7).

Corollary 2.9. *The Euler-Kronecker constant γ_8 of the global field $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{8})$ and König’s two-dimensional integral and supremum $M_0 = \sup B_K(f, g)$ of the bilinear form have closed-form expression*

$$\int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty \text{sign}(\vec{x})\text{sign}(\vec{y}) \frac{\sin(\langle \vec{x}, \vec{y} \rangle)}{\sqrt{e^{\|\vec{x}\|_2^2 + \|\vec{y}\|_2^2}}} d\vec{x}d\vec{y} = \sqrt{2} \frac{R\left(\frac{1}{8}\right) - R\left(\frac{3}{8}\right) - R\left(\frac{5}{8}\right) + R\left(\frac{7}{8}\right)}{\gamma_8 - \log(2\pi e^{2\gamma})} \quad (2.35)$$

and, with the supremum $M_0 = \sup B_K(f, g)$ of the bilinear form (1.3)

$$\sup_{\substack{f, g \in L_\infty(0, \infty) \\ f, g \in [-1, 1] \\ \text{almost} \\ \text{everywhere}}} \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty f(\vec{x})g(\vec{y}) \frac{\sin(\langle \vec{x}, \vec{y} \rangle)}{\sqrt{e^{\|\vec{x}\|_2^2 + \|\vec{y}\|_2^2}}} d\vec{x}d\vec{y} = \frac{R\left(\frac{1}{8}\right) - R\left(\frac{3}{8}\right) - R\left(\frac{5}{8}\right) + R\left(\frac{7}{8}\right)}{\sqrt{8}(\gamma_8 - \log(2\pi e^{2\gamma}))} \quad (2.36)$$

Proof. If we wish, we may write the identity (C.1) **Appendix C** as:

$$2 \log(1 + \sqrt{2}) = \left(R\left(\frac{1}{8}\right) - R\left(\frac{3}{8}\right) - R\left(\frac{5}{8}\right) + R\left(\frac{7}{8}\right) \right) (\gamma_8 - \log(2\pi e^{2\gamma}))^{-1} \quad (2.37)$$

whose LHS is equal to $2 \log(1 + \sqrt{2}) = 2^{-1/2} I_1$. Hence:

$$I_1 = \sqrt{2} \left(R\left(\frac{1}{8}\right) - R\left(\frac{3}{8}\right) - R\left(\frac{5}{8}\right) + R\left(\frac{7}{8}\right) \right) (\gamma_8 - \log(2\pi e^{2\gamma}))^{-1} \quad (2.38)$$

The LHS of (2.39) can be written as:

$$2 \log(1 + \sqrt{2}) = \frac{4 \log(1 + \sqrt{2})}{\sqrt{2}} = \sqrt{8} M_0 \tag{2.39}$$

Replacing (2.39) in (C.1) **Appendix C** gives the supremum $M_0 = \sup B_K(f, g)$ of the König bilinear form:

$$M_0 = \sqrt{8} (\gamma_8 - \log(2\pi e^{2\gamma})) \left(R\left(\frac{1}{8}\right) - R\left(\frac{3}{8}\right) - R\left(\frac{5}{8}\right) + R\left(\frac{7}{8}\right) \right) \tag{2.40}$$

(2.40) is equal to (2.36). The claim follows. ■

2.8. Central binomial coefficients or type B Catalan numbers.

Section 2.8 delves into the infinite series involving reciprocals of central binomial coefficients, exploring their relationships to **Theorem 1.1**, **Corollary 1.2**, and **Lemma 1.3**.

2.8.1 Convergent Apéry-type series with reciprocals of central binomial coefficients.

Let us denote as s_0 the Apéry-type series with reciprocals of *central binomial coefficients* or *type B Catalan Numbers* [8, A000984], [33, pp. 182–9], [34, p. 78], [38, p. 274], [39, pp. 13–88], [43], and section A.4:

$$s_0 \leftarrow \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n 2^{2n}}{(2n+1)^2} \binom{2n}{n}^{-1} = \frac{\pi^2}{8} - \frac{\log(1 + \sqrt{2})^2}{2} \approx 0.84529 \tag{2.41}$$

2.8.2 Apéry-type series, Krivine bound, and Dirichlet L-series of symmetric discriminants.

Lemma 2.0 indicates in the Dirichlet L -series $L_8(1)$ the infimum of the bilinear form I_0 . **Theorem 2.1** shows that the same Dirichlet L -series $L_8(1)$ defines both evaluations of **Theorem 1.2** inequality $M_0 \leq I_1$. **Theorem 2.2** has proved the identity of the ratio $L_{-8}(1)/L_8(1)$ [8, A093954] and Krivine bound (**Lemma 1.4**). Those are motivations to focus the pair of Dirichlet L -series $\{L_{-8}(1), L_8(1)\}$ of symmetric fundamental discriminant $D = \mp 2$, and fundamental unit of norm 1.

Theorem 2.10. *The Apéry-type series s_0 with reciprocals of central binomial coefficients, the Krivine bound $K_G^{\mathbb{R}} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} c(f, g)^{-1}$ over $\mathcal{H}^{\mathbb{R}}$, and the pair $\{L_8(1); L_{-8}(1)\}$ of quadratic Dirichlet L -series of symmetric fundamental discriminant ∓ 2 , have expression:*

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n 2^{2n}}{(2n+1)^2} \binom{2n}{n}^{-1} = (L_8(1)K_G^{\mathbb{R}})^2 - \left(\frac{L_{-8}(1)}{K_G^{\mathbb{R}}} \right)^2 = \left(\frac{L_8(1)}{c(f, g)} \right)^2 - (L_{-8}(1) c(f, g))^2 \tag{2.42}$$

Proof. If we wish, we may write (2.41) [33, p. 186], as:

$$s_0 = 8^{-1}(\pi - 2 \log(1 + \sqrt{2}))(\pi + 2 \log(1 + \sqrt{2})) \tag{2.43}$$

The summands of the factors between brackets are linear combinations of those in **Lemma 1.4**. Multiplying and dividing the RHS of (2.43) by $K_G^{\mathbb{R}}$ [8, A088367], yields:

$$s_0 = 8^{-1} \left(2 \log(1 + \sqrt{2}) K_G^{\mathbb{R}} - \frac{\pi}{K_G^{\mathbb{R}}} \right) \left(2 \log(1 + \sqrt{2}) K_G^{\mathbb{R}} + \frac{\pi}{K_G^{\mathbb{R}}} \right) \tag{2.44}$$

$$s_0 = 8^{-1} (K_G^{\mathbb{R}})^{-2} \left(2 \log(1 + \sqrt{2}) (K_G^{\mathbb{R}})^2 - \pi \right) \left(2 \log(1 + \sqrt{2}) (K_G^{\mathbb{R}})^2 + \pi \right) \tag{2.45}$$

$$s_0 = \underbrace{\left(\frac{\log(1 + \sqrt{2})}{\sqrt{2}} \right)^2}_{L_8(1)^2} (K_G^{\mathbb{R}})^2 - \underbrace{\left(\frac{\pi}{2\sqrt{2}} \right)^2}_{L_{-8}(1)^2} \frac{1}{(K_G^{\mathbb{R}})^2} = (L_8(1) K_G^{\mathbb{R}})^2 - \left(\frac{L_{-8}(1)}{K_G^{\mathbb{R}}} \right)^2 \tag{2.46}$$

$$s_0 = \left(\frac{L_8(1)}{c(f, g)} \right)^2 - (L_{-8}(1) c(f, g))^2 \tag{2.47}$$

(2.46) includes the central identity of (2.42). (2.47) is equal to (2.42) rightmost identity. The claim follows. ■

Theorem 2.11. *The Apéry-type series s_0 with reciprocals of central binomial coefficients or type B Catalan Numbers, the Krivine bound $K_G^{\mathbb{R}} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} c(f, g)^{-1}$ over $\mathcal{H}^{\mathbb{R}}$, and König's and Tomczak-Jaegermann's two-dimensional integrals M_0, I_1 have closed-form expressions*

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n 2^{2n}}{(2n+1)^2} \binom{2n}{n}^{-1} = \left((K_G^{\mathbb{R}})^2 - 1 \right) \left(\sup_{\substack{f, g \in L_{\infty}(0, \infty) \\ f, g \in [-1, 1] \\ \text{almost} \\ \text{everywhere}}} \int_0^{\infty} \int_0^{\infty} f(\vec{x}) g(\vec{y}) \frac{\sin(\langle \vec{x}, \vec{y} \rangle)}{\sqrt{e^{\|\vec{x}\|_2^2 + \|\vec{y}\|_2^2}}} d\vec{x} d\vec{y} \right)^2 \tag{2.48}$$

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n 2^{2n}}{(2n+1)^2} \binom{2n}{n}^{-1} = (K_G^{\mathbb{R}})^2 \left(\sup_{\substack{f, g \in L_{\infty}(0, \infty) \\ f, g \in [-1, 1] \\ \text{almost} \\ \text{everywhere}}} \int_0^{\infty} \int_0^{\infty} f(\vec{x}) g(\vec{y}) \frac{\sin(\langle \vec{x}, \vec{y} \rangle)}{\sqrt{e^{\|\vec{x}\|_2^2 + \|\vec{y}\|_2^2}}} d\vec{x} d\vec{y} \right)^2$$

$$-16^{-1} \left(\int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty \text{sign}(\vec{x})\text{sign}(\vec{y}) \frac{\sin(\langle \vec{x}, \vec{y} \rangle)}{\sqrt{e^{\|\vec{x}\|_2^2 + \|\vec{y}\|_2^2}}} d\vec{x}d\vec{y} \right)^2 \tag{2.49}$$

Proof. Based on **Theorem 2.1**, those identities hold

$$M_0^2 := \frac{\log(1 + \sqrt{2})^2}{2} \tag{2.50}$$

$$M_0^2 := \frac{\pi^2}{8(K_G^{\mathbb{R}^2})^2} = \frac{4\pi^2 \log(1 + \sqrt{2})^2}{8\pi^2} = \frac{\log(1 + \sqrt{2})^2}{2} \tag{2.51}$$

Hence, we can write s_0 as:

$$s_0 = M_0^2 K_G^{\mathbb{R}^2} - M_0^2 = M_0^2 (K_G^{\mathbb{R}^2} - 1) = M_0^2 (c(f, g)^{-2} - 1) \tag{2.52}$$

Recalling the ratio of I_1 to M_0 (2.4), (2.52) has closed-form expressions:

$$s_0 = M_0^2 (K_G^{\mathbb{R}^2})^2 - \frac{I_1^2}{16} = \frac{M_0^2}{c(f, g)^2} - \frac{I_1^2}{16} \tag{2.53}$$

(2.53) is equal to (2.49). The claim follows. ■

2.8.3 Braverman et al. theorem and Apéry constant $\zeta(3)$ irrationality.

Section 2.8.3 indicates that Braverman et al. [4, p. 4 Theorem 1.1] **Theorem 1.4**, which refers to upper bound of the Grothendieck’s inequality which, on 21 February 1977 at Paris, Krivine [6] presented holds, based on the same Pisot-Vijayaraghavan number λ [43] which, on 20 June 1978 at Marseille, Apéry [87, pp. 784–6], [42, p. 13], [132] demonstrated to imply irrationality of the Riemann zeta-function $\zeta(3) = L_1(3, \chi_0)$ or Apéry’s constant [8, A002117], [32, pp. 40–51], [33, p. 99], [41, p. 268], [43, p. 92 (1.1)], [124]. Section 1 includes **Remark 1.6** [4, p. 33 Remark 5.6] to **Theorem 1.5** [4, p. 4 Theorem 1.1]. It holds that

Corollary 2.12. *Assuming*

$$\frac{B_K(f, g)}{\pi} > \log(\lambda) \tag{2.54}$$

then, there exist $\varepsilon_0 > 0$ such that

$$K_G^{\mathbb{R}} < \frac{\pi}{2 \log(1 + \sqrt{2})} - \varepsilon_0 \tag{2.55}$$

Proof. **Remark 1.6** [4, p. 33 Remark 5.6] holds. Divide RHS and LHS of (1.11) by π

$$\frac{B_K(f, g)}{\pi} > 4 \log(1 + \sqrt{2}) = \log(17 + 12\sqrt{2}) \tag{2.56}$$

where $B_K(f, g)$ is the König’s bilinear form and the logarithm’s argument is λ [8, A156164], [48]:

$$\frac{B_K(f, g)}{\pi} > \log(\lambda) \tag{2.57}$$

(2.57) is equal to (2.54). Recalling **Remark 1.6**, one can repeat the proof of **Theorem 1.5** with H_η replaced by H reaching (2.55). The claim follows. ■

2.8.4 Generalized hypergeometric and digamma functions.

We consider the pair of Dirichlet L -series $\{L_{-8}(1); L_8(1)\}$ of symmetric fundamental discriminant $D = \mp 2$, and fundamental unit of norm 1 and by means of a series of lemmas:

- showing that the constant of proportionality between linear combinations of elements of the pairs $\{\pi \pm 2 \log(1 + \sqrt{2})\}$ and $\{L_{-8}(1) \pm L_8(1)\}$, is the same prefactor $\sqrt{8}$ [8, A010466] of **Theorem 1.2**’s factor $\log(1 + \sqrt{2}) \in \mathbb{C} \setminus \mathbb{A} \subset \mathcal{P} \subset \mathbb{C}$ [8, A091648];
- identifying $\{\pi \pm 2 \log(1 + \sqrt{2})\}$ as functions of generalised hypergeometric functions.

Lemma 2.13. *Those identities hold:*

$$\frac{\pi - 2 \log(1 + \sqrt{2})}{L_{-8}(1) - L_8(1)} = \sqrt{8} = \frac{\pi + 2 \log(1 + \sqrt{2})}{L_{-8}(1) + L_8(1)} \tag{2.58}$$

Proof. Compute those ratios

$$\frac{\pi - 2 \log(1 + \sqrt{2})}{L_{-8}(1) - L_8(1)} = (\pi - 2 \log(1 + \sqrt{2})) \left(\frac{\pi}{2\sqrt{2}} - \frac{\log(1 + \sqrt{2})}{\sqrt{2}} \right)^{-1} = 2\sqrt{2} = \sqrt{8} \tag{2.59}$$

$$\frac{\pi + 2 \log(1 + \sqrt{2})}{L_{-8}(1) + L_8(1)} = (\pi + 2 \log(1 + \sqrt{2})) \left(\frac{\pi}{2\sqrt{2}} + \frac{\log(1 + \sqrt{2})}{\sqrt{2}} \right)^{-1} = 2\sqrt{2} = \sqrt{8} \tag{2.60}$$

(2.59) and (2.60) are equal to $\sqrt{8}$. Hence:

$$\frac{\pi - 2 \log(1 + \sqrt{2})}{L_{-8}(1) - L_8(1)} = \sqrt{8} = \frac{\pi + 2 \log(1 + \sqrt{2})}{L_{-8}(1) + L_8(1)} \tag{2.61}$$

The claim follows. ■

Lemma 2.14. *Let us denote as $\{L_{-8}(1); L_8(1)\}$ the pair of Dirichlet L-series of a symmetric fundamental discriminant $D = \mp 2$ and a fundamental unit of norm 1. Those identities hold:*

$$\frac{2 \times 3^{-1} {}_3F_2\left(\frac{3}{4}, \frac{3}{4}, \frac{5}{4}; \frac{3}{2}, \frac{7}{4}; 1\right)}{L_{-8}(1) - L_8(1)} = \sqrt{8} = \frac{{}_4F_2\left(\frac{1}{4}, \frac{1}{4}, \frac{3}{4}; \frac{1}{2}, \frac{5}{4}; 1\right)}{L_{-8}(1) + L_8(1)} \tag{2.62}$$

where the constant of proportionality between the leftmost and the rightmost quotient is $\sqrt{8}$, and

$$B_2 \frac{{}_3F_2\left(\frac{3}{4}, \frac{3}{4}, \frac{5}{4}; \frac{3}{2}, \frac{7}{4}; 1\right)}{L_{-8}(1) - L_8(1)} = \sqrt{B_1} = \frac{{}_3F_2\left(\frac{1}{4}, \frac{1}{4}, \frac{3}{4}; \frac{1}{2}, \frac{5}{4}; 1\right)}{L_{-8}(1) + L_8(1)} \tag{2.63}$$

where the Bernoulli Number $B_2 = 6^{-1}$ is the prefactor of the leftmost identity, and the square root of the Bernoulli number B_1 [82, p. 658 Table 3] is the constant of proportionality.

Proof. **Table 1** is an excerpt from the latest version of Knuth’s [82, p. 658 Table 3] treatise. It evaluates the first and second Bernoulli number as, respectively, $B_1 = 2^{-1}$ and $B_2 = 6^{-1}$.

Table 1. Harmonic numbers H_n , Bernoulli numbers B_n , and Fibonacci numbers F_n for small values of n .

n	H_n	B_n	F_n
0	0	1	0
1	1	1/2	1
2	2/3	1/6	1

The generalised hypergeometric function [61, p. 92 Table 2 (7.4.4.197b)] can be written as:

$$\frac{2}{3} {}_3F_2\left(\frac{3}{4}, \frac{3}{4}, \frac{5}{4}; \frac{3}{2}, \frac{7}{4}; 1\right) = \pi - 2 \log(1 + \sqrt{2}) \tag{2.64}$$

The generalised hypergeometric function [61, p. 92 Table 2 (7.4.4.134a)] can be written as:

$$4 {}_3F_2\left(\frac{1}{4}, \frac{1}{4}, \frac{3}{4}; \frac{1}{2}, \frac{5}{4}; 1\right) = \pi + 2 \log(1 + \sqrt{2}) \tag{2.65}$$

Replacing evaluations with generalised hypergeometric functions' symbols, **Lemma 2.13** reads

$$\frac{2 \times 3^{-1} {}_3F_2\left(\frac{3}{4}, \frac{3}{4}, \frac{5}{4}; \frac{3}{2}, \frac{7}{4}; 1\right)}{L_{-8}(1) - L_8(1)} = \sqrt{8} = \frac{4 {}_3F_2\left(\frac{1}{4}, \frac{1}{4}, \frac{3}{4}; \frac{1}{2}, \frac{5}{4}; 1\right)}{L_{-8}(1) + L_8(1)} \tag{2.66}$$

(2.66) is equal to (2.62). The greatest common divisor of (2.66) is 4. Dividing (2.66) by 4 gives

$$\frac{1}{6} \frac{{}_3F_2\left(\frac{3}{4}, \frac{3}{4}, \frac{5}{4}; \frac{3}{2}, \frac{7}{4}; 1\right)}{L_{-8}(1) - L_8(1)} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} = \frac{{}_3F_2\left(\frac{1}{4}, \frac{1}{4}, \frac{3}{4}; \frac{1}{2}, \frac{5}{4}; 1\right)}{L_{-8}(1) + L_8(1)} \tag{2.67}$$

Hence, the constant of proportionality $1/\sqrt{2}$ at the centre of (2.67), equals $\sqrt{B_1}$ [8, A010503] and B_2 [8, A020793] is the prefactor of the leftmost identity. Then, (2.67) can be written as:

$$B_2 \frac{{}_3F_2\left(\frac{3}{4}, \frac{3}{4}, \frac{5}{4}; \frac{3}{2}, \frac{7}{4}; 1\right)}{L_{-8}(1) - L_8(1)} = \sqrt{B_1} = \frac{{}_3F_2\left(\frac{1}{4}, \frac{1}{4}, \frac{3}{4}; \frac{1}{2}, \frac{5}{4}; 1\right)}{L_{-8}(1) + L_8(1)} \tag{2.68}$$

(2.68) is equal to (2.63). The claim follows. ■

The following **Lemma 2.15** connects:

- the logarithmic derivative $\Psi(x)$, at rational evaluations $\{\Psi(1/8); \Psi(3/8); \Psi(5/8); \Psi(7/8)\}$ of the argument, of the classical gamma function $\Gamma(x)$ [71];
- a pair of generalised hypergeometric functions ${}_3F_2(\cdot)$ [63, pp. 820–76 979–86 1014–27], [70];
- the Apéry-type series s_0 (2.52) with reciprocals of type B Catalan Numbers [8, A000984], [33, pp. 182–9], [34, p. 78], [38, p. 274], [39, pp. 13–88], [104]–[107].

Thus, linking other enunciates in this paper. Let us denote as $\Psi(x)$ the logarithmic derivative of the gamma function or *digamma function* [61, p. 80], [62, p. 25] defined as

$$\Psi(x) := \frac{d}{dx} \log|\Gamma(x)| = \frac{\Gamma'(x)}{\Gamma(x)} \Big|_{x \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \mathbb{Z}_{\leq 0}} \tag{2.69}$$

having special values $\Psi(1) = -\gamma$ [8, A001620], [32, pp. 28–39], [34, 4–6], [35], and $\Psi(2^{-1}) = -\gamma - \log 4$ [8, A020759]. Let us denote as $\beta(x)$ the function [61, p. 90 (21)], [62, pp. 25–67], defined as

$$\beta(x) := \Psi\left(\frac{x+1}{2}\right) - \Psi\left(\frac{x}{2}\right) \Big|_{x \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \mathbb{Z}_{\leq 0}} \tag{2.70}$$

Lemma 2.15. *The Apéry-type series s_0 with reciprocals of type-B Catalan Numbers, Krivine bound $K_G^{\mathbb{R}} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} c(f, g)^{-1}$ in the Hilbert space $\mathcal{H}^{\mathbb{R}}$ and König two-dimensional integrals M_0, I_1 have closed-form expressions*

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n 2^{2n}}{(1+2n)^2} \binom{2n}{n}^{-1} = 16^{-1} \left(\Psi\left(\frac{7}{8}\right) - \Psi\left(\frac{3}{8}\right) \right) \left(\Psi\left(\frac{5}{8}\right) - \Psi\left(\frac{1}{8}\right) \right) \tag{2.71}$$

$$= 3^{-1} \left(\frac{1}{4}, \frac{1}{4}, \frac{3}{4}; \frac{1}{2}, \frac{5}{4}; 1 \right) {}_3F_2 \left(\frac{3}{4}, \frac{3}{4}, \frac{5}{4}; \frac{3}{2}, \frac{7}{4}; 1 \right) \tag{2.72}$$

Proof. Based on (2.64–5), (2.69–70), we have

$$\frac{2}{3} {}_3F_2 \left(\frac{3}{4}, \frac{3}{4}, \frac{5}{4}; \frac{3}{2}, \frac{7}{4}; 1 \right) = \pi - 2 \log(1 + \sqrt{2}) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \left(\Psi\left(\frac{7}{8}\right) - \Psi\left(\frac{3}{8}\right) \right) \approx 1.37884 \tag{2.73}$$

$$4 {}_3F_2 \left(\frac{1}{4}, \frac{1}{4}, \frac{3}{4}; \frac{1}{2}, \frac{5}{4}; 1 \right) = \pi + 2 \log(1 + \sqrt{2}) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \left(\Psi\left(\frac{5}{8}\right) - \Psi\left(\frac{1}{8}\right) \right) \approx 4.90433 \tag{2.74}$$

where the quadruple $\{\Psi(1/8); \Psi(3/8); \Psi(5/8); \Psi(7/8)\}$ denotes special values of the digamma function (2.69) at rational arguments [61, p. 90 (21)], [70]. Based on [61, p. 91], (2.74) arises. Replacing (2.73) and (2.74) in the identity, yields a closed-form expression of the Apéry-type series s_0 (2.41–2) with reciprocals of type B Catalan Numbers or central binomial coefficients [8, A000984], [38, p. 274], [39, pp. 1–12 89–102], in terms of digamma functions at rational arguments [61, p. 80], [70]

$$s_0 = 16^{-1} \left(\Psi\left(\frac{7}{8}\right) - \Psi\left(\frac{3}{8}\right) \right) \left(\Psi\left(\frac{5}{8}\right) - \Psi\left(\frac{1}{8}\right) \right) \tag{2.75}$$

(2.75) is equal to (2.71). Moreover, a closed-form expression of the Apéry-type series s_0 in terms of generalised hypergeometric functions ${}_3F_2(\cdot)$ [61], [64, pp. 820–76 979–86 1014–27], [70]

$$s_0 = 3^{-1} \times 8 \times 8^{-1} {}_3F_2 \left(\frac{1}{4}, \frac{1}{4}, \frac{3}{4}; \frac{1}{2}, \frac{5}{4}; 1 \right) {}_3F_2 \left(\frac{3}{4}, \frac{3}{4}, \frac{5}{4}; \frac{3}{2}, \frac{7}{4}; 1 \right) \tag{2.76}$$

(2.76) is equal to (2.72). The claim follows. ■

2.9 Type B Catalan numbers representations of π and $K_G^{\mathbb{R}}$.

Corollary 2.16. *Archimedes' constant π [8, A000796] admits an Apéry-type series representation with reciprocals of central binomial coefficients or type B Catalan Numbers [8, A000984]:*

$$\pi = 3 \sqrt{\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n 2^{2n}}{(2n+1)^2} \binom{2n}{n}^{-1} + \left[\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2^n(2n-1)} \right]^2} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{4n+1} - \frac{1}{4n-3} \right) \binom{2^{-1}}{n} \quad (2.77)$$

The Krivine bound $K_G^{\mathbb{R}} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} c(f, g)^{-1}$ has closed-form expressions with the Apéry-type series with reciprocals of type B Catalan Numbers and the supremum of the bilinear form M_0

$$K_G^{\mathbb{R}} \leq \sup_{\substack{f, g \in L_{\infty}(0, \infty) \\ f, g \in [-1, 1] \\ \text{almost} \\ \text{everywhere}}} \int_0^{\infty} \int_0^{\infty} f(\vec{x})g(\vec{y}) \frac{\sin(\langle \vec{x}, \vec{y} \rangle)}{\sqrt{e^{\|\vec{x}\|_2^2 + \|\vec{y}\|_2^2}}} d\vec{x}d\vec{y} \sqrt{1 + \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n 2^{2n}}{(2n+1)^2} \binom{2n}{n}^{-1}} \quad (2.78)$$

and, with its Dirichlet L-series analogue $L_8(1)$:

$$K_G^{\mathbb{R}} \leq \frac{1}{c(f, g)} \leq L_8(1) \sqrt{1 + \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n 2^{2n}}{(2n+1)^2} \binom{2n}{n}^{-1}} \quad (2.79)$$

Proof. Making those substitutions in the Apéry-type series with reciprocals of central binomial coefficients [8, A000984], [33, pp. 182–9], [34, p. 78], [38, p. 274], [39, pp. 13–88], [43], (2.45):

$$\left(\frac{\pi}{\sqrt{8}}\right)^2 \rightarrow s_1, \quad \left(\frac{\log(1 + \sqrt{2})}{\sqrt{2}}\right)^2 \rightarrow s_2 \quad (2.80)$$

$$s_0 = s_1 - s_2 \implies s_1 = s_0 + s_2 \quad (2.81)$$

where $s_0, s_1, s_2 > 0$, $s_2 < s_0 < s_1$, and taking the square root of (2.81), yields:

$$\sqrt{s_1} = \sqrt{s_0 + s_2} \quad (2.82)$$

Recalling (A.1) and (A.3), we find that the positive root of (2.82) has representation:

$$\pi / \sqrt[3]{\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{4n+1} - \frac{1}{4n-3} \right) \binom{2^{-1}}{n}} = \sqrt{\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n 2^{2n} \binom{2n}{n}^{-1}}{(2n+1)^2} + \left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2^n(2n-1)} \right)^2} \quad (2.83)$$

$$\pi = 3 \sqrt{\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n 2^{2n} \binom{2n}{n}^{-1}}{(2n+1)^2} + \left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2^n(2n-1)} \right)^2} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{4n+1} - \frac{1}{4n-3} \right) \binom{2^{-1}}{n} \quad (2.84)$$

(2.84) is equal to (2.77). An alternate representation, via Dirichlet L -series of symmetric fundamental discriminants ∓ 2 , and moduli ∓ 8 , reads [8, A093954]:

$$L_{-8}(1) = \sqrt{\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n 2^{2n} \binom{2n}{n}^{-1}}{(2n+1)^2} + L_8(1)^2} \quad (2.85)$$

After **Theorem 2.3** (2.6), $K_G^{\mathbb{R}} = L_{-8}(1) L_8(1)$. Hence, (2.85) can be written as $c(f, g)^{-1} = K_G^{\mathbb{R}}$:

$$\frac{K_G^{\mathbb{R}}}{L_8(1)} = \sqrt{\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n 2^{2n} \binom{2n}{n}^{-1}}{(2n+1)^2} + L_8(1)^2} \quad (2.86)$$

$$K_G^{\mathbb{R}} \leq L_8(1) \sqrt{\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n 2^{2n} \binom{2n}{n}^{-1}}{(2n+1)^2} + L_8(1)^2} = L_8(1) \sqrt{1 + \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n 2^{2n} \binom{2n}{n}^{-1}}{(2n+1)^2}} \quad (2.87)$$

and, of König's and Tomczak-Jaegermann's two-dimensional integrals M_0, I_1 (**Theorem 1.2**):

$$K_G^{\mathbb{R}} \leq \frac{1}{c(f, g)} \leq \sqrt{1 + \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n 2^{2n} \binom{2n}{n}^{-1}}{(2n+1)^2}} M_0 \quad (2.88)$$

(2.87) is equal to (2.79). (2.88) is equal to (2.78). The claim follows. ■

2.10 Global to local reduction of analytic functions properties.

Section 2.10 connects a special case of Fourier series cosine expansion to the combinatorial problem of reducing *global* (integral) to *local* (residue) properties of analytic functions.

2.10.1 Limit laws of Gaussian type: sign function-triangular function connection.

As Pain [22] clarifies, a deep connection exists between the seemingly different concepts of quadratic form optimisation and Fourier series decomposition. The Grothendieck constant emerges when comparing the maximum of a quadratic form over unit vectors in a Hilbert space with the maximum of the same form over scalars (± 1). The proofs based on Krivine's methods, to establish the Grothendieck's inequality bounds, frequently use transfer functions. In particular, their special case: the sign function. In the framework of signal processing, a square function is precisely a sequence of sign functions. Let $f(x)$ denote a triangular function, and as $p \in [0, 1]_{\mathbb{R}}$ its period. The triangular function is a periodic, piecewise linear continuous function over \mathbb{R} that rises and falls linearly, with odd harmonic content. Then, $f(x)$ is the integral of a square function:

$$f(x) = \int_0^t \operatorname{sgn}\left(\sin\left(\frac{u}{p}\right)\right) du \quad (2.89)$$

In certain approaches to the Grothendieck constant, like Krivine's bounds, integral identities are used to transform scalar products. For instance, the Grothendieck identity relies on the function: $2\pi^{-1} \arcsin(\langle \vec{x}, \vec{y} \rangle)$, $\vec{x}, \vec{y} \in \mathbb{R}^n$. Series expansions of triangular and sawtooth-type functions sometimes appear in either the linearisation of these optimisation problems or in the study of the associated kernel functions. Certain methods for finding the bounds of the Grothendieck constant use geometric vector configurations whose correlations can be modelled by simple periodic functions, and their distributions.

Local limit laws have that:

Definition 2.17. (Flajolet and Sedgewick [49, p. 695]). *A sequence of discrete probability distributions, with mean μ_n , standard deviation σ_n and approximation p_n is said to obey a local limit law of the Gaussian type if for a sequence $\epsilon_n \rightarrow 0$:*

$$\sup_{x \in \mathbb{R}} \left| \sigma_n p_{n, |\mu_n + x\sigma_n|} - \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi e^{x^2}}} \right| \leq \epsilon_n \quad (2.90)$$

The local limit law is said to hold with speed ϵ_n .

A local limit law, such as (2.90), holds for *binomial coefficients* [39, pp. 1–12 89–102], [49, pp. 8–12], [54, pp. 9–23 75–93 143–6] and for the *Eulerian distribution* [49, pp. 8–12 210–1], [49, pp. 697–8 Example IX.35]. The latter has a relationship to the combinatorial class (see **Definition 1.8**) of *Eulerian numbers*, denoted $\langle n \rangle_k$ [54, pp. 210–6]–[56]. **Figure 2** plots the histogram of a Eulerian distribution based on $n = 60$ triangular functions for $|u| = 1$. After standardisation, the Eulerian distribution results asymptotically with speed of convergence $\mathcal{O}(1/\sqrt{n})$, mean $\mu_n = (n - 1)/2$ and variance $\sigma_n^2 = (n + 1)/12$. Those authors examined that distribution, performed a meromorphic analyses of a movable singularity [49, pp. 697–8 Example IX.35]. Denoting as $B(u)$ the function [49, pp. 658–9 Example IX.12]:

Figure 2. The Eulerian distribution histogram, scaled to $(n + 1)|_{n \in [3,60]_{\mathbb{N}}}$ on the horizontal axis, converges to a bell-shaped curve of density $1/\sqrt{2\pi e^{x^2}}$.

$$B(u) = \frac{1}{\rho(u)} = \frac{u - 1}{\log(u)} \Big|_{u \in \mathbb{C}; \Re(u) \in [0, \infty)} \tag{2.91}$$

They found that, for u close to 1, the approximation $p_n(u)$ is

$$p_n(u) = \frac{1}{B(u)^{n+1}} + \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{1}{2^n}\right) \tag{2.92}$$

Then, they characterised the set of poles $\rho_j(u) \Big|_{j \in \mathbb{Z}}$ of the bivariate generating function $F(z, u)$.

Under the conditions $u \in \mathbb{C}, \Re(u) \in [0, \infty)$ they deduced that [49, p. 697 Example IX.35]:

- (i) $\rho(u)$ is the unique dominant singularity,
- (ii) the infimum of the distance of all other poles from the singularity $\rho(u)$ is [8, A093954]:

$$\inf_{j \in \mathbb{Z}} (\rho_j(u) - \rho(u)) = \frac{\pi}{\sqrt{8}} \tag{2.93}$$

2.10.2 Limit cases of limaçons of Pascal, called circle and cardioid.

Sections 2.10.2–3 introduce information from analytic combinatorics, geometry of quartic surfaces, and differential topology, used in the proof of the following section 2.10.4's **Lemma 2.22**. In 1525, Dürer established a method to draw a curve which, after Étienne Pascal father of Blaise rediscovered it in 1630, is called *limaçon of Pascal* (snail of Pascal) [68, pp. 49–51 113–7], [100]

Definition 2.18 (Kanas and Masih [100, pp. 20]). *A bicircular rational plane algebraic curve of degree 4 which belongs to the family of curves called centered trochoids or epitrochoids. Pascal snail is the inversion of conic sections with respect to a focus.*

Lawrence [68, pp. 113] gives a succinct definition as (quoting): “The conchoid of a circle of radius a , with respect to a point O on the circumference of the circle.” **Figure 3** plots the polar representation $|B(e^{i\theta})| : \theta \in [0, 2\pi]_{\mathbb{R}}; u \in [-1, 1]_{\mathbb{R}}$ of **Figure 2**'s Eulerian distribution histogram [49, p. 698 Figure IX.15]. Dashed the comparison unit circle. **Figure 4** plots (blue) the special case $r(\theta)|_{\theta \in [0, 2\pi]_{\mathbb{R}}; 2a=0.4; b=0.6}$ of the plane closed oval quartic parametric polar curve called dimpled *limaçon*. (Dashed) Limit case of limaçon degeneration, called *circle* [68], [100]. **Figure 5** plots (orange) the limit case $r(\theta)|_{\theta \in [0, 2\pi]_{\mathbb{R}}; 2a=b=0.5}$ of limaçon degeneration, called *cardioid*. The (blue) dot at the cusp, is an irreducible multi-germ with an ordinary double point [68], [70]. **Figures 3–5** coordinate systems are *isometric*. **Figures 2–3** plot a histogram and a polar representation of a distribution based on 60 points. Thus, explaining why the Gaussian curve in **Figure 2** and the (solid black) curve in **Figure 3**, are not smooth. **Figure 4** is a Computer Algebra System-generated plot [115] with computational errors $< 10^{-200}$. If the number of points in the Eulerian distribution would be an order of magnitude larger, then the (black) curve in **Figure 3** would look as smooth as the (blue) curve **Figure 4** looks, making patterns indistinguishable.

In 1964, the eminent geometer Fejes Tóth, listed the constant $\sqrt{2} - 1$ among those few assuring compact packings of the plane $\mathbb{R}^2 \cong \mathbb{C}$ by discs of radius $\{1, r\}|_{r \in]0, 1[_{\mathbb{R}}}$. In 2000, Hepped [131] demonstrated that the *densest* packing $(1, \sqrt{2} - 1)$ is a *compact* packing. In 2004, Kennedy [102, p. 256 Theorem 1] demonstrated that no more than $n \in [1, 9]_{\mathbb{N}}$ constants c_n are endowed with such a property [102, p. 257 Table 1]. **Figure 6** plots a region of the Euclidean plane packed by circles of radius $(1, c_4) = (1, \sqrt{2} - 1) = (1, -\alpha_2^{-1}) = (1, \tan(\pi/8))$. The region of the plane embraces thirty-five of the circles in **Figures 3–4** of radius 1. The cardioid in **Figure 5**, circles and limaçons in **Figures 3, 4**, and **6** are isometric. Hence, those representations of limaçon, and of its cardioidal and circular limit cases, can be considered tiling the compact packing plane $\mathbb{R}^2 \cong \mathbb{C}$, of which **Figure 6** plots a region, by means of discs of radius 1 and $r = c_4 := \sqrt{2} - 1$ [8, A010503].

Figure 3. (Black) Function $|B(u)|, |u| = 1$ relative to the Eulerian distribution of the histogram in **Figure 2**, here represented by the polar plot $|B(e^{i\theta})|, \theta \in [0, 2\pi]_{\mathbb{R}}, u \in [-1, 1]_{\mathbb{R}}$ on the ray of angle θ . (Dashed) Comparison circle of radius 1, itself a limit case of degenerate limaçon.

Figure 4. (Blue) Special case $r(\theta)|_{\theta \in [0, 2\pi]_{\mathbb{R}}; 2a=0.4; b=0.6}$ of dimpled *limaçon* plane closed oval quartic parametric polar curve. (Dashed) Comparison circle of radius 1 is a limit case of degenerate *limaçon*.

Figure 5. (Orange) Limit case $r(\theta)|_{\theta \in [0, 2\pi]_{\mathbb{R}}}$; $2a=b=0.5$ of degenerate limaçon, called *cardioid*. The (blue) dot at the cusp is an irreducible multi-germ with an ordinary double point. Comparison circle of radius 1 not shown.

Figure 6. Compact packing of $\mathbb{R}^2 \cong \mathbb{C}$ by discs of radius 1 and $r = c_4 := \sqrt{2} - 1$ [8, A010503].

2.10.3 $z := i/\sqrt{2}$ mediates the global-to-local reduction of analytic functions' properties.

Flajolet and Sedgewick [49, pp. 236–7] indicated the special value $i/\sqrt{2}$ of the complex variable $z \in \mathbb{C}$ among those playing a prominent role in the reduction from global (integral) to local (residue) properties of all analytic functions. That, motivates looking in directions where analytical functions admit decomposition via sums of infinite Apéry-type series, with reciprocals of central binomial coefficients. Ira Gessel attributes to Egorychev [57], [58] breakthrough of 1977, known as “methods of coefficients” for computing sums of finite and infinite series. In 2006, Sprugnoli [51] applied the method to show convergence of certain sums of infinite Apéry-type series, with reciprocals of type B Catalan numbers or central binomial coefficients [8, A000984], [38], [51], [55]–[56], [103]–[105]:

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{b_n} \binom{2n}{n}^{-1} \tag{2.94}$$

where a_n and b_n are elementary functions of n , and signs are alternating. Let us denote as z the positive root [8, A010503] of $\sqrt{-1/2} \in \mathbb{C} \setminus \mathbb{A} \subset \mathcal{P} \subset \mathbb{C}$:

$$z := \left| \sqrt{-\frac{1}{2}} \right| = \frac{i}{\sqrt{2}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} e^{\frac{i}{\sqrt{2}} \frac{\pi}{\sqrt{2}}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} e^{z \frac{\pi}{\sqrt{2}}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \left(\cos\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right) + i \sin\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right) \right) \approx 0.70711i \tag{2.95}$$

Sprugnoli selected the special evaluation (2.95) of the complex inverse tangent function of argument $z = x + iy \in \mathbb{C} : x, y \in (-\infty, \infty)_{\mathbb{R}}$, demonstrating that [51, pp. 8–9 Theorem 3.2]:

$$\arctan z = -i \log\left(\frac{1 + iz}{\sqrt{1 + z^2}}\right) \xrightarrow{z:=\frac{i}{\sqrt{2}}} -i \log(\sqrt{2} - 1) \in \mathbb{C} \setminus \mathbb{A} \subset \mathcal{P} \subset \mathbb{C} \tag{2.96}$$

Remark 2.19. Based on [51, p. 8 Theorem 3.2 (1)] the arctangent function of $z \in \mathbb{C}$ transforms into a number whose coefficient of the imaginary is the natural logarithm of $-\bar{a}_2$. After Kennedy’s [102, p. 256 Theorem 1] theorem, we can write (2.96) as [34, p. 75 Table 8.11], [99, p. 257 Table 1]:

$$\arctan z \xrightarrow{z:=\frac{i}{\sqrt{2}}} -i \log c_4 \tag{2.97}$$

Let us consider the function $f(z) = z^{-1} \arctan z$, $z = x + iy \in \mathbb{C}$, $x, y \in (-\infty, \infty)_{\mathbb{R}}$ and the associated Riemann surface [69, pp. 247–393], which in **Table 2**, section D.2 corresponds to the case $n = 1$ of complex inverse tangent of $z := i/\sqrt{2}$. (2.97) shows the combined effect of the $1/\sqrt{2}$ transformation $1/\sqrt{2} \rightarrow z$ and scaling $1/\sqrt{2}$ applied to $f(z) = z^{-1} \arctan z$, $z = x + iy \in \mathbb{C}$, $x, y \in (-\infty, \infty)_{\mathbb{R}}$: the transformation $f(z) \rightarrow \log(1 + \sqrt{2})$:

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \frac{\arctan z}{z} \Big|_{z=x+iy \in \mathbb{C}; x,y \in (-\infty, \infty)_{\mathbb{R}}} \xrightarrow{z:=\frac{i}{\sqrt{2}}} \log(1 + \sqrt{2}) \tag{2.98}$$

Figure 7 plots Cartesian representations of (2.97). Inset (a) is $\Re(f(z))$ and inset (b) is $\Im(f(z))$. The latter's orientation makes the primitive topological object called *pair-of-pants* [73], [74] discernible, as **Theorem 1.7** expects. Thus, including the case $\mathbb{C}\mathbb{P}^1$ which Penrose and Rindler [89, pp. 8–32], [90, pp. 1–10], Frauendiener and Penrose [90, pp. 478–88], Luna et al. [92], White [93], Woit [94, p. 27], Scholze [95] and others identify by the twistor whose representation is the Riemann sphere [69, pp. 117–52] of the Argand plane S^- in $\mathbb{M} \subset \mathbb{R}^4$.

Example 2.20. Let us denote as $\Phi(z, \omega) \Big|_{s=t+i\tau \in \mathbb{C}; \omega \in (-\infty, \infty)_{\mathbb{R}}}$ a function [94, p. 42 Appendix C.2]:

$$\Phi = \frac{i}{2\pi} \frac{1}{s - \omega} \Big|_{s=t+i\tau \in \mathbb{C}; \omega \in (-\infty, \infty)_{\mathbb{R}}} = \frac{i}{\sqrt{2}} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}\pi(s - \omega)} = \frac{z}{\sqrt{2}\pi} \frac{1}{s - \omega} \Big|_{z:=\frac{i}{\sqrt{2}}} \tag{2.99}$$

where $\sqrt{2}\pi$ is the exact evaluation of (i) the circumference of the circumcircle of the unit square, (ii) the hypotenuse of the right isoscele triangle of equal sides (π, π) [8, A063448]. Its representations include:

$$\sqrt{2}\pi = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{e^{\frac{x}{4}}}{e^x + 1} dx = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{1 + x^2}{1 + x^4} dx = \int_0^{\infty} \log\left(1 + \frac{2}{x^2}\right) dx = \int_0^{\infty} \log\left(1 + \frac{1}{x^4}\right) dx \tag{2.100}$$

$$= \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{1}{\sin^2(x) + 1} dx = \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{1}{\cos^2(x) + 1} dx = \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{4}\right) \Gamma\left(\frac{3}{4}\right) \tag{2.101}$$

The hyperfunction corresponding to the interpretation of (2.99) as a distribution is the limit that describes the Dirac *delta function*. Its hyperfunction version reads [94, p. 42 Appendix C.2]

$$\oint_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{i}{2\pi} \frac{f(t)}{t - \omega} dt \Big|_{s=t+i\tau \in \mathbb{C}; \omega \in (-\infty, \infty)_{\mathbb{R}}} = \frac{i}{2\pi} \oint_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{f(t)}{t - \omega} dt \Big|_{s=t+i\tau \in \mathbb{C}; \omega \in (-\infty, \infty)_{\mathbb{R}}} \tag{2.102}$$

$$= \frac{i}{\sqrt{2}} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}\pi} \oint_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{f(t)}{t - \omega} dt \Big|_{s=t+i\tau \in \mathbb{C}; \omega \in (-\infty, \infty)_{\mathbb{R}}; z:=\frac{i}{\sqrt{2}}} = \frac{z}{\sqrt{2}\pi} \oint_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{f(t)}{t - \omega} dt \Big|_{s=t+i\tau \in \mathbb{C}; \omega \in (-\infty, \infty)_{\mathbb{R}}; z:=\frac{i}{\sqrt{2}}} \tag{2.103}$$

Recall the Plouffe constant $P_A = 1/2\pi$ [37], [122].

Figure 7. Cartesian representation of the function $f(z) = z^{-1} \arctan z$ (2.98) on the range $x, y \in [-2, 2]_{\mathbb{R}}, f(z) \in [-1.5, 1.5]_{\mathbb{R}}$. Inset (a) plots the real part $\Re(f(z))$. Inset (b) plots the imaginary part $\Im(f(z))$ where it is visible a pair-of-pants object of differential topology (see **Theorem 1.7** and references).

Then, (2.102) has a further representation as:

$$iP_A \oint_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{f(t)}{t - \omega} dt \Big|_{s=t+i\tau \in \mathbb{C}; \omega \in (-\infty, \infty)_{\mathbb{R}}} \tag{2.104}$$

Example 2.21. The pair $\{z, z^{-1}\} := \{i/\sqrt{2}, \sqrt{2}/i\}$ factors out > 50 forms and operators of Penrose’s [89], [90] twistor geometry. $z := i/\sqrt{2}$ factors out the quantum field theoretic *double copy*’s formalism in Luna et al. [92, p. 13 (4.15)] and in White [93, p. 3 (18)].

Section 2.10.3 has found the presence of the complex constant $z := i/\sqrt{2}$ in the most accurate formulation of high-energy physics: Wightman’s distributions or functions [96]. The Langlands [95] program’s success, implicitly, confirms the correctness of Flajolet’s and Sedgewick’s statement. As of 2026, the pair $\{z, z^{-1}\}$ factors out systematically quantum field theoretic: (i) *operators and functions*, endowed with global or nonlocal properties, and (ii) *objects of differential topology*, expected by the decomposition of a smooth complex projective hypersurface, typically associated with spacelike separations or Grothendieck constants $K_G > 1$.

2.10.4 Cardioid and circle are degenerate limaçons over $\mathbb{C}\mathbb{P}^1$.

The relationship between triangular functions, Eulerian distribution local and limit law of the Gaussian type which sections 2.10.1–3 introduced, motivates that:

Lemma 2.22. *Let us denote as $r(\theta)$ the plane closed oval quartic parametric polar curve, called limaçon of Pascal, a transitional form between circle and cardioid, whose inverses are the classical conic sections. Then, the envelope*

$$r(\theta) = a \cos(\theta) + b \Big|_{\theta \in [0, 2\pi]_{\mathbb{R}}; a, b \in (-\infty, \infty)_{\mathbb{R}}} \in \mathbb{R} \tag{2.105}$$

of a one-parameter family of $n \rightarrow \infty$ curves of the Eulerian distribution function $|B(e^{i\theta})|_{\theta \in [0, 2\pi]_{\mathbb{R}}; u \in [-1, 1]_{\mathbb{R}}} \in \mathbb{R}$, is the quartic polar plane closed curve, called cardioid, corresponding to $2a = b = 0.5$

$$r(\theta) = z^2(z^2 \cos(\theta) - 1) \Big|_{\theta \in [0, 2\pi]_{\mathbb{R}}; z := \frac{i}{\sqrt{2}}} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{2} \cos(\theta) + 1 \right) \Big|_{\theta \in [0, 2\pi]_{\mathbb{R}}} \in \mathbb{R} \tag{2.106}$$

limit case of degenerate limaçon of Pascal. Let us denote as $P_A = 1/2\pi$ the Plouffe constant A, relevant to the limit case of degenerate limaçon of Pascal, called circle. Then, the Eulerian discrete probability distribution histogram, with mean μ_n , standard deviation σ_n and approximation p_n , obeys a local limit law of the Gaussian type which holds with speed $\epsilon_n \rightarrow 0$, and converges to the bell-shaped distribution of Gaussian density

$$\sup_{x \in \mathbb{R}} \left| \sigma_n p_{n, |\mu_n + x \sigma_n|} - \sqrt{\frac{P_A}{e^{x^2}}} \right| \leq \epsilon_n \tag{2.107}$$

Proof. (i) Let us consider a special case of that quartic algebraic curve without singular points, with origin O and polar equation [68, p. 113 (5.1.1)]:

$$r(\theta) = 2a \cos(\theta) + b \Big|_{\theta \in [0, 2\pi]_{\mathbb{R}}; a, b \in (-\infty, \infty)_{\mathbb{R}}} \in \mathbb{R} \tag{2.108}$$

which **Figure 4** plots. (ii) The (blue) envelope of the dimpled limaçon closely matches the function $|B(u)|_{|u|=1; B(1)=1}$ relative to the Eulerian distribution of $n = 60$ triangular functions, in the **Figure 4** (solid black) polar representation of (2.105) on the ray of angle θ [49, p. 698 Figure IX.15] (**Figure 3**). Section 2.10.2, p. 31, motivates the slight segmentation of the Eulerian distribution plot of **Figure 3** versus the regular plot of the dimpled limaçon in **Figure 4**. (iii) Discussing families of generating functions, Flajolet and Sedgewick [49, pp. 535–8] analysed the height of binary trees. The formal limit of their recurrence relation is the ordinary generating function of a classical or type A Catalan number $C_n = \binom{2n}{n} / (n + 1)$ [8, A000108], [39, pp. 103–374]. The central character of C_n is a type B Catalan number or central binomial coefficient [8, A000984], [33, pp. 182–9], [34, p. 78], [38, p. 274], [39, pp. 13–88], [51], [55]–[56], [103]–[105]. **Theorem 2.10–1**, **Lemma 2.15**, **Corollary 2.16**, **Corollary 2.21**, and **Theorem 2.24** are reformulating **Conjecture 1.1**, **Theorem 1.2**, **Corollary 1.3**, **Lemma 1.4**, and **Theorem 1.5** in terms of type B Catalan numbers or central binomial coefficients. (iv) One of the special cases of those binary trees satisfies the recurrence relation from which the complex generalization of dynamical systems theory’s *logistic map* arises in the Mandelbrot set [118, pp. 102–9], [119]. The latter region of convergence is a cardioid. Flajolet’s and Sedgewick’s recurrence relation [49, p. 536 (149)] is based on the logistic map [118, pp. 4–43 251–67]. (v) Limaçons (2.96) define transitional forms between a circle and a cardioid. Their general quartic polar plane closed curve is:

$$r(\theta) = a \cos(\theta) + b \Big|_{\theta \in [0, 2\pi]_{\mathbb{R}}; a, b \in (-\infty, \infty)_{\mathbb{R}}} \tag{2.109}$$

For $a = 0$, the degenerate limaçon is known as a *circle*. For example, the comparison circles in **Figures 3** and **4**. For $2a = b$, (2.109) degenerates in the quartic algebraic curve, known as *cardioid*, with a singular point and polar equation:

$$r(\theta) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{2} \cos(\theta) + 1 \right) \Big|_{\theta \in [0, 2\pi]_{\mathbb{R}}} \tag{2.110}$$

(2.110) is equal to the explicit solution in (2.106). (vi) Section 2.10.3 has introduced certain applications of the constant complex number $z := i/\sqrt{2}$ in the elsewhere region, corresponding to spacelike separations like those implicit in Grothendieck’s constants $K_G > 1$. It can be noted that:

$$z^2 = \left(\frac{i}{\sqrt{2}}\right)^2 = -\frac{1}{2} \tag{2.111}$$

Replacing (2.111) in (2.110) yields:

$$r(\theta) = -\frac{1}{2} \left(-\frac{1}{2} \cos(\theta) - 1\right) \Big|_{\theta \in [0, 2\pi]_{\mathbb{R}}} = z^2 (z^2 \cos(\theta) - 1) \Big|_{\theta \in [0, 2\pi]_{\mathbb{R}}; z := \frac{i}{\sqrt{2}}} \tag{2.112}$$

(2.112) is equal to identity in the complex constant z in (2.106). (vii) The cusp in the **Figure 5** cardioid represents an irreducible multi-germ, at a finite point set, with an ordinary double point [70]. Thus, fulfilling Flajolet’s and Sedgewick’s **Definition 1.8** [49, p. 16 Definition I.1.] of a *combinatorial class* as a surface in \mathbb{R}^4 . (viii) Catalan numbers [39], Dirichlet L -series [41], Pisot-Vijayaraghavan numbers (for example, $1 + \sqrt{2}$) [45], [83, pp. 9–16] and Eulerian numbers [54, pp. 210–6]–[56] are examples of elements of combinatorial classes over the projective space $\mathbb{C}P^1$ of complex lines through the origin in \mathbb{C}^2 , isomorphic to the 2-dimensional Riemann sphere [69, pp. 117–52]. (ix) Grothendieck constants’ applications in the classically-forbidden region of the harmonic oscillator (quantum computation, quantum communication, quantum finance, and quantum engineering) motivate a relevant example of the instanton-symmetric double well in quantum field theory, endowed with both nonlocal and local properties. Let us consider the minimal, irreducible quartic polynomial with roots over \mathbb{R}^4

$$q(x) = a_4 x^4 + a_2 x^2 + a_0 \tag{2.113}$$

and with constant coefficients $(a_4, a_2, a_0) \in \mathbb{Q} \setminus \{0\}$ on \mathbb{S}^1 . Three of its real classical critical points lie around the origin $O(0,0)$, and the fourth critical point at infinity $\sup q(x) = \infty$, has:

Definition 2.23. (Mond and Nuño-Ballesteros [70, pp. 13–5]). *An irreducible multi-germ at an infinite point set, with an ordinary double point.*

(x) In [4, p. 33 Remark 5.6], Braverman et al. denote $B_K(f, g)$ the König’s [2], [3] bilinear form. Bilinear forms and double points have long-standing relationships [71]. Double points play a prominent role in the description of physical objects endowed with nonlocal properties [121].

(xi) If we wish, we may write the density (2.90) of the Gaussian bell-shaped distribution, at the centre of **Figure 2**, in terms of Plouffe constant $P_A = 1/2\pi$ [37], [122], obtaining:

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi e^{x^2}}} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2\pi} \frac{1}{e^{x^2}}} = \sqrt{\frac{P_A}{e^{x^2}}} \tag{2.114}$$

Hence, we may express the supremum (2.90) of a sequence of discrete probability distributions, with mean μ_n , standard deviation σ_n , and approximation p_n which obey a local limit law of the Gaussian type with speed ϵ_n , as:

$$\sup_{x \in \mathbb{R}} \left| \sigma_n p_{n, \lfloor \mu_n + x \sigma_n \rfloor} - \sqrt{\frac{\mathcal{P}_A}{e^{x^2}}} \right| \leq \epsilon_n \quad (2.115)$$

(2.115) is equal to (2.107). (xii) [49, p. 535–8 Example VII.27] applies singularity analyses [70] to the height of simple varieties of trees. The latter's formal limit is the ordinary generating function of Catalan numbers. **Figure 8** plots the Mandelbrot set 180° rotated, after $n = 90$ iterations. The grey level of each point $z = x + iy \in \mathbb{C}$ has a relationship with the number of iterations necessary for the generating function to either diverge to a finite limit or to infinity. Inner darker regions converge to a finite limit. The outer darker regions, divergent to ∞ .

Figure 8. Mandelbrot set, after 90 iterations and a rotation 180°.

The claim follows. ■

2.10.5 Fourier infinite series expansion of a triangular function.

Section 2.10.5 defines and characterizes a special case of Fourier infinite series expansion that Pain [21], [22] recently studied, in the following sections called ‘‘Pain-Fourier series’’. [64] gives a succinct introduction to Fourier series. [65] and [66] offer their treatise-level account.

Definition 2.24. Let us denote as $\mathcal{F}(x)$ the Fourier infinite series expansion $\{a_n\}_{n \in [0, \infty)_{\mathbb{N}}}$ of the even parity triangular function [64, pp. 474–6 Example 2]:

$$\mathcal{F}(x) = \frac{1}{\cos\left(\frac{x}{4}\right)} \quad x \in [-\pi, \pi]_{\mathbb{R}} \quad (2.116)$$

a periodic function of period 8π , here restricted into $x \in [-\pi, \pi]_{\mathbb{R}}$, which is a special case of the Fourier series expansion [21], [22]:

$$\mathcal{F}(x) = \frac{a_0}{2} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} a_n \cos(nx) + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} b_n \sin(nx) \quad x \in [-\pi, \pi]_{\mathbb{R}} \quad (2.117)$$

The even parity of $\mathcal{F}(x)$ implies that $\forall n \in [1, \infty)_{\mathbb{N}}$, $b_n = 0$ reducing (2.117) to cosinusoidal terms:

$$\mathcal{F}(x) = \frac{a_0}{2} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} a_n \cos(nx) \quad x \in [-\pi, \pi]_{\mathbb{R}} \quad (2.118)$$

where the zeroth coefficient a_0 of the constant term [21, p. 2 (7)] reads:

$$a_0 = \frac{8}{\pi} \log(1 + \sqrt{2}) \approx 2.24439 \quad (2.119)$$

Based on (2.119), $a_0/(8/\pi) = \log(1 + \sqrt{2})$. **Table 2** section B.2 **Appendix B** shows a selection of its representations. Let us denote as g_0 a constant function:

$$g_0 := \frac{a_0}{2} = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \mathcal{F}(x) dx = \frac{4}{\pi} \log(1 + \sqrt{2}) \approx 1.12219 \quad (2.120)$$

which minimises the total square error denoted E , defined as [64, pp. 474–6 Example 2]–[66], in the Pain-Fourier series expansion $\{a_n\}_{n \in [0, \infty)_{\mathbb{N}}}$ of the even parity function $\mathcal{F}(x)$:

$$E := \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} [\mathcal{F}(x) - g(x)]^2 dx \quad (2.121)$$

Using any Computer Algebra System, for example [114], it is possible to see that the constant function g_0 's logarithmic, trigonometric and hyperbolic representations include:

$$g_0 = \frac{\log \lambda}{\pi} = \frac{\log(17 + 12\sqrt{2})}{\pi} = -\frac{8}{\pi} i \arctan\left(z \frac{\sqrt{2}}{1 + \sqrt{2}}\right) \Big|_{z:=\frac{i}{\sqrt{2}}} = \frac{8}{\pi} i \operatorname{arccot}\left(z(2 + \sqrt{2})\right) \Big|_{z:=\frac{i}{\sqrt{2}}}$$

$$= \frac{8}{\pi} \operatorname{arctanh}\left(\frac{1}{1 + \sqrt{2}}\right) = \frac{8}{\pi} \operatorname{arctanh}(\sqrt{2} - 1) = \frac{1}{\pi} \operatorname{arcsech}\left(\frac{1}{17}\right) \tag{2.122}$$

Let us denote as E_{2n} the topological invariant [72] called $2n^{\text{th}}$ Euler number or secant number [8, A000364], [54]–[56]. Let us denote as $T_{1/4}(\cos(x))$ the special evaluation of the Chebyshev classical polynomial of the first kind, of rational index $n = 1/4$ and argument $x = \cos(x)$, $x \in [-\pi, \pi]_{\mathbb{R}}$. Then, $\mathcal{F}(x)|_{x \in [-\pi, \pi]_{\mathbb{R}}}$ has polynomial and series representations:

$$\mathcal{F}(x) \Big|_{x \in [-\pi, \pi]_{\mathbb{R}}} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(-\frac{1}{16}\right)^n \frac{x^{2n}}{(2n)!} E_{2n} = \frac{1}{T_{1/4}(\cos(x))} \tag{2.123}$$

Let us denote as B_1, B_2 respectively the first and second Bernoulli numbers (see **Table 1** and [56]). Then, $\mathcal{F}(x)|_{x \in [-\pi, \pi]_{\mathbb{R}}}$ has trigonometric representations:

$$\mathcal{F}(x) \Big|_{x \in [-\pi, \pi]_{\mathbb{R}}} = \sec\left(\frac{x}{4}\right) = \frac{\cos\left(\frac{x}{4}\right)}{1 + \cos\left(\frac{x}{2}\right)} = \frac{\sec\left(\frac{x}{12}\right)}{2 \cos\left(\frac{x}{6}\right) - 1} = \frac{\sec(B_1 B_2 x)}{2 \cos(B_2 x) - 1} = \frac{\sec^2\left(\frac{x}{8}\right)}{2 - \sec^2\left(\frac{x}{8}\right)} \tag{2.124}$$

Setting the special value $z := i/\sqrt{2}$ [49, pp. 236–7], [51, p. 8 Theorem 3.2 (1)] gives exponential:

$$\mathcal{F}(x) \Big|_{x \in [-\pi, \pi]_{\mathbb{R}}} = \frac{2}{e^{\frac{i}{4}x} + \frac{1}{e^{\frac{i}{4}x}}} = \frac{2e^{\frac{i}{\sqrt{2}}\frac{x}{\sqrt{8}}}}{1 + e^{\frac{i}{\sqrt{2}}\frac{x}{\sqrt{8}}}} = \frac{2e^{\frac{z}{\sqrt{8}}x}}{1 + e^{\frac{z}{\sqrt{8}}x}} \Big|_{z:=\frac{i}{\sqrt{2}}} \tag{2.125}$$

and hyperbolic representations:

$$\mathcal{F}(x) \Big|_{x \in [-\pi, \pi]_{\mathbb{R}}} = \sqrt{\frac{\operatorname{sech}\left(\frac{x}{4}\right)}{\cosh\left(\frac{x}{4}\right)}} = \operatorname{sech}\left(-\frac{z}{\sqrt{8}}x\right) \Big|_{z:=\frac{i}{\sqrt{2}}} = \frac{1}{\cosh\left(-\frac{z}{\sqrt{8}}x\right)} \Big|_{z:=\frac{i}{\sqrt{2}}} \tag{2.126}$$

2.10.6 Fourier series, type B Catalan numbers, and Krivine bound.

Section 2.10.6 applies Fourier analyses to operator space theory and analytic combinatorics. Here, we show the consistency of Flajolet’s and Sedgewick’s [49, pp. 697–8 Example IX.35] (sections 2.10.1–2) results in analytic combinatorics, with those which, in operator space theory, König and Tomczak-Jaegermann [2], [3] and Braverman et al. [1] obtained. Let us denote as $\binom{2n}{n}$ the elements, called type B Catalan numbers or central binomial coefficients, of a subset of classical binomial coefficients $\binom{n}{k}$, [8, A000984], [33, pp. 182–9], [34, p. 78], [38, p. 274], [39, pp. 13–88], [51], [55]–[56], [103]–[105] and section A.4. The type B Catalan number is the central character of the classical type A Catalan number C_n [8, A000108].

Corollary 2.25. *The representations of the infimum of the distance of all other poles $\rho_j(u) \Big|_{j \in \mathbb{Z}; u \in \mathbb{C}; \Re(u) \in [0, \infty)}$ from the unique dominant singularity $\rho(u)$ of the bivariate generating function $F(z, u)$ include*

$$\inf_{j \in \mathbb{Z}} (\rho_j(u) - \rho(u)) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{4^n}{n^2} \binom{2n}{n}^{-1} = \frac{\pi}{\sqrt{8}} \tag{2.127}$$

$$= \frac{1}{a_0} \int_0^{\infty} \int_0^{\infty} \text{sign}(\vec{x}) \text{sign}(\vec{y}) \frac{\sin(\langle \vec{x}, \vec{y} \rangle)}{\sqrt{e^{\|\vec{x}\|_2^2 + \|\vec{y}\|_2^2}}} d\vec{x} d\vec{y} \tag{2.128}$$

$$= \frac{1}{4a_0} \sup_{\substack{f, g \in L_{\infty}(0, \infty) \\ f, g \in [-1, 1] \\ \text{almost} \\ \text{everywhere}}} \int_0^{\infty} \int_0^{\infty} f(\vec{x}) g(\vec{y}) \frac{\sin(\langle \vec{x}, \vec{y} \rangle)}{\sqrt{e^{\|\vec{x}\|_2^2 + \|\vec{y}\|_2^2}}} d\vec{x} d\vec{y} \tag{2.129}$$

$$= K_G^{\mathbb{R}} M_0 = L_{-8}(1) = \int_0^{\infty} \sin(x^2) dx = \int_0^{\infty} \cos(x^2) dx \tag{2.130}$$

Proof. In 2006, Sprugnoli [51, p. 7 Theorem 3.1] demonstrated that:

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{4^n}{n^2} \binom{2n}{n}^{-1} = \frac{\pi^2}{2} \approx 4.93480 \tag{2.131}$$

Taking the square root of both RHS and LHS and choosing the positive root gives:

$$\frac{\pi}{\sqrt{2}} = \pm \sqrt{\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{4^n}{n^2} \binom{2n}{n}^{-1}} \approx 2.22144 \tag{2.132}$$

The quotient of König’s [2]–[4, pp. 6 34–40 Theorem 1.4 (1.6)] **Theorem 1.2** (1.4) to the evaluation of a_0 (2.103) [21, p. 2 (7)] is equal to:

$$\frac{I_1}{a_0} = \sqrt{8} \log(1 + \sqrt{2}) \left(\frac{8}{\pi} \log(1 + \sqrt{2})\right)^{-1} = \frac{\pi}{\sqrt{8}} \tag{2.133}$$

(2.133) is equal to (2.127) and (2.128). After **Theorem 2.1**, the Braverman *et al.* [4, p. 5 (1.5)], [4, pp. 34–6], [8, A196525], supremum of the bilinear form $B_K(f, g)$, equals $M_0 = I_1/4$. Therefore

$$\frac{M_0}{a_0} = \frac{1}{4} \frac{I_1}{a_0} = \frac{1}{4} \sqrt{8} \log(1 + \sqrt{2}) \left(\frac{8}{\pi} \log(1 + \sqrt{2})\right)^{-1} = \frac{\pi}{4\sqrt{8}} \tag{2.134}$$

(2.134) is equal to (2.129). In (2.130), the leftmost identity immediately arises from **Lemma 2.0** and **Theorem 2.2**. The evaluation of $L_{-\beta}(1)$ (see section A.1) and the Fresnel integrals’ $S(x)$, $C(x)$ asymptotic limit $\lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} S(x) = \lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} C(x) = \pi/\sqrt{8}$ [32, p. 22], are both equal to the infimum of the separation of all other poles from the singularity $\rho(u)$ (2.93). The claim follows. ■

2.10.7 Zeroth coefficient of the Fourier series cosine expansion of a triangular function.

Section 2.10.7 applies Fourier analyses to operator space theory.

Proposition 2.26. *The zeroth coefficient a_0 of the Pain-Fourier cosine series expansion of the triangular function $\mathcal{F}(x)|_{x \in [-\pi, \pi]_{\mathbb{R}}}$, the Krivine bound $K_G^{\mathbb{R}} \leq c(f, g)^{-1}$ of Grothendieck’s inequality in the Hilbert space $\mathcal{H}^{\mathbb{R}}$, and the error function $\text{erf}(x)$ have closed-form expressions:*

$$K_G^{\mathbb{R}} \leq \frac{1}{c(f, g)} \leq \frac{4}{a_0} = \frac{2}{\mathcal{F}(x) - \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} a_n \cos(nx)|_{x \in [-\pi, \pi]_{\mathbb{R}}}} \tag{2.135}$$

$$a_0 = \log(1 + \sqrt{2}) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (1 - \text{erf}(x)^2) dx \tag{2.136}$$

Proof. Multiplying a_0 (2.119) by (1.6) [4, p. 10 Corollary 2.3] gives $a_0 K_G^{\mathbb{R}} \leq 4$. Dividing the latter’s LHS and RHS by a_0 yields $K_G^{\mathbb{R}} \leq 4/a_0$ which is identical to the central term of (2.135).

Hence, we may write (2.118) [64, pp. 474–6 Example 2]–[66] as:

$$\frac{a_0}{2} = \mathcal{F}(x) - \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} a_n \cos(nx) \tag{2.137}$$

Multiplication by 2 of the LHS and RHS gives:

$$a_0 = 2\mathcal{F}(x) - 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} a_n \cos(nx) \tag{2.138}$$

Replacing (2.138) in $a_0 K_G^{\mathbb{R}} = a_0 c(f, g)^{-1} = 4$. Recalling **Corollary 1.3** yields:

$$K_G^{\mathbb{R}} \leq \frac{1}{c(f, g)} \leq \frac{4}{a_0} = \frac{2}{\mathcal{F}(x) - \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} a_n \cos(nx)|_{x \in [-\pi, \pi]_{\mathbb{R}}}} \tag{2.139}$$

(2.139) is equal to the rightmost identity in (2.135). (A.9) connects the Plouffe constant $\mathcal{P}_A = 1/2\pi$ [37] to the error function $\operatorname{erf}(x)$ [32, pp. 262–4 289 364 423]:

$$16 \mathcal{P}_A \left(\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (1 - \operatorname{erf}(x)^2) dx \right)^{-1} = 1 \rightarrow 16 \frac{1}{2\pi} \left(\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (1 - \operatorname{erf}(x)^2) dx \right)^{-1} = 1 \tag{2.140}$$

hence

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (1 - \operatorname{erf}(x)^2) dx = \frac{8}{\pi} \tag{2.141}$$

Replacement of the RHS of (2.141) in the 0th coefficient a_0 of the Pain-Fourier cosine series expansion of the triangular function $\mathcal{F}(x)|_{x \in [-\pi, \pi]_{\mathbb{R}}}$ [21, p. 2 (7)], yields:

$$a_0 = \log(1 + \sqrt{2}) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (1 - \operatorname{erf}(x)^2) dx \tag{2.142}$$

The claim follows. ■

2.11 Apéry-type series and reciprocals of type B Catalan numbers.

2.11.1 König Theorem, and reciprocals of type B Catalan numbers.

We reword König’s and Tomczak-Jaegermann’s **Theorem 1.2**, demonstrating that the two-dimensional integrals M_0, I_1 have an Apéry-type series representation with reciprocals of those numbers which, in 2007, Devadoss [38, p. 274] characterised and called *type B Catalan numbers* or *central binomial coefficients* ([8, A000984], [33, pp. 182–9], [34, p. 78], [39, pp. 13–88], [51], [55]–[56], [103]–[105] and section A.4). Let us denote as

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-4)^n}{2n+1} \binom{2n}{n}^{-1} = -\frac{\log(\sqrt{2}-1)}{\sqrt{2}} \in \mathbb{C} \setminus \mathbb{A} \subset \mathcal{P} \subset \mathbb{C} \tag{2.143}$$

the infinite, alternating Apéry-type series, with reciprocals of type B Catalan Numbers $\binom{2n}{n}$.

Theorem 2.27. (König and Tomczak-Jaegermann [2]–[4, pp. 6 38–40 Theorem 1.4]). *For every Lebesgue measurable function $f, g : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \{-1, 1\}$ we have an infinite Apéry-type series with reciprocals of type B Catalan numbers $\binom{2n}{n}$, such that*

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-4)^n}{2n+1} \binom{2n}{n}^{-1} = \sup_{\substack{f, g \in L_{\infty}(0, \infty) \\ f, g \in [-1, 1] \\ \text{almost} \\ \text{everywhere}}} \int_0^{\infty} \int_0^{\infty} f(\vec{x})g(\vec{y}) \frac{\sin(\langle \vec{x}, \vec{y} \rangle)}{\sqrt{e^{\|\vec{x}\|_2^2 + \|\vec{y}\|_2^2}}} d\vec{x}d\vec{y} \tag{2.144}$$

$$\leq \int_0^{\infty} \int_0^{\infty} \text{sign}(\vec{x})\text{sign}(\vec{y}) \frac{\sin(\langle \vec{x}, \vec{y} \rangle)}{\sqrt{e^{\|\vec{x}\|_2^2 + \|\vec{y}\|_2^2}}} d\vec{x}d\vec{y} = 4 \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-4)^n}{2n+1} \binom{2n}{n}^{-1} \tag{2.145}$$

Proof. The RHS of (2.143) has an alternate form:

$$-\frac{\log(\sqrt{2}-1)}{\sqrt{2}} = \frac{\log(1+\sqrt{2})}{\sqrt{2}} \tag{2.146}$$

which is the exact evaluation of M_0 . Hence, the identity [8, A196525]

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-4)^n}{2n+1} \binom{2n}{n}^{-1} = \frac{\log(1+\sqrt{2})}{\sqrt{2}} \tag{2.147}$$

Thus, recovering **Theorem 1.2**, **Corollary 1.3**, and **Lemma 1.4**’s natural logarithm of the Pisot-Vijayaraghavan number $\alpha_2 = 1 + \sqrt{2}$ from $\sqrt{2} - 1$. Pisot-Vijayaraghavan numbers are outlined in section B.1, and [83, pp. 9–16]. [45] gives their treatise-level account. (1.3), and (1.5) [1, p. 36 (6.10)] are equal to the RHS of (2.147). The quadruple of the RHS of (2.147) is equal to the

evaluation of (1.4). After **Theorem 2.1**, we can aggregate those results, writing

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-4)^n}{2n+1} \binom{2n}{n}^{-1} = M_0 \leq I_1 = 4 \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-4)^n}{2n+1} \binom{2n}{n}^{-1} \tag{2.148}$$

(2.148) is equal to (2.144–5). The claim follows. ■

2.11.2 König’s theorem over $\mathbb{C} \cong \mathbb{R}^2$.

Section A.4 gives sections 2.11.2–3 relevant notation, main definitions and references. As an application of Cauchy’s residue theorem, **Theorem 2.26** demonstrates that the supremum of the bilinear form $M_0 = \sup B_K(f, g)$ in the König’s and Tomczak-Jaegermann’s **Theorem 1.2** is an elementary function of the real part of the function $\arctan z$ [51, p. 8 Theorem 3.2 (1)]. Then **Theorem 1.2** can be alternatively enunciated as

$$\Re \left(\frac{\arctan z}{\sqrt{2}} \right) \Big|_{z \in \mathbb{C}} = M_0 \leq I_1 = \Re(\sqrt{8} \arctan z) \tag{2.149}$$

Theorem 2.28. (König and Tomczak-Jaegermann [2]–[4, pp. 6 38–40 Theorem 1.4]). *For every Lebesgue measurable function $f, g : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \{-1, 1\}$, we have*

$$\Re \left(\frac{\arctan z}{\sqrt{2}} \right) \Big|_{z := i/\sqrt{2} \in \mathbb{C} \cong \mathbb{R}^2} = \sup_{\substack{f, g \in L_\infty(0, \infty) \\ f, g \in [-1, 1] \\ \text{almost} \\ \text{everywhere}}} \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty f(\vec{x})g(\vec{y}) \frac{\sin(\langle \vec{x}, \vec{y} \rangle)}{\sqrt{e^{\|\vec{x}\|_2^2 + \|\vec{y}\|_2^2}}} d\vec{x}d\vec{y} \tag{2.150}$$

$$\leq \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty \text{sign}(\vec{x})\text{sign}(\vec{y}) \frac{\sin(\langle \vec{x}, \vec{y} \rangle)}{\sqrt{e^{\|\vec{x}\|_2^2 + \|\vec{y}\|_2^2}}} d\vec{x}d\vec{y} = \Re(\sqrt{8} \arctan z) \Big|_{z := \frac{i}{\sqrt{2}} \in \mathbb{C} \cong \mathbb{R}^2} \tag{2.151}$$

Proof. **Theorem 2.28** holds over the ground of [51, p. 8 Theorem 3.2 (1)]. Hence, the supremum $M = \sup B_K(f, g)$ of the bilinear form $B_K(f, g)$, has an evaluation M_0 as the real part of the complex number iM_0 obtained by the ratio $\arctan z$ to $\sqrt{2}$, because

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \arctan z \Big|_{z := \frac{i}{\sqrt{2}}} = -\frac{i}{\sqrt{2}} \log(\sqrt{2} - 1) = \frac{i}{\sqrt{2}} \log(1 + \sqrt{2}) = iM_0 \tag{2.152}$$

whose real part, is equal to

$$M_0 = \Re(iM_0) = \Re\left(\frac{\arctan z}{\sqrt{2}}\right) = \Re\left(\frac{i}{\sqrt{2}}\log(1 + \sqrt{2})\right) = \frac{\log(1 + \sqrt{2})}{\sqrt{2}} \tag{2.153}$$

(2.153) is equal to (2.150). The ratio (1.4) to (2.1) is $I_1/M_0 = 4$ (2.4). Hence, from (2.131):

$$I_1 = 4 \Re(iM_0) = 4 \Re\left(\frac{\arctan z}{\sqrt{2}}\right) = \Re\left(\frac{4}{\sqrt{2}} \arctan z\right) = \Re(\sqrt{8} \arctan z) \tag{2.154}$$

(2.154) is equal to (2.151). The claim follows. ■

2.12 Krivine bound as ratio of Gauss hypergeometric functions of symmetric unit arguments.

The Krivine bound of the Grothendieck inequality in the Hilbert space $\mathcal{H}^{\mathbb{R}}$ has an expression as the ratio of hypergeometric functions of symmetric unit arguments.

Theorem 2.29. *The Krivine upper bound $K_G^{\mathbb{R}}$ of Grothendieck’s inequality is the ratio of hypergeometric functions of symmetric unit arguments:*

$$K_G^{\mathbb{R}} \leq \frac{1}{c(f, g)} \leq \frac{{}_2F_1\left(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}; \frac{3}{2}; 1\right)}{{}_2F_1\left(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}; \frac{3}{2}; -1\right)} = \frac{\pi}{2 \log(1 + \sqrt{2})} \tag{2.155}$$

Proof. Let us consider the Gauss hypergeometric function ${}_2F_1(\cdot)$, whose representations include, but are not limited to, those [32], [64]:

$${}_2F_1\left(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}; \frac{3}{2}; x\right) = \frac{\log(\sqrt{1-x} + \sqrt{-x})}{\sqrt{-x}} = \frac{\arcsin(\sqrt{x})}{\sqrt{x}} \tag{2.156}$$

For $x = 1$, (2.156) gives [8, A019669]:

$${}_2F_1\left(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}; \frac{3}{2}; 1\right) = \frac{\log(\sqrt{1-1} + \sqrt{-1})}{\sqrt{-1}} = \frac{\arcsin(\sqrt{1})}{\sqrt{1}} = \frac{\pi}{2} \tag{2.157}$$

For $x = -1$ (2.156) is equal to [8, A091648], [61, p. 92 Table 1 (7.3.6.28a)]:

$${}_2F_1\left(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}; \frac{3}{2}; -1\right) = \frac{\log(\sqrt{1+1} + \sqrt{1})}{\sqrt{1}} = \frac{\arcsin(i)}{i} = \log(1 + \sqrt{2}) \tag{2.158}$$

Hence, the ratio:

$${}_2F_1\left(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}; \frac{3}{2}; 1\right) / {}_2F_1\left(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}; \frac{3}{2}; -1\right) = \frac{\pi}{2} \frac{1}{\log(1 + \sqrt{2})} \tag{2.159}$$

is the evaluation of $K_G^{\mathbb{R}}$ **Lemma 1.3** [8, A088367], [4, p. 10 Corollary 2.3]. The claim follows. ■

2.13 Universal parabolic constant.

Section 2.13 links the König’s integrals M_0, I_1 to the *universal parabolic* constant [34, pp. 70–1] which, in 2013 Sondow (see [107]) found having a closed-form expression with the perimeter of an arbitrary *arbelos* and π^{-1} . For a description of the geometric object called “arbelos”, see [68].

Definition 2.30. The scale-invariant ratio, constant across all parabolas due to their similarity under affine transformations, of the parabolic segment arc comprised between the latus rectum’s end points to any parabola’s semilatus rectum or focal parameter.

Let us denote as $P \in \mathbb{C} \setminus \mathbb{A} \subset \mathcal{P} \subset \mathbb{C}$ the *universal parabolic* constant of geometric probability [8, A103710]:

$$P := 2 \int_0^1 \sqrt{1+x^2} dx = \sqrt{2} + \log(1 + \sqrt{2}) \tag{2.160}$$

Theorem 2.31. (König and Tomczak-Jaegermann [2]–[4, pp. 6 38–40 Theorem 1.4]). *For every Lebesgue measurable function $f, g : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \{-1, 1\}$, we have*

$$1 - \frac{P}{\sqrt{2}} = \sup_{\substack{f, g \in L_\infty(0, \infty) \\ f, g \in [-1, 1] \\ \text{almost} \\ \text{everywhere}}} \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty f(\vec{x})g(\vec{y}) \frac{\sin(\langle \vec{x}, \vec{y} \rangle)}{\sqrt{e^{\|\vec{x}\|_2^2 + \|\vec{y}\|_2^2}}} d\vec{x}d\vec{y} \tag{2.161}$$

$$\leq \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty \text{sign}(\vec{x})\text{sign}(\vec{y}) \frac{\sin(\langle \vec{x}, \vec{y} \rangle)}{\sqrt{e^{\|\vec{x}\|_2^2 + \|\vec{y}\|_2^2}}} d\vec{x}d\vec{y} = \sqrt{8}(\sqrt{2} - P) \tag{2.162}$$

Proof. (2.160) can be written as:

$$\log(1 + \sqrt{2}) = \sqrt{2} - P \tag{2.163}$$

whose replacement in the **Theorem 1.2** integral I_1 , gives:

$$I_1 = \sqrt{8}(\sqrt{2} - P) = 4 - \sqrt{8}P = \sqrt{8}(\sqrt{2} - P) \tag{2.164}$$

(2.164) is equal to (2.162). After **Theorem 2.1**, $I_1 = 4M_0$. Hence:

$$\frac{4 - \sqrt{8}P}{4} = 1 - \frac{P}{\sqrt{2}} = M_0 \leq I_1 = \sqrt{8}(\sqrt{2} - P) \tag{2.165}$$

(2.165) is equal to (2.161–2). The claim follows. ■

2.14 The edge of the square $[-1, 1]_{\mathbb{R}} \times [-1, 1]_{\mathbb{R}}$.

A corollary connects **Theorem 1.2** integrals M_0, I_1 to remarkable expressions that, in 2014, Dalthorp [52, p. 68] found in geometric probability. Based on the classical trigonometric identity $\int \sec(x) dx = \log |\sec(x) + \tan(x)|$, let us denote as $\langle d_0 \rangle$ the average distance:

$$\langle d_0 \rangle := \frac{2}{\pi} \int_{-\pi/4}^{\pi/4} \sec(x) dx = \frac{4}{\pi} \log(1 + \sqrt{2}) \tag{2.166}$$

in a random direction x , between centre and edges of a $[-1, 1]_{\mathbb{R}} \times [-1, 1]_{\mathbb{R}}$ square, of evaluation twice [8, A355186]. Let $f, g : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a Krivine rounding scheme [1, p. 8 Definition 2.1]. Let us denote as $c(f, g)$ the evaluation of (1.7) in **Lemma 1.4** [4, p. 11 Lemma 2.4].

Corollary 2.32.

$$\langle d_0 \rangle \geq 2 c(f, g) \geq \frac{2}{K_G^{\mathbb{R}}} \tag{2.167}$$

Proof. In [52, p. 68], the expectation value of $\langle d_0 \rangle$ is twice that of $c(f, g)$ in **Lemma 1.4** (1.7). The claim follows. ■

Let us denote as $\langle d_1 \rangle$ the average distance to a random point on the edge of the $[-1, 1]_{\mathbb{R}} \times [-1, 1]_{\mathbb{R}}$ square.

$$\langle d_1 \rangle := \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} + \frac{1}{2} \log(1 + \sqrt{2}) \tag{2.168}$$

Theorem 2.33. (König and Tomczak-Jaegermann [2]–[4, pp. 6 38–40 Theorem 1.4]). *For every Lebesgue measurable function $f, g : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \{-1, 1\}$, we have*

$$\sqrt{2} \langle d_1 \rangle - 1 = \sup_{\substack{f, g \in L_\infty(0, \infty) \\ f, g \in [-1, 1] \\ \text{almost} \\ \text{everywhere}}} \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty f(\vec{x})g(\vec{y}) \frac{\sin(\langle \vec{x}, \vec{y} \rangle)}{\sqrt{e^{\|\vec{x}\|_2^2 + \|\vec{y}\|_2^2}}} d\vec{x}d\vec{y} \tag{2.169}$$

$$\leq \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty \text{sign}(\vec{x})\text{sign}(\vec{y}) \frac{\sin(\langle \vec{x}, \vec{y} \rangle)}{\sqrt{e^{\|\vec{x}\|_2^2 + \|\vec{y}\|_2^2}}} d\vec{x}d\vec{y} = 4(\sqrt{2} \langle d_1 \rangle - 1) \tag{2.170}$$

Proof. $\langle d_1 \rangle$ (2.168) [52, p. 68], can be written as an elementary function of the supremum $M_0 = M := \sup B_K(f, g)$ of the bilinear form in **Theorem 1.2**:

$$\langle d_1 \rangle := \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \left(1 + \frac{\log(1 + \sqrt{2})}{\sqrt{2}} \right) = \frac{1 + M_0}{\sqrt{2}} \tag{2.171}$$

which, solved for M_0 gives:

$$\sqrt{2} \langle d_1 \rangle = 1 + M_0 \Rightarrow M_0 = \sqrt{2} \langle d_1 \rangle - 1 \tag{2.172}$$

(2.172) is equal to (2.169). Based on **Theorem 2.0–1**, we can reword **Theorem 1.2** as:

$$\sqrt{2} \langle d_1 \rangle - 1 = M_0 \leq I_1 = 4(\sqrt{2} \langle d_1 \rangle - 1) \tag{2.173}$$

(2.173) is equal to (2.169–70). The claim follows. ■

2.15 Square error of the Fourier expansion of a triangular function.

Corollary 2.34. *The average distance $\langle d_0 \rangle$ in a random direction x , between the centre of the $[-1, 1]_{\mathbb{R}} \times [-1, 1]_{\mathbb{R}}$ square and its edges, equals the constant function g_0 which minimises the total square error E in the estimation of the Pain-Fourier series expansion of the triangular function $\mathcal{F}(x) = 1/\cos(x/4)|_{x \in [-\pi, \pi]_{\mathbb{R}}}$*

$$\langle d_0 \rangle = \mathcal{F}(x) - \sum_{n=1}^\infty a_n \cos(nx) = g_0 = \frac{a_0}{2} \tag{2.174}$$

Proof. Based on [21], [22], [64, pp. 474–6 Example 2], the ratio g_0 to $\langle d_0 \rangle$ is equal to:

$$\frac{g_0}{\langle d_0 \rangle} = \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \frac{\mathcal{F}(x)}{2\pi} dx \Big/ \int_{-\pi/4}^{\pi/4} \frac{2}{\pi} \sec(x) dx = \frac{4\pi \log(1 + \sqrt{2})}{\pi^4 \log(1 + \sqrt{2})} = 1 \tag{2.175}$$

Hence, $g_0 = \langle d_0 \rangle$. From (2.118–20), those identities arise:

$$\langle d_0 \rangle = \mathcal{F}(x) - \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} a_n \cos(nx) = g_0 = \frac{a_0}{2} \tag{2.176}$$

(2.176) is equal to (2.174). The claim follows. ■

Corollary 2.35. *The constant function g_0 which minimizes the total square error E of the Pain-Fourier cosine series expansion $\{a_n\}_{n \in [0, \infty)_{\mathbb{N}}}$ of the even parity function $\mathcal{F}(x) = 1/\cos(x/4)|_{x \in [-\pi, \pi]_{\mathbb{R}}}$ and the Krivine bound $K_G^{\mathbb{R}}$ have closed-form expression:*

$$g_0 K_G^{\mathbb{R}} = 2 \tag{2.177}$$

Proof. If $f, g : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a Krivine rounding scheme, then $K_G^{\mathbb{R}} \leq c(f, g)^{-1} \leq \pi/(2 \log(1 + \sqrt{2}))$ Corollary 1.3 [4, p. 10 Corollary 2.3]. The ratio of g_0 to $c(f, g)$ is equal to:

$$\frac{g_0}{c(f, g)} = \frac{4 \log(1 + \sqrt{2})}{\pi} \frac{\pi}{2 \log(1 + \sqrt{2})} = 2 \implies g_0 K_G^{\mathbb{R}} = 2 \tag{2.178}$$

(2.178) is equal to (2.177). The claim follows. ■

2.16 Ratio $c_{\mathbb{C}}/c_{\mathbb{R}}$ of projection constants of 1-symmetric l_p^n -spaces, $p \in [1, 2]_{\mathbb{R}}$.

Among the Plouffe constant P_A relationships [37], [122], section A.3 lists König’s, Schütt and Tomczak-Jaegermann [17, p. 2 Theorem 1] projection constants of 1-symmetric spaces l_p^n -spaces, $\forall p \in [1, 2]_{\mathbb{R}}$, $c_{\mathbb{R}} := \sqrt{2/\pi} = 2\sqrt{P_A}$ [8, A076668], and $c_{\mathbb{C}} := \sqrt{\pi}/2 = 1/\sqrt{8P_A}$ [8, A019704]. Invariants of

Analytic combinatorics: in (2.41), **Theorem 2.10** (2.45–6), and (2.93).

Analytic number theory: in **Lemma 2.13** and **Lemma 2.14** (2.62–3).

Operator space theory: in **Theorem 2.2** (2.5), **Corollary 2.3** (2.7) and **Corollary 2.16**;

Fourier analysis: in **Corollary 2.25** (2.127–30);

share the same ratio $c_{\mathbb{C}}/c_{\mathbb{R}} = L_{-8}(1) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} L_8(1, \chi_4)$ [8, A093954] of Banach space theory’s projection constants. To keep this paper self-contained, the following corollary refers to the only analytic combinatorics case [49, p. 697 Example IX.35] of the bivariate generating function $F(z, u)$ in the polar representation of an Eulerian discrete distribution.

Corollary 2.36. *Those closed-form expressions hold:*

$$\frac{c_{\mathbb{C}}}{c_{\mathbb{R}}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{32} \mathcal{P}_A} = \inf_{j \in \mathbb{Z}} (\rho_j(u) - \rho(u)) = L_{-8}(1) = \frac{\pi}{\sqrt{8}} \tag{2.179}$$

Proof. After [17, p. 2 Theorem 1], the evaluation of the quotient $c_{\mathbb{C}}/c_{\mathbb{R}}$ among Banach space theory’s projection constants of 1-symmetric spaces l_p^m -spaces, $p \in [1, 2]_{\mathbb{R}}$ reads [8, A093954]:

$$\frac{c_{\mathbb{C}}}{c_{\mathbb{R}}} = \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2} \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2}} = \frac{\pi}{\sqrt{8}} \tag{2.180}$$

The ratio $c_{\mathbb{C}}/c_{\mathbb{R}}$ and Plouffe constant \mathcal{P}_A [37], [122] have a closed-form expression:

$$\frac{c_{\mathbb{C}}}{c_{\mathbb{R}}} = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{\mathcal{P}_A}\sqrt{8} \mathcal{P}_A} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{32} \mathcal{P}_A} = \frac{\pi}{\sqrt{32} \arctan(2^{-1})} \tag{2.181}$$

(2.93) evaluates the infimum of the distance $\rho_j(u) - \rho(u)$, $j \in \mathbb{Z}$ of all other poles from the singularity $\rho(u)$ of the bivariate generating function $F(z, u)$ as [8, A093954]:

$$\inf_{j \in \mathbb{Z}} (\rho_j(u) - \rho(u)) = \frac{\pi}{\sqrt{8}} \tag{2.182}$$

(2.182) is the exact evaluation (A.3) of the Dirichlet L -series $L_{-8}(1) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} L_8(1, \chi_4)$. Hence, $c_{\mathbb{C}}/c_{\mathbb{R}} = L_{-8}(1)$ and, after (2.180–1), we have [8, A093954]:

$$\frac{c_{\mathbb{C}}}{c_{\mathbb{R}}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{32} \mathcal{P}_A} = \inf_{j \in \mathbb{Z}} (\rho_j(u) - \rho(u)) = L_{-8}(1) = \frac{\pi}{\sqrt{8}} \tag{2.183}$$

(2.183) is equal to (2.179). The claim follows. ■

2.17 Super regularised product over all primes and generalized Stieltjes constant $\gamma_1(m/8)$.

Based on **Proposition 2.6** (Coffey [84, p. 9 Proposition 7 (d)]), **Proposition 2.7** reformulated the the supremum $M_0 = \sup B_K(f, g)$ of the König’s bilinear form $B_K(f, g)$, in terms of the generalised Stieltjes constants $\gamma_1(m/8)|_{m=\{1; 3; 5; 7\}}$ and of the Archimedes’ constant π [8, A000796]. Using **Theorem A.1** [44, p. 78 Theorem 8], [45, p. 3] notation and definition (see section

A.2), we deduce the expression for the super-regularised product over all prime numbers p in terms of $\gamma_1(m/8)|_{m=\{1; 3; 5; 7\}}$ alone.

Theorem 2.37. *The super-regularised product $\prod_p p$ over all prime numbers p , and the generalised Stieltjes constants $\gamma_1(m/8)|_{m=\{1; 3; 5; 7\}}$ at rational argument have a closed-form expression:*

$$\prod_p p = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^k}{k!} \gamma_1\left(\frac{m}{8}\right) \Big|_{m=\{1; 3; 5; 7\}} \tag{2.184}$$

Proof. If we wish, we may write Coffey’s [84, p. 9 Proposition 7 (d)] **Proposition 2.6** (2.25) as

$$4\pi^2 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^k}{k!} \left(\gamma_k\left(\frac{1}{8}\right) - \gamma_k\left(\frac{3}{8}\right) - \gamma_k\left(\frac{5}{8}\right) + \gamma_k\left(\frac{7}{8}\right) \right) \tag{2.185}$$

Replacement of (A.7) in the LHS of (2.185) yields

$$\prod_p p = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^k}{k!} \gamma_1\left(\frac{m}{8}\right) \Big|_{m=\{1; 3; 5; 7\}} \tag{2.186}$$

(2.186) is equal to (2.184). The claim follows. ■

2.18 Complex continued fractions.

2.18.1 Introduction.

Section 2.18.1 succinctly introduces Nakada’s [82] theorem in the metrical theory of complex continued fractions and the (square lattice spanning tree) constant [8, A218387], which Schmidt [83, pp. 215–26] established in 1993 by applying Nakada’s theory to ergodic systems. Kodaira introduces the theory of the Riemann sphere in [69, pp. 117–52] and of the Riemann surfaces in [69, pp. 247–393]. The Riemann sphere is equivalent to the complex projective line $\mathbb{C}P^1 \cong \mathbb{R}^4$. The Möbius group of transformations acts on the Riemann sphere in Nakada [82], Schmidt [83, pp. 215–26], Frauediener and Penrose [87, pp. 478–88], and Penrose and Rindler [88, pp. 8–32], [89]. Let us denote as \mathcal{C} and \mathcal{C}^* a pair of complex planes. Let us denote $(a, b, c, d)|_{ad-bc \neq 0} \in \mathbb{C}$ elements of the algebraic integers or Gaussian integers subfield of \mathbb{C} [48], entries of a 2×2 matrix $A = \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix}, |\det A| = 1$ on the union $\{\mathcal{C} \cup \{\infty\}\} \cup \{\mathcal{C}^* \cup \{\infty\}\}$ of extended complex planes. Let $z \in \mathbb{C}$ be an arbitrary complex number. Nakada’s main result [82 p. 279 Theorem] assumes the linear fractional transformation [82, p. 280]:

$$g_A(z) = \frac{az + b}{cz + d} \tag{2.187}$$

If $\det A = \pm 1$ then $g_A(z)$ acts separately on \mathcal{C} and \mathcal{C}^* . If $\det A = \pm i$ then $g_A(z)$ swaps \mathcal{C} and \mathcal{C}^* . (2.187) corresponds to a general Möbius transformation. On that ground, Schmidt [83, pp. 215–26] considered Apollonian packings, in the upper half-plane $\mathcal{I} \subset \mathbb{C}$ of vertices $(\infty, 0, 1)$ called Farey sets of generation 0. Let us denote as:

$$\frac{p}{q} \Big|_{p,q \in \mathbb{Z}[i] = \{z=x+iy \in \mathbb{C} : x,y \in \mathbb{Z}; q \neq 0; z \in \mathcal{I}} \tag{2.188}$$

an irreducible fraction between algebraic integers [48]. Schmidt [83, p. 221] found that fractions p/q can be convergents of z if:

$$\left| z - \frac{p}{q} \right| \leq \left(1 + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \right)^{-1} |q|^{-2} \tag{2.189}$$

If α_2 denotes the Pisot-Vijayaraghavan number [8, A014176] and $\bar{\alpha}_2$ its conjugate, (2.189) can be written as:

$$\left| z - \frac{p}{q} \right| |q|^2 \leq \frac{\sqrt{2}}{\alpha_2} = -\sqrt{2}\bar{\alpha}_2 \tag{2.190}$$

Based on Nakada’s [82 p. 279 Theorem] main result, Schmidt established the constant [8, A218387], [83, p. 225]:

$$\frac{4}{\pi} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{(2n-1)^2} = \frac{4}{\pi} G = \frac{1 - \frac{1}{9} + \frac{1}{25} - \frac{1}{49} + \frac{1}{81} - \frac{1}{121} + \frac{1}{169} - \dots}{1 - \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{5} - \frac{1}{7} + \frac{1}{9} - \frac{1}{11} + \frac{1}{13} - \dots} \approx 1.16624 \tag{2.191}$$

where G denotes the quadratic Dirichlet L -series $L_{-4}(2)$ called *Catalan constant* (see [8, A006752], [99, p. 14 Table 22] and section A.1). Schmidt noted that, curiously, that series representation is reminiscent of that of the Lévy constant [8, A086702], [32, pp. 59–65] of paramount importance in the theory of dynamical systems [118], [119].

2.18.2 Action of the Möbius group of transformations on the Riemann sphere.

Section 2.18.2 shows that **Theorem 1.2** [2]–[4, pp. 6 38–40 Theorem 1.4] can be reworded in the perspective of Schmidt-Nakada’s ergodic theory of complex continued fractions [83, pp. 215–26]. The Pisot-Vijayaraghavan number $\lambda = 17 + 12\sqrt{2}$ which Apéry [42, p. 13], [43], [87, pp. 784–6], [132] demonstrated to imply irrationality of the Riemann zeta-function $\zeta(3)$ [8, A002117] met in section 2.8.3, and the condition (2.189–90) for algebraic integers’ [48] fractions convergence are proved identical to **Theorem 1.2**’s upper bound I_1 . Let us make the following substitution in the LHS of (2.189):

$$\left| z - \frac{p}{q} \right| |q|^2 \longrightarrow c_0 \tag{2.192}$$

Theorem 2.38. (König and Tomczak-Jaegermann [1, pp. 6 38–40 Theorem 1.4]–[3]).

For every Lebesgue measurable function $f, g : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \{-1, 1\}$, we have

$$\log \left(\sqrt[8]{\lambda^4 \sqrt{\lambda}} \right) c_0 = \sup_{\substack{f, g \in L_\infty(0, \infty) \\ f, g \in \{-1, 1\} \\ \text{almost} \\ \text{everywhere}}} \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty f(\vec{x}) g(\vec{y}) \frac{\sin(\langle \vec{x}, \vec{y} \rangle)}{\sqrt{e^{\|\vec{x}\|_2^2 + \|\vec{y}\|_2^2}}} d\vec{x} d\vec{y} \tag{2.193}$$

$$\leq \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty \text{sign}(\vec{x}) \text{sign}(\vec{y}) \frac{\sin(\langle \vec{x}, \vec{y} \rangle)}{\sqrt{e^{\|\vec{x}\|_2^2 + \|\vec{y}\|_2^2}}} d\vec{x} d\vec{y} = \log \left(\sqrt{\lambda^4 \sqrt{\lambda}} \right) c_0 \tag{2.194}$$

Proof. The ratio of the LHS of (2.189) to the evaluation M_0 of the supremum of the bilinear form (1.3) is equal to:

$$\frac{c_0}{M_0} = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{1 + \sqrt{2}} \left(\frac{\log(1 + \sqrt{2})}{\sqrt{2}} \right)^{-1} = \frac{2(\sqrt{2} - 1)}{\log(1 + \sqrt{2})} \tag{2.195}$$

whose solution for M_0 yields that exact evaluation and closed-form expression:

$$M_0 = \frac{\log(1 + \sqrt{2})}{2(\sqrt{2} - 1)} c_0 = \log \left((1 + \sqrt{2})^{\frac{1 + \sqrt{2}}{2}} \right) c_0 = \log \left(\sqrt{\alpha_2^{\alpha_2}} \right) c_0 \tag{2.196}$$

$$= \log \left(\sqrt[8]{(17 + 12\sqrt{2})^4 \sqrt{17 + 12\sqrt{2}}} \right) c_0 = \log \left(\sqrt[4]{\sqrt{\lambda^4 \sqrt{\lambda}}} \right) c_0 = \log \left(\sqrt[8]{\lambda^4 \sqrt{\lambda}} \right) c_0 \tag{2.197}$$

(2.197) is equal to (2.193). After **Theorem 2.1** (2.3) the ratio $I_1/M_0 = 1/4$. Hence:

$$I_1 = 4M_0 = \frac{\log(17 + 12\sqrt{2})}{2(\sqrt{2} - 1)} c_0 = \log \left(\sqrt[2]{17 + 12\sqrt{2}} \sqrt[4]{17 + 12\sqrt{2}} \right) c_0 = \log \left(\sqrt{\lambda^4 \sqrt{\lambda}} \right) c_0 \tag{2.198}$$

where λ denotes the Pisot-Vijayaraghavan number $\lambda = \alpha_2^4 = 17 + 12\sqrt{2}$ [8, A156164], [43], [45], [42, p. 13], [83, pp. 9–16]. (2.198) is equal to (2.194). The claim follows. ■

2.18.3 Sinus cardinal function $\text{sinc}(\pi/4)$ as reciprocal of $\inf(\rho_j(\mathbf{u}) - \rho(\mathbf{u}))$.

Section 2.18.3 proposes Fourier analysis as a natural meeting place of quantum information theory and analytic combinatorics' ideas. The so-called "Polya's drunkard problem" is an example of Hadamard closure [49, pp. 423–5 Theorem V.11], playing a major role in analytic combinatorics [49] and quantum information theory [117]. Finch and Borwein demonstrated that its case $d = 2$ involves the constant denoted B [8, A185280], [34, p. 49], [49, pp. 425–6 Example VI.14]:

$$B = 1 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(\left(\frac{1}{4^n} \binom{2n}{n} \right)^2 - \frac{1}{\pi n} \right) = \frac{4}{\pi} \log 2 \approx 0.88524 \quad (2.199)$$

where the factor $4/\pi$ is the reciprocal of the classical Leibniz's infinite series representation of $\pi/4$ [8, A003881]:

$$\frac{\pi}{4} = 1 - \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{5} - \frac{1}{7} + \frac{1}{9} - \frac{1}{11} + \frac{1}{13} - \dots \approx 0.785398 \quad (2.200)$$

The ratio of the Schmidt constant to the Finch-Borwein constant B involves the Catalan constant \mathbf{G}

$$\frac{4 \mathbf{G}}{\pi B} = \frac{4}{\pi} \mathbf{G} / \left(\frac{4}{\pi} \log 2 \right) = \frac{\mathbf{G}}{\log 2} \approx 1.321459 \quad (2.201)$$

The multiplicative inverse of $\pi/4$ (2.200) involves the Plouffe constant P_A [37], [122]:

$$\frac{4}{\pi} = 8P_A = \frac{1}{1 - \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{5} - \frac{1}{7} + \frac{1}{9} - \frac{1}{11} + \frac{1}{13} - \dots} \approx 1.273239 \quad (2.202)$$

Multiplying $\pi/4$ (2.200) by $\sqrt{2}$, we obtain the series (A.3), which Newton communicated to Oldenberg in 1676 [41, p. 346], whose signs alternate every two terms [8, A218387]:

$$\frac{\pi}{\sqrt{8}} = 1 + \frac{1}{3} - \frac{1}{5} - \frac{1}{7} + \frac{1}{9} + \frac{1}{11} - \frac{1}{13} - \dots \approx 1.11072 \quad (2.203)$$

Let us denote as:

$$\text{sinc}\left(\frac{\pi}{4}\right) = \sqrt{32} P_A = \frac{\sqrt{8}}{\pi} \approx 0.900316 \quad (2.204)$$

the special value [8, A112628] of the Woodward's sinus cardinal function $\text{sinc}(z)|_{\forall z \in \mathbb{C} \setminus \{0\}: \text{sinc}(z) = z^{-1} \sin(z); \text{sinc}(0) = 1}$. It is relevant to this research the fact that, around 2000,

Kogan proved the *sinus cardinal* function relationship to the Eulerian numbers [54, pp. 210–6]–[56] elements of the Eulerian distributions in section 2.10. The combinatorial class of Eulerian numbers is defined over the projective space $\mathbb{C}P^1$ of complex lines through the origin in \mathbb{C}^2 , isomorphic to the 2-dimensional Riemann sphere [69, pp. 117–52]. **Figure 1** denotes as S^- , S and S^+ three of those spheres.

Theorem 2.39. *Those closed-form expressions hold:*

$$\int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty \text{sign}(\vec{x})\text{sign}(\vec{y}) \frac{\sin(\langle \vec{x}, \vec{y} \rangle)}{\sqrt{e^{\|\vec{x}\|_2^2 + \|\vec{y}\|_2^2}}} d\vec{x}d\vec{y} \leq \frac{a_0}{\text{sinc}\left(\frac{\pi}{4}\right)} \tag{2.205}$$

$$\inf_{j \in \mathbb{Z}} \left(\rho_j(u) - \rho(u) \right) \text{sinc}\left(\frac{\pi}{4}\right) = 1 \tag{2.206}$$

Proof. (2.203) is equal to the infimum of the distance $\rho_j(u) - \rho(u)$, $j \in \mathbb{Z}$, of all other poles from the singularity $\rho(u)$ of the bivariate generating function $F(z, u)$ and to the quotient $c_{\mathbb{C}}/c_{\mathbb{R}}$ among Banach space theory’s projection constants of 1-symmetric spaces l_p^n -spaces, $p \in [1, 2]_{\mathbb{R}}$. The ratio a_0 to $\text{sinc}\left(\frac{\pi}{4}\right)$ is equal to the double integral I_1 , **Theorem 1.2** (1.4):

$$\frac{a_0}{\text{sinc}\left(\frac{\pi}{4}\right)} = \frac{8}{\pi} \log(1 + \sqrt{2}) \frac{\pi}{\sqrt{8}} = \sqrt{8} \log(1 + \sqrt{2}) \geq I_1 \tag{2.207}$$

(2.207) is equal to (2.205). Based on **Corollary 2.36**, multiplication of the infimum of the distance $\rho_j(u) - \rho(u)$, $j \in \mathbb{Z}$ of all other poles from the singularity $\rho(u)$ of the bivariate generating function $F(z, u)$ by (2.204), yields:

$$\inf_{j \in \mathbb{Z}} \left(\rho_j(u) - \rho(u) \right) \text{sinc}\left(\frac{\pi}{4}\right) = \frac{\pi}{\sqrt{8}} \frac{\sqrt{8}}{\pi} = 1 \tag{2.208}$$

(2.208) is equal to (2.206). The claim follows. ■

2.19 Malmsten’s integral and hyperbolic secant.

2.19.1 Introduction.

In 2014, Blagouchine discovered the presence of the so-called *Vardi integral* in the 1842’s Malmsten’s dissertation at Uppsala University. Blagouchine [75]–[78] studied integral forms of

- a discrete real parameter, represented by finite Fourier series;
- a continuous complex parameter, whose link to generalized Stieltjes constants he demonstrated.

Among his research outcomes the demonstration that the Malmsten's integral special value $T_{\pi/2}(1)$ [74, p. 33 (16)] reads:

$$T_{\pi/2}(1) = \int_0^{\infty} \frac{\log(1+u^2)}{\cosh\left(\frac{\pi u}{2}\right)} du = 4 \log\left(\frac{2\Gamma(1)}{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)}\right) = 2 \log\left(\frac{4}{\pi}\right) \approx 0.48312 \quad (2.209)$$

In 2022, Abdulsalam [79] presented generalizations and evaluations of hyperbolic and logarithmic integrals. Developing Blagouchine's findings, Abdulsalam [80, p. 14 Proposition 3.8], [80, p. 5 Definition 1] has proved identity of (2.210) and of the hyperbolic functions' one-dimensional integral representations:

$$\delta_0 := \int_0^{\infty} \frac{1 - \operatorname{sech} x}{x^2} dx = \lambda_1 := \int_0^{\infty} \frac{\tanh x \operatorname{sech} x}{x} dx = \frac{4}{\pi} G \approx 1.16624 \quad (2.210)$$

where $4/\pi$ is [25, A088538] and G denotes the Catalan constant [25, A006752], [32, pp. 53–9].

Observation 2.40. (2.213) is the quadruple of the evaluation of the constant denoted $h_2 : 4h_2 = \lambda_1 = \delta_0$ which enters in the definition of the number of dimer coverings of a $2n \times 2n$ square, $n \in \mathbb{N}$ or domino tilings [8, A218387], [32, pp. 406–7], [34, pp. 59–60], [120, pp. 8361–2].

2.19.2 Identities.

Section 2.19.2 establishes closed-form expressions of Blagouchine's [75, p. 33 (16)] identity (2.212), Abdulsalam's [78, p. 14 Proposition 3.8], [79, p. 5 Definition 1] result (2.213), and certain constants playing a prominent role in this research.

Theorem 2.41. *Let $T_{\pi/2}(1)$ denote a the special evaluation of the Malmsten's integral [75, p. 33 (16)]. Then, those logarithmic closed-form expressions hold:*

$$T_{\pi/2}(1) = \log\left(\left(\frac{g_0}{\log \sqrt[4]{\lambda}}\right)^2\right) \quad (2.211)$$

$$T_{\pi/2}(1) = \log\left(2 \inf_{j \in \mathbb{Z}} (\rho_j(u) - \rho(u))^{-2}\right) \quad (2.212)$$

$$T_{\pi/2}(1) = \log\left(2 \left(\frac{c_{\mathbb{R}}}{c_{\mathbb{C}}}\right)^2\right) \quad (2.213)$$

$$T_{\pi/2}(1) = \log\left(64 / \prod_p p\right) \quad (2.214)$$

$$T_{\pi/2}(1) = \log((8 \mathcal{P}_A)^2) \tag{2.215}$$

$$T_{\pi/2}(1) = \log\left(\frac{1}{L_4(1)^2}\right) = \log\left(\frac{2}{L_{-8}(1)^2}\right) \tag{2.216}$$

$$T_{\pi/2}(1) = 2 \log\left(\frac{1}{G} \int_0^\infty \frac{1 - \operatorname{sech} x}{x^2} dx\right) \tag{2.217}$$

For the integral representations [78, p. 14 Proposition 3.8], [79, p. 5 Definition 1] in the hyperbolic secant of $x \in [0, \infty)_{\mathbb{R}}$ those closed-form expressions hold:

$$\int_0^\infty \frac{1 - \operatorname{sech} x}{x^2} dx = \int_0^\infty \frac{\tanh x \operatorname{sech} x}{x} dx = 4 \frac{L_{-4}(2)}{\pi} = 4 \frac{\beta(2)}{\pi} = 4 \frac{G}{\pi} = \frac{4}{\pi} \Phi\left(-1, 2, \frac{1}{2}\right) \tag{2.218}$$

Proof. If we wish, we may write Blagouchine’s [75, p. 33 (16)] expression $T_{\pi/2}(1)$ (2.209), as:

$$\begin{aligned} T_{\pi/2}(1) &= 2 \log\left(\frac{4}{\pi} \log(1 + \sqrt{2}) (\log(1 + \sqrt{2}))^{-1}\right) = \log\left(\left(\frac{g_0}{\log(1 + \sqrt{2})}\right)^2\right) \\ &= \log\left(\left(\frac{g_0}{\log^4 \sqrt{17 + 12\sqrt{2}}}\right)^2\right) = \log\left(\left(\frac{g_0}{\log^4 \sqrt{\lambda}}\right)^2\right) \end{aligned} \tag{2.219}$$

(2.219) is equal to (2.211). $T_{\pi/2}(1)$ (2.209) and the infimum of the distance of all other poles from the singularity $\rho(u)$ of the polar plot of the Eulerian distribution (2.93) [8, A093954] [49, p. 697 Example IX.35] have a closed-form expression:

$$T_{\pi/2}(1) = 2 \log\left(\frac{4}{\pi}\right) = \log\left(\left(\frac{4}{\pi}\right)^2\right) = \log\left(2 \left(\frac{\sqrt{8}}{\pi}\right)^2\right) = \log\left(2 \inf_{j \in \mathbb{Z}} (\rho_j(u) - \rho(u))^{-2}\right) \tag{2.220}$$

(2.220) is equal to (2.212). König’s, Schütt’s and Tomczak-Jaegermann’s [17, p. 2 Theorem 1] projection constants $c_{\mathbb{R}}$ and $c_{\mathbb{C}}$ of 1-symmetric l_p^n -spaces have closed-form expression:

$$T_{\pi/2}(1) = 2 \log\left(\frac{4}{\pi}\right) = \log\left(2 \left(\sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi} \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}}}\right)^2\right) = \log\left(2 \left(\frac{c_{\mathbb{R}}}{c_{\mathbb{C}}}\right)^2\right) \tag{2.221}$$

(2.221) is equal to (2.213). (2.209) and the super-regularised product over all primes denoted $\prod_p p$ (see [44, p. 78 Theorem 8], [45, p. 3] and section A.2) have closed-form expression

$$T_{\pi/2}(1) = 2 \log\left(\frac{4}{\pi}\right) = \log\left(\frac{16}{\pi^2}\right) = \log\left(16/4 \prod_p\right) = \log\left(64/\prod_p\right) \quad (2.222)$$

(2.222) is equal to (2.214). (2.209) and P_A (see section A.3) closed-form expression reads

$$T_{\pi/2}(1) = \log\left(\left(\frac{8}{2\pi}\right)^2\right) = \log((8P_A)^2) \quad (2.223)$$

(2.223) is equal to (2.215). (2.209) and the Dirichlet L -series $L_4(1)$ [99, p. 14 Table 22] and $L_{-8}(1)$ (see section A.1) have closed-form expressions

$$T_{\pi/2}(1) = \log\left(\left(\frac{4}{\pi}\right)^2\right) = \log\left(\frac{1}{L_4(1)^2}\right) = \log\left(\frac{2}{L_{-8}(1)^2}\right) \quad (2.224)$$

(2.224) is equal to (2.216). The solution of (2.213)

$$\frac{4}{\pi} = \frac{1}{G} \int_0^{\infty} \frac{1 - \operatorname{sech} x}{x^2} dx \quad (2.225)$$

replaced in (2.209) yields

$$T_{\pi/2}(1) = \log\left(\left(\frac{1}{G} \int_0^{\infty} \frac{1 - \operatorname{sech} x}{x^2} dx\right)^2\right) \quad (2.226)$$

(2.226) is equal to (2.217). The Dirichlet L -series $L_{-4}(2) := \mathbf{G}$ for the alternating character of period four coincides with the special evaluation $\beta(2)$ of the Dirichlet beta-function

$$\beta(2) := \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{(2n+1)^x} \Big|_{x=2} = L_{-4}(2) \quad (2.227)$$

and with the special evaluation of the Lerch transcendent [63, pp. 1049–51]

$$L_{-4}(2) := \frac{\Phi(z, s, \nu)}{2^s} \Big|_{z=-1; s=2; \nu=1/2} = \Phi\left(-1, 2, \frac{1}{2}\right) \quad (2.228)$$

Aggregating the identities (2.227) and (2.228) yields

$$\int_0^\infty \frac{1 - \operatorname{sech} x}{x^2} dx = \int_0^\infty \frac{\tanh x \operatorname{sech} x}{x} dx = 4 \frac{L_{-4}(2)}{\pi} = 4 \frac{\beta(2)}{\pi} = 4 \frac{\mathbf{G}}{\pi} = \frac{4}{\pi} \Phi\left(-1, 2, \frac{1}{2}\right) \quad (2.229)$$

(2.229) is equal to (2.218). The claim follows. ■

2.20 Differential operator ϑ , Catalan numbers, and the Dirichlet L -series $L_5(1, \chi_3)$.

It follows a technical lemma, fully meaningful in the sequel to this paper, which indicates the elementary geometry linking this paper’s constants. To inspect **Theorem 1.5**, Braverman et al. [4, p. 33 Remark 5.6] assumed that $f, g : \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow [-1, 1]_{\mathbb{R}}$ are measurable functions, and considered the function $H : \mathbb{S} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ given by (1.10):

$$H(z) = \frac{1}{2\pi(1 - z^2)} \int_{\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2} \frac{f(\vec{x})g(\vec{y})}{\sqrt{e^{1-z^2} \sqrt{\|\vec{x}\|_2^2 + \|\vec{y}\|_2^2 - 2z\langle \vec{x}, \vec{y} \rangle}}} d\vec{x}d\vec{y} \quad (2.230)$$

Section 3.4 of Heilman’s inspection [30] of the proof of Braverman et al.’s [4, p. Theorem 1.1], studies the Lipschitz constant on $i + 2^{-1}\mathbb{D}$. For $H_0(z) = \arcsin z$ he determines the Lipschitz constant L_0 evaluation as [30, p. 4]:

$$L_0 = \sup_{|z-i|\leq 1/2} |H'_0(z)| = \sup_{|z-i|\leq 1/2} \frac{1}{|\sqrt{1 - z^2}|} = \frac{2}{\sqrt{5}} \approx 0.894427 \quad (2.231)$$

(2.131) is one tenth of [8, A010532]. Let us denote as c_1 the constant [8, A020789]:

$$c_1 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{32}} \approx 0.17677669 \quad (2.232)$$

Let us denote as ϑ the differentiation operator [64]:

$$\vartheta = x \frac{d}{dx} \quad (2.233)$$

Considering ϑ ’s applications in the special functions of mathematical physics and in the Sturm-Liouville theory, is of great importance. In 1985, Lehmer [59, p. 451 (8)] linked the operator ϑ to the power series expansion (A.17) in type B Catalan numbers or central binomial coefficients [8, A000984], [33, pp. 182–9], [34, p. 78], [38, p. 274], [39, pp. 13–88], [51], [55]–[56], [103]–[105] He found that two iterations based on the special value $x = 8^{-1}$, let (A.17) generate the infinite series which converges to:

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^2 \binom{2n}{n} x^2 = \frac{\vartheta^2}{\sqrt{1-4x}} \Big|_{x=\frac{1}{8}} = \frac{2x(2x+1)}{\sqrt{(1-4x)^5}} \Big|_{x=\frac{1}{8}} = \frac{5}{4} \sqrt{2} \approx 1.7677669 \tag{2.234}$$

whose minimal irreducible univariate monic real polynomial is $8x^2 - 25$. In 2009, Mathar noted that (2.232) is one-tenth of (2.234). Its initial thirteen summands' explicit evaluations are

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^2 \binom{2n}{n} x^2 &= \frac{1}{4} + \frac{3}{8} + \frac{45}{128} + \frac{35}{128} + \frac{1575}{8192} + \frac{2079}{16384} + \frac{21021}{262144} + \frac{6435}{131072} \\ &+ \frac{984555}{33554432} + \frac{10669659}{1073741824} + \frac{6084351}{1073741824} + \frac{219712675}{68719476736} + \dots + \frac{n^2}{8^n} \binom{2n}{n} + \dots \end{aligned} \tag{2.235}$$

A central binomial coefficient factors out the n^{th} term of the series. Denominators are a subset of $\{2^n\}_{n=0; 2^0=1}^{\infty}$ [8, A000079]. As of 2026, the 11th and 13th numerators are unknown to [8]. All other numerators, either directly or indirectly, have a relationship to classical or type A Catalan numbers denoted $C_n := c(n)$ [8, A000108], [39]. Until Mathar's [60] correction, several typos plagued [59]. Four out of eleven corrections are relevant to the pair $(\varphi, -\bar{\varphi})$ of Pisot-Vijayaraghavan algebraic conjugate numbers, where $\varphi = (1 + \sqrt{5})/2$ denotes the quadratic irrational [38] endowed with the morphic property, known as the *golden ratio* [8, A0001622], [32, pp. 5–11], [34, pp. 1–2 7–8 77]. Seven out of eleven corrections involve series with central binomial coefficients. Furthermore, Mathar noted that $c_1 = 1/\sqrt{32}$ is one-tenth of that which (A.17), **Example A.7**, Section A.4 generates after two iterations based on the special value $x = 8^{-1}$ as

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^2 \binom{2n}{n} x^2 = \frac{\vartheta^2}{\sqrt{1-4x}} \Big|_{x=\frac{1}{8}} = \frac{2x(2x+1)}{\sqrt{(1-4x)^5}} \Big|_{x=\frac{1}{8}} = 10c_1 \tag{2.236}$$

The constant factor c_1 , the ratio $c_{\mathbb{C}}/c_{\mathbb{R}}$ (see Theorem 2.40, section 2.18) links the cycloid curves over $\mathbb{R}^2 \cong \mathbb{C}$ via Plouffe constant P_A [37], [122]. It follows a lemma showing that, up to a constant factor $1/\sqrt{2}$ [8, A010503], an elementary function of the Dirichlet L -series $L_5(1, \chi_3)$ is equal to the power series expansion of the type B Catalan numbers $10 c_1 = 5/\sqrt{8} \approx 1.7677669$ (2.234).

Lemma 2.42.

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{20^n} \binom{2n}{n} = \frac{L_5(1, \chi_3)}{\log \varphi} = \frac{1}{L_0} = \frac{\sqrt{5}}{2} \tag{2.237}$$

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^2 \binom{2n}{n} x^2 = \frac{\vartheta^2}{\sqrt{1-4x}} \Big|_{x=\frac{1}{8}} = \frac{2x(2x+1)}{\sqrt{(1-4x)^5}} \Big|_{x=\frac{1}{8}} = \frac{1}{L_0} \sqrt{\frac{5}{2}} = \frac{\sqrt{5}}{2} \sqrt{\frac{5}{2}} \tag{2.238}$$

Proof. The Lipschitz constant L_0^{-1} on $i + 2^{-1}\mathbb{D}$ (2.231) factors out Lehmer’s identity (2.234). Replacement of (2.231) yields (2.338). (2.237) indicates that the leftmost factor of (2.238) is an elementary function of the irrational Pisot-Vijayaraghavan number [8, A0001622] and of the Dirichlet L -series $L_5(1, \chi_3)$, which is equal to an Apéry-type series. The claim follows. ■

2.21 $z := i/\sqrt{2}$ instantiates the Riemann zeta-function $\zeta(3)$.

Section 2.8.3 noted that the same $\lambda = 17 + 12\sqrt{2}$ which (i) Apéry needed to use to demonstrate that the Riemann zeta-function $\zeta(3)$ is an irrational, and (ii) Braverman et al. [4] used in Remark 1.6 to inspect their Theorem 1.5. Theorem 1.5 which, very recently, Heilman [30] confirmed to be correct. The constant term g_0 of the Pain-Fourier series expansion of a triangular function can be written as $g_0 = \pi^{-1} \log \lambda$. From a number theoretic perspective $\lambda = (1 + \sqrt{2})^4$ [45], [83, pp. 9–16], [85]. The 4th power of $1 + \sqrt{2}$ coincides with the dimension of the space \mathbb{R}^4 all combinatorial classes in section 2 share, and with the dimensions of the Minkowski space of embedded quantum information systems whose measurements indicate violation of Bell’s inequalities. Section 2.10.3 found that several other strands of mathematical physics mirror Flajolet’s and Sedgewick’s [49, pp. 236–7] indication of the special value $i/\sqrt{2}$ (2.95) of the complex variable $z \in \mathbb{C}$ among those playing a prominent role in the reduction from global (integral) to local (residue) properties of all analytic functions. Let $\zeta(3)$ denote the Dirichlet L -series $L_1(3, \chi_0) \approx 1.20205$ called Riemann zeta-function for $n = 3$, or *Apéry constant* [8, A002117], [32, pp. 40–53], [33, p. 99], [41], [42, p. 13], [43], [87, pp. 784–6], [91, pp. 95–144], [124, p. 28 Exercise 3.10], [124]. Let us consider the special case of polygamma function called digamma function $\psi^{(v)}(z)|_{v,z \in \mathbb{C}}$ [62], [63], [106], [116].

Figure 9. Second derivative of the digamma function $\psi^{(2)}(z)|_{z \in [-6,4]_{\mathbb{R}}}$. The special evaluation $z = 1$ which corresponds to $i/\sqrt{2}$ lies at the onset of the region of stability.

Let $\psi^{(2)}(1) = -2 \zeta(3) \approx -2.40411$ the special value of the second derivative at $s = 1$. **Figure 9** plots $\psi^{(2)}(z)|_{z \in [-6,4]_{\mathbb{R}}}$. Let us consider complex symmetric normal distributions, and denote as $\mu(k) \approx 0.86575 \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ the probability measure constant, ground of Haagerup's [9, p. 217 Theorem 2.1] evaluation of the upper bound of Grothendieck's inequality $K_G^{\mathbb{C}} \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ in the ∞ -dimensional Hilbert space \mathcal{H} over the commutative number field \mathbb{C} [8, A088374]. Let $\mu(\tau) \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ denote the Friedland's, Lai's, and Lim's [23, p. 19 Lemma 2.25] analog in the ∞ -dimensional Hilbert space \mathcal{H} over the noncommutative quaternion number field \mathbb{H} of Haagerup's $\mu(k)$. Lai [24] has acknowledged our request and coded software based on series expansions extended to one hundred terms, evaluating the probability measure constant $\mu(\tau)$ as:

$$\mu(\tau) \approx 1.20203976149065128 \tag{2.239}$$

Let us consider a complete graph on n vertices in which the lengths of the edges, of finite variance and mean, are nonnegative, independent and identically distributed random variables, whose common distribution function, denoted F , is differentiable $D = F'(0) \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$. Let us denote as X a random variable associated with F , of finite variance $\sigma_n^2(X) \in]\infty, \infty[_{\mathbb{R}}$. Let us denote as L_n a random variable whose value is the length of the minimum spanning tree of the graph [25, p.47], whose mean is finite $\langle L_n \rangle \in]\infty, \infty[_{\mathbb{R}}$. Based on Kruskal's (1956), Erdős' and Rényi's (1960), Walkup's (1979), Lueker's (1981), Steele's (1981), and Fenner's and Frieze's (1982) foundational works, in 1985 Frieze [25] demonstrated that theorem in lattice theory

Theorem 2.43. (Frieze [25, p. 47 Theorem], [26, p. 99 (1.2)–(1.3)]).

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \langle L_n \rangle = \frac{\zeta(3)}{D} \tag{2.240}$$

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \Pr \left(\left| L_n - \frac{\zeta(3)}{D} \right| > \epsilon \right) = 0 \tag{2.241}$$

In 1987, Steele [26] generalized Frieze's result. In 2017, Baez and others remarked that Frieze's [25, p. 47 Theorem] and Steele's [26, p. 99 (1.2)–(1.3)] theorems indicate a probabilistic meaning of the Apéry constant $\zeta(3)$. Thus, motivating us to compute the difference between the Riemann zeta function $\zeta(3)$ and the probability measure constant $\mu(\tau)$ evaluations. Also, we demonstrate that the complex constant $z := i/\sqrt{2}$ instantiates the Riemann zeta function $\zeta(3)$. The latter is an element of the Standard Model of Particle Physics, endowed with important properties. It participates in characterizing what in the spacetime can be observed. Thus, including the phenomenology behind Grothendieck's constant evaluations which correspond to correlations between quantum systems whose separation is spacelike.

Proposition 2.44. $z := i/\sqrt{2}$ is the complex constant of proportionality between the Riemann zeta function $\zeta(3)$ and the second derivative of the digamma function $\psi^{(2)}(1)$

$$z = \sqrt{\frac{\zeta(3)}{\psi^{(2)}(1)}} = \frac{i}{\sqrt{2}} \quad (2.242)$$

Moreover, up to a difference $\epsilon_1 \approx 0.0000171416689430$, that identity holds:

$$\zeta(3) = \mu(\tau) \quad (2.243)$$

Proof. Representations of $\zeta(3)$ include infinite series, hyperbolic, and digamma functions:

$$\zeta(3) = L_1(3, \chi_0) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^3} = \frac{8}{9} \int_0^{\infty} t^3 \operatorname{sech}^2 t \, dt = -\frac{\psi^{(2)}(1)}{2!} \approx 1.2020569031595942853997 \quad (2.244)$$

Based on Flajolet and Sedgewick [49, pp. 236–7] and Sprugnoli [51, p. 8 Theorem 3.2 (1)], we may write the rightmost identity in (2.244) as:

$$\zeta(3) = -\frac{1}{2} \psi^{(2)}(1) = \left(\frac{i}{\sqrt{2}}\right)^2 \psi^{(2)}(1) = z^2 \psi^{(2)}(1) \Big|_{z:=\frac{i}{\sqrt{2}}} \implies z = \sqrt{\frac{\zeta(3)}{\psi^{(2)}(1)}} = \frac{i}{\sqrt{2}} \quad (2.245)$$

finding that the complex constant $z := i/\sqrt{2}$ is the positive square root of the ratio of the Riemann zeta function $\zeta(3)$ to the digamma function $\psi^{(2)}(1)$. (2.245) is equal to (2.242). The evaluation of the difference between $\zeta(3)$ (2.244) [8, A002117] and $\mu(\tau)$ (2.239) [24], is

$$\epsilon_1 := \zeta(3) - \mu(\tau) \approx 0.0000171416689430 \quad (2.246)$$

The claim follows. ■

2.22 Grothendieck's constant as a function of the Gauß-Heegner numbers (H_1, H_2) .

Section 2.22 introduces *Gauß-Heegner* numbers and shows that the Krivine upper bound of the Grothendieck inequality over the reals may be written as an elementary function of the pair of *Gauß-Heegner* numbers $(H_1, H_2) = (1, 2)$.

2.22.1 Gauß unambiguously-defined factorizations.

Let us denote as $-d$ discriminant evaluations, which let imaginary quadratic fields $\mathbb{Q}[-d]$ be *uniquely* factorable into factors $a + \sqrt{-b} \Big|_{a,b \in \mathbb{Q}}$. Gauß discovered the set [8, A003173]:

$$\{H_n\}_{n=1}^9 = \{H_1, H_2, H_3, H_4, H_5, H_6, H_7, H_8, H_9\} = \{1, 2, 3, 7, 11, 19, 43, 67, 163\} \quad (2.247)$$

Discriminants' evaluations $-d$ corresponding to the pair (H_1, H_2) let imaginary quadratic fields $\mathbb{Q}[-d]$ imply factors $a + \sqrt{-b}|_{a,b \in \mathbb{Z} \subset \mathbb{Q}}$. Conversely, the subset $(H_3, H_4, H_5, H_6, H_7, H_8, H_9)$ implies factors $a + \sqrt{-b}|_{a,b \in \mathbb{Q}}$. Does the set include only nine elements? In 1934, Heilbronn and Linfoot proved that Gauß's original inclusion of nine elements holds up to $|d| > 10^9$ in the imaginary quadratic field of class-number 1. In 1952, Heegner proved that only nine elements exist. Stark demonstrated that there is no tenth complex quadratic field with class number 1. Thus, in 1967, the so-called Gauß class number problem, which Heegner had already solved fifteen years before, was solved. Peculiar properties endow the set $\{H_n\}_{n=1}^9$. Bertolini and Darmon [87, pp. 109–70] illustrated those in the context of p -adic Dirichlet L -series of modular elliptic curves. Cohen [87, pp. 320–3] noted that Heegner points are an element of Kolyagin's "Euler system" linking arithmetic and analytic objects. Faltings [87, pp. 449–54] explained that Heegner points may provide rational points for modular elliptic curves. Kontsevich and Zagier [87, pp. 796–7] indicated the role which the set $\{H_n\}_{n=1}^9$ plays in relationship to periods, Hecke eigenforms of even weight, denoted k , higher-weight Green's functions, denoted $G_{k/2}(z_1, z_2)$, with order $k/2$ of the underlying linear differential operator \mathcal{L}_z . We recall that the latter acts on the fixed point z_1 while z_2 is treated as a parameter, such that:

$$\mathcal{L}_z G_{k/2}(z_1, z_2) = \delta(z_1, z_2) \tag{2.248}$$

where $\delta(z_1, z_2)$ denotes the Dirac delta hyperfunction or distribution, identity of the convolution, met in **Example 2.20**, section 2.10.3.

2.22.2 Grothendieck constant and Gauß-Heegner numbers.

Section 2.22.1 writes the Krivine upper bound of the Grothendieck inequality over the reals as elementary functions of the *Gauß-Heegner* numbers $(H_1, H_2) = (1, 2)$.

Proposition 2.45. *The upper bound of the Grothendieck's inequality over the reals, has symbolic and explicit representations in terms of Gauß-Heegner numbers $(H_1, H_2) = (1, 2)$:*

$$K_G^{\mathbb{R}} \leq \frac{H_1}{\frac{H_1}{H_2} \log \left(H_1 + H_2 \frac{H_1}{H_2} \right) \left(\frac{H_1}{H_2} \left(H_1 + \frac{H_1}{H_2} \frac{H_1}{H_2} \right) \right)^{\frac{H_1}{H_2}} \left(\frac{H_1}{H_2} \left(H_1 + \frac{H_1}{H_2} \frac{H_1}{H_2} \right)^{\frac{H_1}{H_2}} \right)^{\frac{H_1}{H_2}} \dots} \tag{2.249}$$

$$= \frac{1}{\frac{1}{2^{\frac{1}{2}}} \log \left(1 + \frac{1}{2^{\frac{1}{2}}} \right) \left(\frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \frac{1}{2^{\frac{1}{2}}} \right) \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \left(\frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \left(\frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \frac{1}{2^{\frac{1}{2}}} \right) \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \dots} \tag{2.250}$$

Proof. Recall Viète’s classical infinite product representation of π [8, A000796], which expresses the quotient $2/\pi$ [8, A060294] as the limit of a sequence of nested square roots [34, p. 3]:

$$\frac{2}{\pi} = 4 P_A = \frac{1}{\frac{\frac{1}{2^{\frac{1}{2}}}}{\log\left(1 + \frac{1}{2^{\frac{1}{2}}}\right)} \left(\frac{1}{2}\left(1 + \frac{1}{2^{\frac{1}{2}}}\right)\right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \left(\frac{1}{2}\left(1 + \left(\frac{1}{2}\left(1 + \frac{1}{2^{\frac{1}{2}}}\right)\right)^{\frac{1}{2}}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \dots} \tag{2.251}$$

Remark 2.246. (2.251) is (i) the square of the projection constant of 1-symmetric l_p^n -spaces $\forall p \in [1, 2]_{\mathbb{R}}$, over $\mathbb{F} = \mathbb{R}$, $c_{\mathbb{R}} = \sqrt{2/\pi} = 2^{-1} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} [1 - \text{erf}(x)^2] dx$ [8, A076668], [17, p. 2 Theorem 1], and (ii) an elementary function of the projection constant of 1-symmetric spaces l_p^n -spaces, $\forall p \in [1, 2]_{\mathbb{R}}$, over $\mathbb{F} = \mathbb{C}$, $c_{\mathbb{C}} = \sqrt{\pi}/2$ [8, A019704], [17, p. 2 Theorem 1], [32, p. 22].

Observation 2.247. In **Appendix D**, (2.251) and its elementary functions, are the prefactors of Davie’s proof (D.15)–(D.16) and of Reeds’ theorem [19, p. 10 Theorem 3] establishing Grothendieck’s inequality lower bound over the reals.

Then, the Krivine upper bound of Grothendieck’s inequality over the reals may be written as:

$$K_G^{\mathbb{R}} \leq \frac{1}{2 \log(1 + \sqrt{2})} \frac{2}{\frac{\frac{1}{2^{\frac{1}{2}}}}{\log\left(1 + \frac{1}{2^{\frac{1}{2}}}\right)} \left(\frac{1}{2}\left(1 + \frac{1}{2^{\frac{1}{2}}}\right)\right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \left(\frac{1}{2}\left(1 + \left(\frac{1}{2}\left(1 + \frac{1}{2^{\frac{1}{2}}}\right)\right)^{\frac{1}{2}}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \dots} \tag{2.252}$$

$$= \frac{1}{\frac{\frac{1}{2^{\frac{1}{2}}}}{\log\left(1 + \frac{1}{2^{\frac{1}{2}}}\right)} \left(\frac{1}{2}\left(1 + \frac{1}{2^{\frac{1}{2}}}\right)\right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \left(\frac{1}{2}\left(1 + \left(\frac{1}{2}\left(1 + \frac{1}{2^{\frac{1}{2}}}\right)\right)^{\frac{1}{2}}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \dots} \tag{2.253}$$

$$= \frac{H_1}{\frac{\frac{H_1}{H_2}}{\log\left(H_1 + H_2 \frac{H_1}{H_2}\right)} \left(\frac{H_1}{H_2}\left(H_1 + \frac{H_1}{H_2 \frac{H_1}{H_2}}\right)\right)^{\frac{H_1}{H_2}} \left(\frac{H_1}{H_2}\left(H_1 + \frac{H_1}{H_2} \frac{H_1}{H_2 \frac{H_1}{H_2}}\right)^{\frac{H_1}{H_2}}\right)^{\frac{H_1}{H_2}} \dots} \tag{2.254}$$

(2.254) is equal to (2.249). (2.253) is equal to (2.250). The claim follows. ■

3 Conclusions, open problems, and future research directions.

We have examined constants in **Conjecture 1.1**, **Theorem 1.2**, **Corollary 1.3**, **Lemma 1.4**, **Theorem 1.5**, and **Remark 1.6** on the number-theoretic ground only. Section 2 has demonstrated that:

1. The Krivine upper bound of the Grothendieck inequality $K_G^{\mathbb{R}}$ has exact closed-form expressions involving tens of constants from analytic combinatorics and analytic number theory. The latter are combinatorial classes corresponding to surfaces over the space $\mathbb{R}^4 \cong \mathbb{C}\mathbb{P}^1$. Coincidentally, very recently, Heilman [30] has demonstrated that the difference $K_G^{\mathbb{R}} - K_G$ is infinitesimal, $|K_G - K_G^{\mathbb{R}}| \leq 8.23 \times 10^{-457}$.
2. The Krivine upper bound is equal to the ratio $L_{-8}(1)/L_8(1)$ of quadratic symmetric Dirichlet L -series, and the ratio of Gauß hypergeometric functions of symmetric arguments.
3. The supremum of the König bilinear form is identical to the Dirichlet L -series $L_8(1)$. Its quadruple is the König's two-dimensional integral of evaluation $\sqrt{8} \log(1 + \sqrt{2})$.
4. The Krivine upper bound of the Grothendieck inequality $K_G^{\mathbb{R}}$, as well as the supremum of the König bilinear form, admits a representation in terms of Apéry-type series with reciprocals of central binomial coefficients, or type B Catalan Numbers, identified in 2007.
5. Those forms and the super regularized infinite product of primes, discovered in 2008, with the generalised Stieltjes constant γ_1 at arbitrary rational arguments, and with the Euler-Kronecker constant γ_8 of the global field $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{8})$ established in 2006, have closed-form expressions.
6. Triangular functions based on the König two-dimensional integrals and upper bound of the Grothendieck inequality, Eulerian distribution local, limit law of the Gaussian type, König two-dimensional integrals, and upper bound of the Grothendieck inequality, admit closed-form expressions.
7. The special case of the Fourier infinite series expansion of the even parity triangular function $\mathcal{F}(x) = \sec(x/4)$, $x \in [-\pi, \pi]_{\mathbb{R}}$ that Pain recently studied has relationships with König two-dimensional integrals and Grothendieck inequality's Krivine upper bound.
8. The Dirichlet L -series $L_{-8}(1)$ also plays a special role in analytic combinatorics, where it represents the infimum of the distance of the other poles to the singularity of the polar representation of an Eulerian discrete distribution. Hence, $L_{-8}(1)$ enters the global-to-local reduction of the analytic functions' properties, reminiscent of the process behind Grothendieck constants $K_G > 1$.
9. The plane closed oval quartic parametric polar curve, called limaçon of Pascal (of which cardioid and circle are degenerate limit cases), completely described over $\mathbb{R}^4 \cong \mathbb{C}\mathbb{P}^1$ is identical to the polar representation of an Eulerian discrete distribution for $n \rightarrow \infty$. The latter is a combinatorial class over $\mathbb{R}^4 \cong \mathbb{C}\mathbb{P}^1$. This finding which has implications in complex systems theory [119].
10. The complex constant $z := i/\sqrt{2}$ instantiates the Dirichlet L -series $L_1(3, \chi_0)$, known as Riemann zeta function $\zeta(3)$ or Apéry's constant. The latter is an element of the Standard Model of Particle Physics [126], endowed with particularly important properties. It participates in

characterizing what in the space \mathbb{R}^4 can be observed [127]. Thus, including the nonlocal correlations phenomenology behind Grothendieck constant evaluations $K_G > 1$.

11. The Plouffe constant A relevant to cycloid curves [37], [122], themselves based on the degenerate limaçon of Pascal called the circle, factors out all closed-form expressions and, in certain cases, have their simplest expression.
12. Braverman et al. inspection of their [4, p. 4 Theorem 1.1], relevant to the Krivine upper bound of Grothendieck's inequality in the Hilbert space $\mathcal{H}^{\mathbb{R}}$, holds based on the same Pisot number λ which, on 20 June 1978 at Marseille, Apéry demonstrated to imply irrationality of the Riemann zeta-function $\zeta(3)$.

Conjecture 1.1, Theorem 1.2, Corollary 1.3, Lemma 1.4, Theorem 1.5 and Remark 1.6 hold if certain assumptions about “perfect circles” of Euclidean geometry are true. Cayley, Dixon, Grammel, Burgoyne, and Heun first felt this concern. After their seminal works, the study of the parameterization of p -Fermat curves, called generalized trigonometry [67], was born to “cure imperfect circles”. In other words, the curves are incoherent with the circle, which Archimedes' constant $\pi \in \mathbb{C} \setminus \mathbb{A} \subset \mathcal{P} \subset \mathbb{C}$ presumes. Any of the generalised trigonometry's findings is that π is the infimum of the evaluation of a function that we define. Acting on that function regularises what an improper evaluation of π makes irregular. The present author is not aware of any research focusing on Grothendieck inequalities in the modern ground of generalised trigonometry [67]. The generalised trigonometry approach mirrors that which began to be applied to the Euler-Mascheroni constant $\gamma \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \mathbb{A}$ [8, A001620], [32, pp. 28–39], [34, pp. 4–6], [35]. Aside from that γ , there are an infinite number of class field-dependent constants, denoted $\gamma_K \neq \gamma$ (see section D.1 **Appendix D**). Using γ_K allows for extremely accurate evaluation of other constants, such as the Euler-Kronecker constants and the generalised Stieltjes constants, crucial in applied mathematics.

What is the geometric perspective section 2's findings indicate?

In the graph-theoretic framework, the relationships between these five enunciates have been extensively researched. Do Grothendieck constants have relationships with other fundamental constants of mathematical physics?

Acknowledgements. I am grateful to Alexander Munro Davie, University of Edinburgh, Scotland, for authoring the proof of his 1984 theorem, which defines the lower bound of the Grothendieck inequality in the ∞ -dimensional Hilbert space $\mathcal{H}^{\mathbb{R}}$, and for permitting to include it in this publication as **Appendix D**. Many thanks to Steven Michael Heilman, University of Southern California–Los Angeles, for authoring and communicating the proof of the new upper bound of the Grothendieck inequality in the ∞ -dimensional Hilbert space $\mathcal{H}^{\mathbb{R}}$. I am grateful to Alessandro Languasco, Università di Padova–Padova, and Pieter Moree, Max-Planck-Gesellschaft zur Förderung der Wissenschaften–Bonn, for computing the Euler-Kronecker constant γ_8 of the global field $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{8})$ and permitting to include it as evaluation (C.6) **Appendix C**. The author wants to thank the following scholars for proofreading sections of the draft relevant to their own findings: Herrmann König, Christian-Albrechts-Universität zu Kiel–Kiel; Jean-Christophe Pain, Université de Paris–Saclay, and Laboratoire Matière en Conditions Extrêmes–Bruyères-le-Châtel; Robert Sedgewick, Princeton University–Princeton NJ; Mark Dalthorp, Cornell University–Ithaca NY, and Simon Plouffe, Université du Québec à Montréal–Montréal. Many thanks for providing helpful

comments and inspiring discussions during the investigation to: Wolf-Dieter Lang, Institut für Theoretische Physik, Universität Karlsruhe–Karlsruhe; Stefan Müller-Stach, Johannes Gutenberg-Universität–Mainz; Frank Vallentin, Universität zu Köln–Köln; Richard Mathar, Max-Planck-Institut für Astronomie–Heidelberg; Jop Briët, Centrum Wiskunde & Informatica–Amsterdam; Iaroslav Veniaminovich Blagouchine, Steklov Mathematical Institute of the Russian Academy of Sciences–Sankt Petersburg and Université de Toulon–Toulon; Christian Beck, Queen Mary University of London; Christopher White, Queen Mary University of London; Peter Jossen, King’s College–London; and Davide Ritelli, Università di Bologna–Bologna.

Funding. This research began with the project 7ME525 (ID 101793691) at The University of Derby, England, and has not received external funding.

Figures.

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Data Availability. The data supporting the findings of this study are available within the paper.

CRedit authorship contribution statement.

Roberto Alfano: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration.

The author certifies that he has: (1) no conflicts of interest to declare that are relevant to the content of this paper; (2) no relevant financial or non-financial interests to disclose; (3) no involvement or affiliation in any entity or organization with any financial or non-financial interest in the subject matter discussed in this manuscript, and (4) no financial or proprietary interests in any material discussed in this paper.

Appendix A.

A.1 Certain quadratic Dirichlet L -series.

Section A.1 outlines the notation, evaluation, references and representations of certain real or quadratic Dirichlet L -series [33, pp. 97–112], [41], [91, pp. 95–144], [99]. We give a special focus to the pair $\{L_8(1); L_{-8}(1)\}$ with symmetric fundamental discriminants. Let us denote as $L_8(1) \in \mathbb{C} \setminus \mathbb{A} \subset \mathcal{P} \subset \mathbb{C}$ the special case of quadratic Dirichlet L -series of *fundamental discriminant* $D = 2$ [33, pp. 78–80] and *fundamental unit* E of norm 1 [41, p. 349]:

$$\frac{\log E}{2\sqrt{D}} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \binom{D}{n} \frac{1}{n} \Big|_{D=2; h=1} = 1 - \frac{1}{3} - \frac{1}{5} + \frac{1}{7} + \frac{1}{9} - \frac{1}{11} - \frac{1}{13} + \dots = \frac{\log(1 + \sqrt{2})}{\sqrt{2}} \approx 0.623225 \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where $\binom{D}{n}$ denotes the completely multiplicative function over $\mathbb{Z}_{>0}$ called Kronecker-Jacobi-Legendre symbol. Below, further logarithmic, hyperbolic and integral representations [8, A196525], [33, p. 98], [101, pp. 64–8], equal to (1.3) and (1.5):

$$L_8(1) = \log\left((1 + \sqrt{2})^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}}\right) = \log\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{2} + 1}\right) = \frac{\operatorname{arcsinh}(1)}{\sqrt{2}} = \int_0^{\pi/2} \frac{\sin^2(x)}{\sin(x) + \cos(x)} dx \quad (\text{A.2})$$

Let us denote as $L_{-8}(1) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} L_8(1, \chi_4)$ the Dirichlet L -series of fundamental discriminant $D = -2$, fundamental unit E of norm 1 [8, A093954], [41, p. 346], or the Dirichlet L -series of modulus $m = 8$ at $s = 1$ for the non-principal character $(1,0,1,0, -1,0, -1,0)$ such that:

$$\frac{\pi}{2\sqrt{|D|}} := \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \binom{D}{n} \frac{1}{n} \Big|_{D=-2; h=1} = 1 + \frac{1}{3} - \frac{1}{5} - \frac{1}{7} + \frac{1}{9} + \frac{1}{11} - \frac{1}{13} - \dots = \frac{\pi}{\sqrt{8}} \approx 1.11072 \quad (\text{A.3})$$

Below, eight further alternating series without and with type B Catalan numbers, Plouffe constant P_A [37], [122], Riemann zeta function $\zeta(2)$ and quadratic Dirichlet L -series representations [99, p. 14 Table 22]:

$$\begin{aligned} L_{-8}(1) &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{2^n}{1 + 2n} \binom{2n}{n}^{-1} \left(1 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{2^{2n}} \binom{2n}{n} \right) = \pi / \left[3 \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{4n + 1} - \frac{1}{4n - 3} \right) \binom{2^{-1}}{n} \right] \\ &= \pi / \left[3 \left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} 2^n \binom{2n}{n} - 1 \right) \right] = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{8} P_A} = \frac{\sqrt[2]{3\zeta(2)}}{2} = \sqrt[2]{L_2(2)} = \sqrt[2]{2} L_4(1) = \sqrt[4]{2} \sqrt{L_8(2)} \quad (\text{A.4}) \end{aligned}$$

where (i) $\sqrt{8}$ is the surface area of the regular 8-gon with unit circumradius [8 A010466], [32, pp. 519–23] and Diophantine approximation theory’s second number of Lagrange denoted L_2 ; (ii)

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{4n+1} - \frac{1}{4n-3} \right) \binom{2^{-1}}{n} = \frac{\sqrt{8}}{3} \tag{A.5}$$

(iii) one of the series is a product of Apéry-type series with reciprocals of type B Catalan numbers or central binomial coefficients in section A.4, [8, A000984], [33, pp. 182–9], [34, p. 78], [38, p. 274], [39, pp. 13–88], [51], [55]–[56], [103]–[105]; (iv) P_A denotes the Plouffe constant A .

Let us denote as:

$L_{-8}(2) \approx 1.06473$ the Dirichlet L -series modulo -8 [8, A309710], [33, p. 98].

$L_2(2) := L_2(2, \chi_1) = 3 \times 4^{-1} \zeta(2) = 8^{-1} \pi^2$ the Dirichlet L -series of the non-principal character modulo 2 [8, A111003], [99, p. 14 Table 22].

$L_4(2) := L_4(2, \chi_2) = \int_0^1 x^{-1} \arctan x \, dx \approx 0.91596$ the Dirichlet L -series called *Catalan constant* denoted $\mathbf{G} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} C$ [8, A006752], [32, pp. 53–8], [33, p. 591], [99, p. 14 Table 22].

$L_5(1, \chi_3) := 2 \log((1 + \sqrt{5})/2)/\sqrt{5} = 2 \log \varphi/\sqrt{5} \approx 0.430408$ [8, A086466], [33, p. 98], [99, p. 14 Table 22].

$L_8(2) := L_8(2, \chi_2) = 128^{-1/2} \pi^2$ the Dirichlet L -series of the non-principal character modulo 8 [8, A328895], [33, p. 98], [99, p. 14 Table 22].

A.2 Regularized infinite products.

Section A.2 outlines the notation, evaluation and references concerning the zeta-regularised infinite product of natural numbers, as well as the super-regularised product over all primes. Let us denote as $\prod_{k=1}^{\infty} k := \infty!$ the zeta-regularised infinite product of natural numbers [8, A000027] or Stirling’s approximation [8, A019727], [33, pp. 18 135–6]:

$$\prod_{k=1}^{\infty} k := 1 \times 2 \times 3 \times 4 \times 5 \times 6 \times 7 \times 8 \times \dots = \sqrt{2\pi} \tag{A.6}$$

We denote as $\prod_p p$ [8, A212002], [44, p. 73 Definition 1], [45, p. 3] the generalisation of the zeta-regularised infinite product of natural numbers [8, A000027], for which the following holds:

Theorem A.1. (Muñoz García and Pérez Marco [44, p. 78 Theorem 8]). *The super-regularised product over all prime numbers p is:*

$$\prod_p p := 1 \times 2 \times 3 \times 5 \times 7 \times 11 \times 13 \times 17 \times 19 \times \dots = 4\pi^2 \tag{A.7}$$

A.3 Plouffe constants P_A and P_γ .

We outline notation and expression of the Plouffe constants P_A and P_γ . Let us denote as P_A the constant Plouffe constant A [8, A086201]

$$P_A := \frac{1}{2\pi} \tag{A.8}$$

which has relationships to

Regularised infinite products $\prod_{k=1}^{\infty} k$ (A.6) [33, pp. 18 135–6], and $\prod_p p$ (A.7) [43, p. 78 Theorem 8].

Archimedes' constant π [8, A000796], [32, pp. 17–27].

Projection constant of 1-symmetric l_p^n -spaces $\forall p \in [1, 2]_{\mathbb{R}}$, on $\mathbb{F} = \mathbb{R}$, $c_{\mathbb{R}} = \sqrt{2/\pi} = 2\sqrt{P_A} = 2^{-1} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} [1 - \operatorname{erf}(x)^2] dx$ [8, A076668], [17, p. 2 Theorem 1].

Projection constant of 1-symmetric spaces l_p^n -spaces, $\forall p \in [1, 2]_{\mathbb{R}}$, over $\mathbb{F} = \mathbb{C}$, $c_{\mathbb{C}} = \sqrt{\pi}/2 = 1/\sqrt{8P_A}$ [8, A019704], [17, p. 2 Theorem 1], [32, p. 22].

Area $\sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi e}} = 2\sqrt{\frac{P_A}{e}}$ [8, A103647] of the largest rectangle of the normal distribution curve which defines the sharp lower bound $K_G^{\mathbb{R}}$ in $\mathcal{H} \in \mathbb{R}^{\infty}$ of the Grothendieck's inequality as presented in Davie's **Appendix D**, and Reeds' [19] article.

Error function $\operatorname{erf}(x)$ [32, pp. 262–4 289 364 423] and other invariants of mathematical statistics, geometric probability, and general optimisation.

Cycloid curves over $\mathbb{R}^2 \cong \mathbb{C}$. We may consider them as trajectories of movements composed of two uniform motions, linear and circular and linear, at the same speed. For example, cycloid, and centred-cycloids (epicycloid and hypocycloid).

Determinant $\det(\Delta_M^p)$ of the Laplacian Δ_M^p of the circle [121, pp. 601–22].

Those identities hold [32, pp. 430–3], [101, p. 226 (4.1c)], [122]:

$$\begin{aligned} 1 &= 2\pi P_A = P_A \det(\Delta_M^p) = P_A \left(\prod_{k=1}^{\infty} k \right)^2 = P_A \sqrt{\prod_p p} \\ &= 16 P_A \left(\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (1 - \operatorname{erf}(x)^2) dx \right)^{-1} = P_A \left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \operatorname{sech}^2 \left(\frac{2n-1}{2} \pi \right) \right)^{-1} \end{aligned} \tag{A.9}$$

Let us denote as P_γ the Plouffe constant γ [8, A086201], [37], [122]:

$$P_\gamma := \frac{1}{\pi} \arctan\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) = \frac{1}{\pi} \operatorname{arccot}(2) \tag{A.10}$$

A.4 Semifactorial, and type B Catalan numbers or central binomial coefficients.

Section A.4 explores infinite series involving the classical sequence of *type B Catalan numbers* or *central binomial coefficients* [8, A000984], [33, pp. 182–9], [34, p. 78], [51], [55]–[56], [103]–[105]. Over a century ago, Ramanujan [39, p. 83], [43, pp. 92–96] recorded similar formulas. However, their properties began to be studied only after Apéry used them in his proof of the irrationality of the Riemann zeta-functions $\zeta(2)$ and $\zeta(3)$ [42], [43, p. 92 (1.1) (1.2)]. Van der Poorten, Beukers, Zagier, Cohen and others called them *Apéry-type series* or *Apéry-like sums*. Around 1984, these series had expressions in terms of real Dirichlet L -series [43, p. 94 (1.11)]. Let us consider the set of binomial coefficients $\binom{n}{k} := \frac{n!}{k!(n-k)!}$ [39, pp. 1–12 89–102], [102]. Let us denote as $\binom{2n}{n}$ the subset of *central binomial coefficients*: $\binom{2n}{n} \subset \binom{n}{k}$. Let $C_n := c(n)$ denote the n^{th} classical Catalan number [8, A000108], [39]. Then, the central binomial coefficients are the central character of the type A Catalan number C_n :

$$\binom{2n}{n} := (n + 1)C_n \tag{A.11}$$

Thus, motivating Devadoss [38, p. 274] to call them *type B Catalan numbers*. Let us denote as $(2n - 1)!!$ the semifactorial, or $(2n - 1)$ double factorial. For $n \in [0, \infty)_{\mathbb{Z}}$, it has

Definition A.3.

$$(2n - 1)!! := \frac{(2n)!}{2^n n!} \Big|_{n \in [0, \infty)_{\mathbb{Z}}} = 1 \times 3 \times 5 \times \dots \times (2n - 5)(2n - 3)(2n - 1) \tag{A.12}$$

Example A.4. The $(2n)^{\text{th}}$ moment of the normal distribution, for $n \in [0, \infty)_{\mathbb{Z}}, x \in (-\infty, \infty)_{\mathbb{R}}$

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{x^{2n}}{e^{x^2/2}} dx = \sqrt{P} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{x^{2n}}{e^{x^2/2}} dx = (2n - 1)!! \tag{A.13}$$

Remark A.5. (A.13) has alternative forms based on the semifactorial (A.12) via

- (i) Plouffe constant P_A (A.8–9) [37], [122];
- (ii) determinant $\det(\Delta_M^p)$ of the Laplacian Δ_M^p of the circle [121, pp. 601–22];

(iii) zeta-regularized infinite product of natural numbers [8, A000027] or Stirling’s formula or Stirling’s approximation $\prod_{k=1}^{\infty} k$ [8, A019727], [33, pp. 18 135–6] (A.6);

(iv) super-regularized product over all primes $\prod_p p$ [44, p. 78 Theorem 8], [27, p. 3], (A.7)

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x^{2n} e^{-\frac{x^2}{2}} dx \Big|_{n \in [0, \infty)_{\mathbb{Z}}; x \in (-\infty, \infty)_{\mathbb{R}}} = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \sqrt{\frac{x^{4n}}{e^{x^2}}} dx = \sqrt{2\pi}(2n - 1)!! = \frac{(2n - 1)!!}{\sqrt{P_A}} \tag{A.14}$$

$$= \frac{(2n - 1)!!}{\sqrt{\det(\Delta_M^p)}} = (2n - 1)!! / \sqrt[4]{\prod_p p} = (2n - 1)!! \prod_{k=1}^{\infty} k \tag{A.15}$$

The elements of the set of type B Catalan numbers or central binomial coefficients have:

Definition A.6.

$$\binom{2n}{n} := \frac{(2n)!}{(n!)^2} \Big|_{n \in [0, \infty)_{\mathbb{Z}}} = \frac{2^n}{n!} (2n - 1)!! \tag{A.16}$$

Example A.7. Coefficients:

$$\sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k}^2$$

of the power series expansion [8, A000984], [39, p. 28]:

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - 4x}} \Big|_{x \in]-1/4, 1/4[_{\mathbb{R}}} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \binom{2n}{n} x^n = 1 + 2x + 6x^2 + 20x^3 + 70x^4 + \dots \tag{A.17}$$

generated based on the binomial theorem, upper-bounded as $\binom{2n}{n} < 4^{n-1}$. The infinite sequence of coefficients in (A.17), includes both $(\infty - 1)$ composite numbers and the Gauß-Heegner point $H_2 = 2$ [87, pp. 109–70 320–3 449 796–7] which, iff $n = 1$, enables (A.17) to generate:

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \binom{2}{1} x = 2x \tag{A.18}$$

Appendix B. Pisot-Vijayaraghavan number $1 + \sqrt{2}$.

We characterize the Pisot-Vijayaraghavan number $1 + \sqrt{2}$ in **Conjecture 1.1**, **Theorem 1.2**, **Corollary 1.3**, **Lemma 1.4**, **Theorem 1.5** and **Remark 1.6**. Then, we show certain representations of the natural logarithm of $1 + \sqrt{2}$.

B.1 $1 + \sqrt{2}$ is an element of the Pisot-Vijayaraghavan subset of Parry numbers.

Section D.1 defines Pisot-Vijayaraghavan numbers. In 1912, Thue discovered the set of numbers today known as Pisot-Vijayaraghavan numbers [45], [83, pp. 9–16] which form a closed subset of Parry numbers [85]. Parry numbers have that:

Definition B.2. Algebraic integer numbers [48] denoted β , where:

- (i) The orbit of 1 under the transformation $x \mapsto x\beta \pmod{1}$ is finite [85], and
- (ii) the algebraic conjugate $\bar{\beta} < \varphi$ [8, A001622].

We refer the reader to Fomenko's and Fuchs' [72] treatise for the properties of closed sets and -subsets and their relation to topological spaces. Pisot-Vijayaraghavan numbers are usually denoted by either of these symbols α , β or θ . These numbers have a small Mahler measure and tend to satisfy a large number of cyclotomic equations. Their quadratic subset has that:

Definition B.3. Algebraic integer numbers $\alpha \in]1, \infty)_{\mathbb{C} \setminus \bar{\mathbb{Q}}}$ [48], whose minimal, irreducible, monic, real, univariate, quadratic polynomial is:

$$\alpha^2 - p\alpha \pm q \Big|_{p \in]1, \infty)_{\mathbb{N}}; q \in \mathbb{Z} \setminus \{0\}; \alpha \in]1, \infty)_{\mathbb{C} \setminus \bar{\mathbb{Q}}}; |\bar{\alpha}| \in]0, 1[_{\mathbb{C} \setminus \bar{\mathbb{Q}}}} \quad (\text{B.1})$$

Let us denote as $\alpha_2 \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} 1 + \sqrt{2} = [2; \bar{2}] \in \mathbb{C} \setminus \bar{\mathbb{Q}} \subset \mathcal{P} \subset \mathbb{C}$ the algebraic number of degree 2 [48], known as the *silver ratio* [8, A014176], which satisfies the Pisot-Vijayaraghavan minimal, irreducible, monic polynomial $\alpha^2 - 2\alpha - 1$ [45], [83, pp. 9–16].

In the special case $(p, q) = (2, -1)$, α_2 is the positive root of (B.1). **Conjecture 1.1** (1.2), **Theorem 1.2** (1.4–5), **Lemma 1.4** (1.7), **Theorem 1.5** (1.8), and **Remark 1.6** (1.11) involve an elementary function of the Pisot-Vijayaraghavan number α_2 [8, A014176], [45]:

$$\log(\alpha_2) := \log(1 + \sqrt{2}) \quad (\text{B.2})$$

because $\sinh(\pi/2)$ factors out both upper bounds of Grothendieck's [1, p. 47] main result, and the identity $\operatorname{arcsinh}(1) = \log(1 + \sqrt{2})$ holds. For $\gamma \in]0, \infty)_{\mathbb{R}}$, $s \in \mathbb{C}$ representations include [94]

$$\sinh\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right) = -\frac{i}{\sqrt{8}}\sqrt{\frac{\pi}{8}} \int_{\gamma-i\infty}^{\gamma+i\infty} \frac{e^{\frac{\pi^2}{16s}+s}}{s^{\frac{3}{2}}} ds = \left(\frac{i}{\sqrt{2}}\right)^3 \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{8}} \int_{\gamma-i\infty}^{\gamma+i\infty} \frac{e^{\frac{\pi^2}{16s}+s}}{s^{\frac{3}{2}}} ds \tag{B.3}$$

where the radical factor $\sqrt{\pi/8}$ [8, A217841] is the square root of [8, A019675], [32, p. 492] whose reciprocal has a closed-form expression $\sqrt{8/\pi} = 4P_A$ with the Plouffe constant P_A (see section A.3). Moreover, $L_4(1) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} L_4(1, \chi_2) = 4^{-1}\pi$ is the Dirichlet L -series of the non-principal character modulo 4 [8, A003881], [33, pp. 97–112], [41], [99, p. 14 Table 22], whose square $\pi^2/16 \approx 0.61685$ [8, A222068] representations include:

- the inverse tangent function of Fibonacci numbers sequence $\{F_n\}_0^\infty$ [8, A000045], [81, p. 754];
- elementary functions of the Apéry-type series with reciprocals of central binomial coefficients or type B Catalan numbers [8, A111003] and of the projection constant of 1-symmetric spaces l_p^n -spaces, $\forall p \in [1, 2]_{\mathbb{R}}$, $c_{\mathbb{C}} = \sqrt{\pi}/2$ [8, A019704], [17, p. 2 Theorem 1], [32, p. 22], [113];
- the fourth power of the projection constant of 1-symmetric spaces l_p^n -spaces, $\forall p \in [1, 2]_{\mathbb{R}}$, over $\mathbb{F} = \mathbb{C}$, $c_{\mathbb{C}} = \sqrt{\pi}/2$ [8, A019704], [17, p. 2 Theorem 1], [32, p. 22]:

$$L_4(1)^2 = \frac{\pi^2}{16} = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (-1)^{k+1} \arctan\left(\frac{1}{F_{2k+1}}\right) \arctan\left(\frac{3}{F_{2k-1}}\right) \tag{B.4}$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{2^k}{k^2} \binom{2n}{n}^{-1} = c_{\mathbb{C}}^4 \tag{B.5}$$

For $\gamma \in]0, \infty[_{\mathbb{R}}$, $s \in \mathbb{C}$ and $z := i/\sqrt{2} \in \mathbb{C}$, the contour integral representations of (B.3) include

$$\sinh\left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right) = \frac{z^3}{\sqrt{2}} \sqrt{L_4(1)} \int_{\gamma-i\infty}^{\gamma+i\infty} e^{\frac{L_4(1)^2}{s}+s} s^{-\frac{3}{2}} ds \tag{B.6}$$

$$= \frac{z^3}{\sqrt{2}} \sqrt{L_4(1)} \int_{\gamma-i\infty}^{\gamma+i\infty} \exp\left(\frac{1}{2s} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{2^k}{k^2} \binom{2n}{n}^{-1} + s\right) s^{-\frac{3}{2}} ds \tag{B.7}$$

$$= \frac{z^3}{\sqrt{2}} \sqrt{L_4(1)} \int_{\gamma-i\infty}^{\gamma+i\infty} \exp\left(\frac{1}{s} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (-1)^{k+1} \arctan\left(\frac{1}{F_{2k+1}}\right) \arctan\left(\frac{3}{F_{2k-1}}\right) + s\right) s^{-\frac{3}{2}} ds \tag{B.8}$$

B.2 Representations of the natural logarithm of $1 + \sqrt{2}$.

Table 2. Integral, contour integral, series, generalised hypergeometric, inverse trigonometric and hyperbolic functions representations of the natural logarithm $\log(1 + \sqrt{2}) \in \mathbb{C} \setminus \mathbb{A} \subset \mathcal{P} \subset \mathbb{C}$.

n	$\log(1 + \sqrt{2})$	Reference
1	$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \frac{\arctan z}{z} \Big _{z=i/\sqrt{2}}$	[114]
2	$\operatorname{arccoth}(\sqrt{2})$	[114]
3	$\operatorname{arctanh}\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\right)$	[114]
4	$\frac{1}{2} {}_3F_2\left(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{4}, \frac{5}{4}; \frac{3}{2}, \frac{3}{2}; 1\right)$	[61, p. 92 Table 2 (7.4.4.179a)]
5	$\frac{\sqrt{8}}{3} {}_3F_2\left(\frac{1}{4}, \frac{3}{4}, 1; \frac{5}{4}, \frac{7}{4}; -1\right)$	[61, p. 90 (7.4.5.34)]
6	$\sqrt{{}_3F_2\left(1, 1, 1; \frac{3}{2}; 2; -1\right)}$	[61, p. 93 Table 2 (7.4.5.74a)]
7	$\int_0^{\pi/4} \sec t \, dt$	[114]
8	$\int_0^1 \frac{x^{\sqrt{2}} - 1}{\log(x)} \, dx$	[8, A091648]
9	$\sqrt{2} \int_0^{\pi/2} \frac{\sin^2(x)}{\sin(x) + \cos(x)} \, dx$	[125, p. 64 (2.2.c)]
10	$\frac{i}{\sqrt{32\pi^3}} \int_{\gamma-i\infty}^{\gamma+i\infty} 2^s \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2} - s\right) \Gamma(1-s) \Gamma(s)^2 \, ds \Big _{\gamma \in]0, 1/2[_{\mathbb{R}}}$	[114]
11	$\frac{1}{\sqrt{8}} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \operatorname{Res}_{s=-j} \left(\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2} - s\right) \Gamma(1-s) \Gamma(s) \right) \left(\left(-\frac{1}{2}\right)^s \Gamma\left(\frac{3}{2} - s\right) \right)^{-1}$	[114]
12	$a_0 \left(\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (1 - \operatorname{erf}(x)^2) \, dx \right)^{-1}$	[21, p. 2 (7)], [63, p. xxxiv]

Appendix C. Euler-Kronecker constant γ_8 of the global field $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{8})$.

We introduce the Euler-Kronecker constant γ_8 of the global field $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{8})$ [40, pp. 291–440] as applied in Section 2.8. In 2021, Languasco [97] has demonstrated methods to evaluate Euler-Kronecker constants for prime cyclotomic fields. Recently, Moree and Languasco [98] have connected Dirichlet L -series [33, pp. 97–112], [41], [91, pp. 95–144], [99], arithmetic-geometric mean, Hurwitz zeta-function and Euler constant. Let us denote as $\gamma_8 \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ the Euler-Kronecker constant of the global field $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{8})$ [33, p. 103], [36, pp. 407–58], as $\{R(1/8); R(3/8); R(5/8); R(7/8)\}$ special values of R -functions [33, p. 104], [97, p. 6 (15–6)] and as P_A the Plouffe constant A (see section A.3). Let us denote as γ the Stieltjes constant $\gamma_K = \gamma_{\mathbb{Q}} = \gamma_0$ of the number field $K = \mathbb{Q}$, called Euler-Mascheroni constant [8, A001620], [32, pp. 28–39], [34, pp. 4–6], [35] and as λ the Pisot-Vijayaraghavan number $\lambda = 17 + 12\sqrt{2}$ [8, A156164], [42, p. 13], [43], [45], [87, pp. 784–6]. Then

$$\gamma_8 := \log(2\pi e^{2\gamma}) + \frac{R\left(\frac{1}{8}\right) - R\left(\frac{3}{8}\right) - R\left(\frac{5}{8}\right) + R\left(\frac{7}{8}\right)}{2 \log(1 + \sqrt{2})} \tag{C.1}$$

$$= \frac{\log(17 + 12\sqrt{2}) + 2 \log(1 + \sqrt{2}) \log(2\pi\gamma) + R\left(\frac{1}{8}\right) - R\left(\frac{3}{8}\right) - R\left(\frac{5}{8}\right) + R\left(\frac{7}{8}\right)}{\log(3 + \sqrt{8})} \tag{C.2}$$

$$= \frac{\log \lambda \left(1 + \sqrt{\frac{\gamma}{P_A}}\right) + R\left(\frac{1}{8}\right) - R\left(\frac{3}{8}\right) - R\left(\frac{5}{8}\right) + R\left(\frac{7}{8}\right)}{\log \sqrt{\lambda}} \tag{C.3}$$

$$= 2 + \sqrt{8\pi\gamma} + \frac{R\left(\frac{1}{8}\right) - R\left(\frac{3}{8}\right) - R\left(\frac{5}{8}\right) + R\left(\frac{7}{8}\right)}{\log \sqrt{\lambda}} \tag{C.4}$$

$$= 2 \left(1 + \sqrt{\frac{\gamma}{P_A}}\right) + \frac{R\left(\frac{1}{8}\right) - R\left(\frac{3}{8}\right) - R\left(\frac{5}{8}\right) + R\left(\frac{7}{8}\right)}{\log \sqrt{\lambda}} \tag{C.5}$$

$$\approx 1.20933063094138118664026424093547097334700909059315456011578210585217390057 \tag{C.6}$$

Appendix D. Lower bound for real Grothendieck constant $K_G^{\mathbb{R}}$.

by Alexander Munro Davie (1984). Based on ideas of Haagerup, it holds that:

Theorem D.1. (Davie [113]).

$$K_G^{\mathbb{R}} \geq \sup_{0 < \alpha \leq 1} \frac{1 - \rho(\alpha)}{\max(\rho(\alpha), F_{\rho(\alpha)}(\alpha))} \quad (\text{D.1})$$

where F and ρ are defined by, respectively (D.16) and (D.17) below.

Proof. For $n \in \mathbb{N}$ let S_n denote the unit sphere in \mathbb{R}^n , let σ_n denote the normalised area measure on S_n , and let B_n denote the set of all measurable real functions f on S_n such that $|f(x)| \leq 1$ for all $x \in S_n$. Let us denote as $\rho \in [0, 1]_{\mathbb{R}}$ and define:

$$M_{\rho,n} = \sup_{f,g \in B_n} \left| n \int \int f(y)g(x) \langle x, y \rangle d\sigma_n(x)d\sigma_n(y) - \rho \int f(x)g(x)d\sigma_n(x) \right| \quad (\text{D.2})$$

Then:

$$K_G^{\mathbb{R}} M_{\rho,n} \geq \left| n \int \int \langle x, y \rangle^2 d\sigma_n(x)d\sigma_n(y) - \rho \int |x|^2 d\sigma_n(x) \right| = 1 - \rho \quad (\text{D.3})$$

If we define $M_{\rho} = \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} M_{\rho,n}$ then it follows that:

$$\forall \rho : K_G^{\mathbb{R}} M_{\rho} \geq 1 - \rho \quad (\text{D.4})$$

Hence:

$$K_G^{\mathbb{R}} \geq \sup_{0 \leq \rho \leq 1} \frac{1 - \rho}{M_{\rho}} \quad (\text{D.5})$$

We now seek an upper bound for M_{ρ} . Fix $f, g \in B$ and let:

$$h(x) = \int \langle x, y \rangle f(y) d\sigma_n(y) \quad (\text{D.6})$$

Then h is linear and so there is $z \in S$ and $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}$ so that $\forall x \in \mathbb{R}^n : h(x) = \lambda \langle x, z \rangle$. We have:

$$\lambda = h(z) = \int \langle z, y \rangle f(y) d\sigma_n(y) \quad (\text{D.7})$$

Let:

$$\mu = \int \langle z, x \rangle g(x) dx \quad (\text{D. 8})$$

Then:

$$\int \int f(y)g(x) \langle x, y \rangle d\sigma_n(x)d\sigma_n(y) = \mu\lambda \leq \frac{(\lambda + \mu)^2}{4} \quad (\text{D. 9})$$

and since:

$$\lambda + \mu \leq \int (f(x) + g(x))\langle x, z \rangle d\sigma_n(x) \quad (\text{D. 10})$$

it follows, choosing coordinates so that $z = (1, 0, \dots, 0)$, that:

$$M_{\rho, n} \leq \sup_{f, g \in B} \left\{ \frac{n}{4} \left[\int (f(x) + g(x))x_1 d\sigma_n(x) \right]^2 - \rho \int f(x)g(x) d\sigma_n(x) \right\} \quad (\text{D. 11})$$

and then, writing:

$$\phi(x) = \frac{1 + f(x)g(x)}{2} \quad (\text{D. 12})$$

we have:

$$M_{\rho, n} \leq \sup_{\phi \in A} \left\{ n \left(\int \phi(x)|x_1| d\sigma_n(x) \right)^2 + \rho \left(1 - 2 \int \phi d\sigma_n \right) \right\} \quad (\text{D. 13})$$

where A is the set of measurable $\phi \in [0, 1]_{\mathbb{R}}$. For a given value of $\int \phi d\sigma_n$, the expression on the right will be maximised by choosing $\phi = 1$ when $|x_1| > \lambda$ and $\phi = 0$ otherwise, for appropriate λ . Hence,

$$M_{\rho, n} \leq \sup_{\lambda > 0} \left\{ n \left(\int_{|x_1| > \lambda} |x_1| d\sigma_n \right)^2 + \rho \left(1 - 2\sigma_n(\{x : |x_1| > \lambda\}) \right) \right\} \quad (\text{D. 14})$$

Next, it is not hard to show that as $n \rightarrow \infty$ the distribution of $\sqrt{n}x_1$ under σ_n tends to standard normal, and we have:

$$\sqrt{n} \int_{\sqrt{n}|x_1| > \alpha} |x_1| d\sigma_n \longrightarrow \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} \frac{1}{e^{\frac{\alpha^2}{2}}} \quad (\text{D.15})$$

Then, letting $n \rightarrow \infty$ in (D.14) gives $M_\rho \leq \sup_{\alpha > 0} F_\rho(\alpha)$ where:

$$F_\rho(\alpha) = \frac{2}{\pi} \frac{1}{e^{\frac{\alpha^2}{2}}} + \rho \left(1 - \sqrt{\frac{8}{\pi}} \int_0^\infty \frac{1}{e^{\frac{x^2}{2}}} dx \right) \quad (\text{D.16})$$

Consideration of the derivative of F_ρ shows that if $\rho \geq \sqrt{2/\pi e}$ then F_ρ is monotone increasing, and its supremum is ρ , whereas if $0 \leq \rho < \sqrt{2/\pi e}$ then F_ρ has a local maximum at the smaller root (the root in $]0, 1]_{\mathbb{R}}$) of $\rho = \sqrt{2/\pi} \alpha e^{-\alpha^2/2}$; its supremum is the greater of ρ and its value at this maximum. It follows that if $\alpha \in]0, 1]_{\mathbb{R}}$ and if:

$$\rho = \rho(\alpha) := \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} \frac{\alpha}{e^{\frac{\alpha^2}{2}}} \quad (\text{D.17})$$

then:

$$M_\rho \leq \max(\rho, F_\rho(\alpha)) \quad (\text{D.18})$$

Hence:

$$K_G^{\mathbb{R}} \geq \sup_{0 < \alpha \leq 1} \frac{1 - \rho(\alpha)}{\max(\rho(\alpha), F_{\rho(\alpha)}(\alpha))} \quad (\text{D.19})$$

The claim follows. ■

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